

75th Conference

25-27 November 2024

75 years in the service of plant breeding -
From chi-square to genomic selection

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Raumberg-Gumpenstein

75 Years in the service of plant breeding
- From chi-square to genomic selection

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A century in service of plant breeding: Austrian plant breeding associations and their annual meetings

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In November 2024, Saatgut Austria, the *Vereinigung der Pflanzzüchter und Saatgutkaufleute Österreichs*, celebrated its 75th Annual Conference in Raumberg-Gumpenstein. Including the 25 annual meetings of the forerunner organisation, the *Gesellschaft für Pflanzzüchtung Wien*, it would have been indeed the centenary scientific meeting of Austrian plant breeders. In the following a chronological review on the history of these meetings is given.

The “Z” (1912-1938)

The *Gesellschaft für Pflanzzüchtung Wien* (from 1917 onwards also known by its official short form “Z”) was founded on 26th October 1912 by 50 members. Initiator of the association was Carl Fruwirth (1862-1930), at that time associate professor at the *Technische Universität Wien*, chair for agriculture and forestry. The first president of the association was Emanuel Ritter von Proskowetz (1849-1944). Fruwirth’s idea was, to bring all plant breeders of the Austrian-Hungarian empire together for the exchange of knowledge and, thus, enable progress in the development of varieties and the multiplication and certification of seeds. Role model were already existing similar associations in Germany, the United States and Canada.

„Er [der Verein, ed.] soll den Züchtern einen engen Zusammenschluß ermöglichen, wie ihn derartige Vereinigungen in Deutschland, in den Vereinigten Staaten, in Kanada schon seit längerer Zeit bieten.“ (Carl Fruwirth, 1912)

The first general assembly of the “Z” was on 1st March 1913 at the *Zentralverein für Rübenzuckerindustrie*, Elisabethstr. 18, Vienna (Palais Mayr ex Bloch-Bauer¹). The annual membership at that time was 200 Kronen which are of equivalent value of 1437 € by 2025². In the same year, Fruwirth established the *Zeitschrift für Pflanzzüchtung* (since 1986 named „Plant Breeding”) as the official organ of the *Österreichischen Gesellschaft für Pflanzzüchtung*, the *Gesellschaft zur Förderung deutscher Pflanzzüchtung* and the *Bayerischen Saatzüchtvereins* (Wricke & Röbbelen, 1988). Also in 1913, the first three varieties (*i.e.* Original Loosdorfer Frühgerste “Laa”, Original Loosdorfer Frühgerste “Zaya”, Proskowetz-Original-Hanna-Pedigree-Saatgerste) were registered in the *Zuchtbuch* (Fig. 1) which was managed by the “Z” under the aegis of Fruwirth.

Figure 1 Carl Fruwirth, founder of the *Gesellschaft für Pflanzzüchtung Wien* (“Z”; Austrian Association for Plant Breeding) and the *Zeitschrift für Pflanzzüchtung* (today Plant Breeding by Wiley-VCH), and first accountant of the *Zuchtbuch*. The trademark was registered on 8th February 1913 at the *Wiener Handels- und Gewerbekammer* and was used for seeds of varieties registered in the *Zuchtbuch* (variety list) of the association.

After the Great War, the association continued their work and general assemblies were held more or less annually despite that the members were now allocated in different countries and traveling between the successor states of the Habsburg empire was sometimes painful. In 1936, the Ministry of Agriculture took over the management of the “Zuchtbuch”. At the general assembly held in June 1937 at the Academy of Sciences, Vienna, the association celebrated its 25th anniversary. Until then, the association held 22 general assemblies, 10 of them outside Vienna (Table 1). The end of the “Z” came in March 1938 with the Austrian Anschluss to Nazi Germany and the integration of the association into the *Reichsverband der deutschen Pflanzzüchtbetriebe*.

Restart after 1945: Vienna, Admont and Trautenfels

In 1947, the *Bundesversuchsanstalt für alpine Landwirtschaft* (BAL) was established in Admont where a workshop on recent developments in field testing was organized in 1949. The big interest and success of this workshop encouraged the Austrian plant breeding

Table 1 General assemblies held by the “Z” between 1912 and 1938. For detailed dates and programmes see Tschermak-Seysenegg (1937) and the “Vereinsnachrichten” published regularly in issues of the *Zeitschrift für Pflanzenzüchtung*.

Location	Country ¹	Year
Vienna	Austria	1913, 1916, 1918, 1921, 1923, 1925, 1927, 1931, 1933, 1935, 1936, 1937
Prague	Czech Republic	1914
Brno	Czech Republic	1917, 1932
Graz	Austria	1920
Klosterneuburg	Austria	1922
Győr	Hungary	1924
Linz	Austria	1926
Weihenstephan	Germany	1929
Magyaróvár	Hungary	1930
Krakow & Warszawa	Poland	1934

¹ at the time of the general assemblies, 1914 and 1917, respectively, Prague and Brno were still part of Austria-Hungary; in 1932, Brno was part of former Czechoslovakia.

community to re-establish a regular, annual meeting for knowledge exchange. Finally, in 1950, Ladislaus Michael Kopetz (1902-1966), head of the *Institut für Pflanzenbau und Pflanzenzüchtung* of the *Hochschule für Bodenkultur*, and Felix Mainx (1900-1983), head of the *Institut für Allgemeine Biologie* of the University of Vienna, organized the first official annual meeting of the *Arbeitsgemeinschaft der Saatzuchtleiter* (then chaired by Josef Bogner; 1899-1974) within the *Vereinigung österreichischer Saatzüchter* (then chaired by Ferdinand Piatti; 1898-1980) in Vienna. Due to limited resources at the involved universities, the host and place for the 2nd meeting in 1951 was again the BAL in Admont. Alfred Zeller (1908-1976) welcomed from 9-11 February the first participants to 17 presentations dealing with plant breeding in the former Soviet Union, cereal breeding including recent developments in cytogenetics, heterosis and breeding of vegetables, new results in virus research, fertilization and weed science; most of the presentations were given by researchers of the BAL. At the 3rd meeting in 1952, the first foreign participant, Dieter von Reininghaus from Bavaria, Germany, attended the conference. In 1953, the Republic of Austria decided to move the BAL from Admont to Gumpenstein and, thus, the conference in 1954 was the last one in Admont. As adequate rooms were not yet available in Gumpenstein, the 1955 conference from 18-20 January took place in the castle of Trautenfels.

„In diesem Bestreben [beständig ertragreiche und qualitativ hochwertige Sorten für die österreichische Landwirtschaft zu entwickeln; ed.] „schrecken“ sie, die sich vorwiegend mit der lebendigen Materie verbunden fühlen und, wie die Vortragsthemen zur Genüge beweisen, selbst davor nicht zurück, auch scheinbar toten mathematischen Problemen ihre gebührende Reverenz zu erweisen. Ist doch die Pflanzenzüchtung als angewandte Genetik heute mehr denn je darauf angewiesen, lassen sich doch diese Gesetzmässigkeiten nur in Zahlen ausdrücken.“ (Alfred Buchinger, 1952)

Gumpenstein: from 1956 to today

While the first six conferences took place in January and February, the 7th conference and the first one at the new site of BAL in Gumpenstein was organized from 22-24 November with an official opening ceremony of the new BAL facilities on the last day of the conference. Part of this ceremony was the disclosure of a memorial stone in remembrance of the 90th anniversary of Gregor Mendel’s publication on the hybridization of peas (Mendel, 1866). This first conference at the new site in Gumpenstein saw also a significant increase in participants from neighbouring Germany with attendees from Braunschweig, Göttingen, Hannover, Hohenheim, Köln-Voglsang and Weihenstephan. The Austrian State Treaty and Declaration of Neutrality in 1955, made the annual conferences at Gumpenstein to a preferred meeting place for researchers from the West and Eastern Bloc countries (*i.e.* Bulgaria, Czechoslovakia, German Democratic Republic, Hungary, Romania and Yugoslavia) from the 1960s onwards. By 2024, participants and presenters from more than 20 countries (*i.e.* Austria, Belgium, Bulgaria, Croatia, Czechia, Czechoslovakia, Denmark, France, Germany, German Democratic Republic, Hungary, Ireland, Italy, the Netherlands, Norway, Poland, Romania, Serbia, Slovakia, Slovenia, Spain, Sweden, Switzerland, United Kingdom, United States, Yugoslavia) attended the conferences. Nearly half of the presenters over all decades were from Germany, followed by Austrian researchers who contributed to more than 25% of the presentations. The most diligent speaker at the conferences was Prof. Hermann Hänsel (1918-2005) who gave talks at 35 conferences, in some years he contributed to the success of the meetings with even more than one presentation.

Over decades, the character of the conferences changed: presentations on vegetable and maize breeding, and by commercial plant breeders became rare, while presentations by researchers and on cereal species became dominant. A majority of presentations focused on breeding for resistance and end-use quality, respectively (Fig. 2). The advance of molecular techniques, use of marker-assisted selection and genome analysis had a major impact on presentations in recent years.

Figure 2 Resistance breeding was a main topic in presentations given at the *Arbeitstagung* since its beginning despite that some researchers complained in the early days that some diseases are often ignored due to the use of pesticides. Illustration from Pichler (1953) displaying **a** healthy wheat spike, **b** common bunt infected spike, **c** healthy grains, **d** bunt sori, and **e** spores of common bunt (manifold 1000 times).

“Auf die Resistenz einer Sorte wird aber bei uns noch immer viel zu wenig geachtet, ja gegen manche Krankheiten, wie z.B. Steinbrand oft als überflüssig erklärt” (Friedrich Pichler, 1953)

New developments in experimental designs and statistical analysis of field trials (Fig. 3) was the original motivation by the *Arbeitsgemeinschaft der Saatzuchtleiter* to organize workshops. Today, the analysis of big data from phenomics and genomics plays an eminent role in integrated plant breeding. Some of the ‘ancient’ presentations are still relevant or of new relevance in view of recent trends. For example, the development of multi-line varieties with different resistance sources/genes against multiple diseases (*Konvergenzzüchtung*) has new perspectives with respect to recent regulations that made the marketing of propagating material with a high level of genetic diversity possible, but also in view of the need of varieties tolerant to multiple stresses and enhanced resilience associated with climate change.

Keywords

Austria · end-use quality · plant breeding history · resistance breeding

Figure 3 Illustrations of resolvable experimental designs from the presentation of Jähnl (1952).

“Nicht jeder Versuch kann nach der Varianzanalyse ausgewertet werden. Das muss schon bei der Anlage berücksichtigt werden. [...] Vor allem müssen die Versuche so angelegt werden, dass alle zufälligen äusseren Einflüsse die Versuchsobjekte durchaus unregelmässig treffen.”

“Das sind einige Beispiele für Anordnungen die wirksamer sind als ungeordnete Blocks und die trotz hoher Sortenzahl nur kleine Blocks enthalten.” (Gertrud Jähnl, 1952)

References

- Jähnl G (1952) Einige mit Hilfe der Varianzanalyse auswertbare Versuchsanordnungen. Ber Arbeitstag 1952, pp 195-206. BAL Admont.
- Mendel G (1866) Versuche über Pflanzen-Hybriden. Verhandlungen des Naturforschenden Vereins zu Brünn 4:3-47. <https://vlp.mpiwg-berlin.mpg.de/library/data/lit26745>
- Pichler F (1953) Über die Anfälligkeit verschiedener Getreidesorten gegen Krankheiten. Ber Arbeitstag 1953, pp 5-14. BAL Admont.
- Tschermak-Seysenegg E (1937) Zum 25jährigen Bestehen der Gesellschaft für Pflanzenzüchtung „Z“ Wien. Der Züchter 9:137-144. DOI: 10.1007/BF01878547
- Wricke G, Röbbelen G (1988) 75 years 100 volumes 1913-1988 Zeitschrift für Pflanzenzüchtung/Plant Breeding. Plant Breed 100: ix-xv. DOI: 10.1111/j.1439-0523.1988.tb00211.x

¹ Ferdinand Bloch (1864-1945) was a Bohemian sugar factory owner who married Adele Bauer (1881-1925) in 1899. From then on the couple carried the common family name Bloch-Bauer. The Bloch-Bauers were art lovers and financed especially Gustav Klimt who portrayed Adele several times (1901: Judith I; 1907: Adele Bloch Bauer I; 1909: Judith II; 1912: Adele Bloch-Bauer II), and Oskar Kokoschka who portrayed Ferdinand in 1936. F. Bloch-Bauer fled at first to Prag and finally to Zurich when the Nazis occupied Austria and Czechoslovakia, respectively, and confiscated all his estates. He died in poverty shortly after the end of WW II. Over decades, the surviving heir fought for the restitution of five Klimt paintings, among them Adele Bloch-Bauer I (known as the “Woman in gold”) from the original family’s property. See <https://www.neuegalerie.org/womaningold>

² Historischer Währungsrechner (historic currency converter) der Österreichischen Nationalbank, Wien: <https://finanzbildung.oenb.at/docroot/waehrungsrechner/#/>

Perspectives of a mid-sized family enterprise in modern seed industry

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Abstract

Today, Probstdorfer Saatzucht is a family-owned and family-managed enterprise and as such part of the Mauthner company group based in Vienna. Probstdorfer Saatzucht is looking back on a 77-year-old history of internal and external changes, challenges, hard achieved successes, bold decisions and significant people.

The beginning was in 1947 under the ownership of the family Baron von Thavonat. The region around Probstdorf, the so-called Marchfeld, had always played an important role in Vienna's food supply. The success of Probstdorfer's cereal varieties is firmly linked with the legendary breeder Prof. Hermann Hänsel. Under his leadership, between 1951 and 1988, the breeding programmes of spring barley, winter wheat and durum wheat set new benchmarks. Even today one of his last winter wheat varieties, 'Capo' (registered in 1989), enjoys highest market shares among organic farmers.

In 1970, the entrepreneur Fritz Mauthner, a school colleague of Prof. Hänsel, acquired Probstdorfer Saatzucht and over the following 20 years they together leveraged the genetic achievements into economic success: winter common wheat and spring durum wheat breeding programmes were intensified, the seed processing capacities were expanded on industrial level, and the KWS maize seed brand was introduced in Austria.

In the 1990s, Probstdorfer started the collaboration in hybrid maize seed production with Pioneer, that is still thriving today. After Austria's accession to the EU common market and the consequent changes in the year 2000, Probstdorfer merged its breeding activities with Saatbau Linz in the 50/50 joint venture Saatzucht Donau. Following the EU east expansion after 2000, Probstdorfer set foot in the CEE markets and internationalized its business over Europe. In 2009, Saatzucht Donau started its soybean breeding programme and Probstdorfer intensively engaged in the seed production and market development of this decisive crop. In 2014, Probstdorfer and Saatbau expanded their breeding collaboration on sunflower breeding in Romania with the company Donau Saat.

Learning from its own history and analyzing the ever-changing, competitive seed market, there are important perspectives and lessons for Probstdorfer worth mentioning:

The seed business has become a concert of multinational corporations and cooperatives. As mid-sized family company, Probstdorfer cannot compete with them on all levels and has to con-

sciously allocate its resources. The breeding know-how is outsourced in Saatzucht Donau. Hence, Probstdorfer is setting its focus on the practical aspects of variety developments and seed production.

Thanks to its co-ownership in important breeding programmes (*inter alia* winter common and durum wheat, winter barley, soybean), Probstdorfer holds a relevant and independent market position toward licensing partners. On the Austrian home market, Probstdorfer is a full portfolio provider. The brand is promoted and driven by leading varieties in key crops. This market position is enhanced by the personal touch of a family-run company, that is maintaining eye-level relationships with all stakeholders.

As Probstdorfer's genetics are predominantly royalty crops, a direct commercialization in foreign markets is hardly calculating, especially in CEE countries. Hence, Probstdorfer mainly commercializes its varieties in other countries via long-lasting license partnerships with local companies. Only in Hungary and Croatia, Probstdorfer is running own subsidiaries in combination with commodity trading. In Romania and Ukraine, Probstdorfer established joint ventures with local partners or Saatbau Linz, respectively.

The focus on qualitative and reliable seed production has proven to be a key element of success, especially in market periods without genetical competitive advantage. This comprises long-term partnerships with reliable seed multiplication farmers, constant investments in the processing technologies and motivated employees. Together, these factors constitute an integral part of the brand image and strengthen the internal and external brand loyalty.

As mid-sized private company competing with considerable bigger market participants, Probstdorfer must have a clear picture of its strengths and weaknesses. It is not afraid of transparency in numerous collaborations with other market players, which has manifested in three long-term strategic partnerships, each on one level of the value chain: Breeding – seed production – sales and logistics.

Probstdorfer's emotionally engaged owner family has proven to be an advantage in difficult phases. First, not each decision is driven by KPIs but more by cross-generational considerations. Still a careful watch on finances and liquidity is a condition *sine qua non* for long-term success. Last but not least important, Probstdorfer is supported by a number of loyal and motivated key employees over all age levels. These aspects decisively contribute to the company's agility and resilience.

Keywords

Austria · barley · cereal breeding · common wheat · durum wheat · maize · soybean

Further reading

Hänsel H (1958) Cereal breeding in Austria. *Euphytica* 7:59-82.
DOI: 10.1007/BF00037865

Probstdorfer Saatzucht (2023) The history of Probstdorfer Saatzucht. <https://www.probstdorfer.at/uber-uns/geschichte/?lang=en>; International: <https://www.probstdorfer.at/uber-uns/international/?lang=en>

75 years of plant breeding at SAATBAU LINZ

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Abstract

Five regional seed co-operatives were formed in Upper Austria after the Second World War. These were dedicated to the reconstruction of plant breeding and seed production of potatoes, cereals, red clover and forage grasses. On the initiative of the Upper Austrian state government, Saatbau Linz (Oberösterreichische Landessaatbau- Genossenschaft) was founded on 22 May 1950. A particular challenge from 1950 to 1955 was the administration, logistics and development of the various locations in two different occupation zones. North of the Danube there was a Russian administration and south of the Danube an American one.

The seed potato held a central role in the newly founded co-operative until the mid-1960s. From 1953, potato breeding was concentrated at the Kefermarkt site and steadily expanded. The potato breeder Franz Herber was able to register a total of 21 varieties in the Austrian variety list. The most successful varieties were 'Linzer Delikatess', Linzer Rose and Linzer Gelbe.

Due to the constant decline in the area under potato cultivation from the mid-1960s onwards, potato breeding was ultimately no longer cost-covering, which is why it was finally discontinued in 1989. In 1990, an agreement was reached with the Lower Austrian Seed Growers' Co-operative (NÖS) to continue existing variety and propagation activities in Upper Austria. The last varieties from this breeding programme were marketed by NÖS until the 2010s.

Parallel to the decline in potato areas and quantities, the importance of cereal seed sales increased rapidly. Cereal breeding in Reichersberg am Inn was very efficient and included winter wheat, winter barley, spring barley and oats. Field bean breeding was added in 1985, soybean breeding in 1992 and winter oilseed rape breeding in 1997. Josef Körber was in charge from 1950 until his retirement in 1990. He was a gifted and extremely successful breeder. In his 40 years of work, he was able to have 40 varieties entered in the Austrian variety list for Saatbau. His most outstanding variety was the winter wheat 'Ikarus'. From 1985 to 1995, it achieved an annual market share of over 50% of the total area of milling wheat in Austria.

In 1990, cereal breeding (winter wheat and winter barley) was acquired from the plant breeding company Neuhof Rohrau and integrated into the breeding programmes of Saatbau Linz from 1991. Saatbau Donau was founded in 2000 together with

Probstdorfer Saatbau. The existing breeding activities of both companies for cereals, oil and protein crops were combined and resources pooled, laying the foundations for a successful Austrian breeding company with European perspectives.

Saatbau Linz's maize breeding activities were launched on a small scale in Feldkirchen an der Donau in 1978. From 1984, these activities were concentrated at the Schönering site (municipality of Wilhering). From 1994, the winter nursery in Chile was established and expanded. DH technology was introduced in 2000, significantly increasing the volume of crossbreeding. With the implementation of genomic selection and the expansion of breeding to a second mainstay the dent breeding programme, competitiveness was further expanded. In 2020, the 200th variety was entered in the European variety list. The breeding mastermind behind this development was engineer Robert Taucher together with his team. They produced more than 250 varieties registered in the EU in 30 years.

Breeding work on the oil pumpkin has been ongoing since 2020. Saatbau Linz had already been involved in the development and commercialisation of New Zealand pumpkin genetics since 2006. This breeding material was purchased in 2022 and is now being further processed at the site in Weikendorf, Lower Austria.

In addition to these direct breeding activities, Saatbau Linz tests a large number of varieties from other breeding companies every year in order to successfully round off the portfolio for national and international seed sales.

Keywords

maize breeding · oilseed pumpkin · soybean · Saatbau Donau

Further reading

Fischer K (2025) Moch ma glei wos G'scheit's. Inform - Magazin für Pflanzenzüchtung und Saatgutproduktion 02/25:6-10.

Overview of breeding activities of the RWA/Lagerhaus network and future challenges for cooperative breeding programmes

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Abstract

In recent years, the seed industry has experienced severe upheavals and is faced with numerous challenges. Seed breeding in particular is under great pressure due to high financial expenditures. The following topics are the main drivers of this development:

- (i) Climate change and global crises lead to rapid and sudden changes in demand; a quick response to global changes in demand is becoming more and more important;
- (ii) the significant consolidation in the breeding sector has gained momentum in the medium-sized breeding sector, particularly in recent years;
- (iii) different political interests and viewpoints on global but also national scale make agriculture and its suppliers often a political pawn;
- (iv) increased social pressure on the seed industry, especially regarding sustainable production, traceability and higher CSR standards;
- (v) lack of effective seed treatment, increasing the pressure on breeding programmes to release more tolerant and resistant varieties.

Due to the challenges mentioned above, breeding companies are even more dependent on reliable partners for production and distribution. This requires companies with a fast go-to-market strategy on the one hand, and partners with a dense trial network throughout Europe on the other hand. A high level of technical expertise for all crops is expected. Breeding companies are looking for partners who operate effective risk management for field production in various regions, complemented by a strict quality management. An additional requirement for seed producers is a well-developed network of powerful seed production with a dense sales and distribution network and effective logistics.

In recent years, the Lagerhaus cooperatives, together with their wholesale company, RWA AG, have taken on exactly this role for Central Europe. The cooperative sector acts as a key factor in translating global demands in national needs. As a cooperative seed company, RWA sees itself in the role of increasing the economic competitiveness of Austrian and Central European farmers. It is also the cooperative's mission to make farmers successful with the breeders' products.

RWA maintains over 120 partnerships with breeders worldwide, demonstrating yearlong trust on both sides. RWA has been operating two breeding companies for many years now, which has enabled it to build up years of expertise. With its subsidiaries, RWA has a dense trial network, produces seed on over 30,000 hectares in all European countries and has production capacities of more than 100,000 tons of seed per year, which are designed according to the highest quality management standards.

The local connection with the cooperative roots is the building block of success. Despite the major crises of recent years (*e.g.* COVID-19 pandemic, Russian invasion of Ukraine, etc.), the supply with locally produced seed was never in danger. Thanks to the motto "local production for local demand" – in other words, farmers producing for farmers – there were never any shortages. On the other hand, the cooperative system is not a charitable one: cooperatives have to make profit to be able to invest sustainably in facilities and employees. Furthermore, RWA is also active in alternative crops and not just focussed on cash crops. Niche crops complement the product range of global breeding companies and, thus, meet the demand of farmers to increase biodiversity. This has always been the cooperative idea at its origin and this idea will continue to be lived in this form by the RWA Lagerhaus group.

Keywords

Field trial network · Seed production · seed treatment

Cereal and soybean breeding in Saatzucht Donau 2000 – 2024 – 2036: past – present – future

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Abstract

Saatzucht Donau was founded in the year 2000 as a merger of the research and breeding departments for cereal, oilseed and protein crops of Saatzucht Linz and Probstdorfer Saatzucht. Both shareholders own 50% and are still fully independent in seed production and distribution activities. The idea behind Saatzucht Donau was to strengthen the position of Austrian plant breeding in the European market. Since its founding, Saatzucht Donau runs two climatically quite different breeding stations: the breeding station Probstdorf is located close to Vienna in the Pannonian region with hot and dry springs and summers (549 mm average rainfall, 11.2°C average temperature) and breeding station Reichersberg is located close to the German border with cooler and more humid climate (827 mm average rainfall, 9.7°C average temperature). After founding and merging of breeding programmes, Saatzucht Donau had the following breeding programs in July 2000:

- Probstdorf: winter wheat (focus Central Europe, high quality), winter barley 6-row (feed), winter durum, spring durum, spring barley
- Reichersberg: winter wheat, winter triticale, winter oilseed rape, winter barley 2row (feed)

In 2004, a breeding program for 2-row winter malting barley was started, in 2010 the spring barley breeding was stopped. In 2009, soybean breeding started, which was the most profitable decision in the history of Saatzucht Donau. In 2012, the breeding method “genomic selection” was introduced first in winter wheat breeding and then extended to all other breeding programs. In 2018, spelt wheat breeding started. Some breeding programs were stopped, such as the winter wheat “West-program” in 2010 and the winter oilseed rape program in 2023. In 2024, research about how to use Artificial Intelligence (AI) in plant breeding started.

In 2000, all registered varieties and lines in official trials remained in possession of the two shareholders, so Saatzucht Donau’s first variety registrations were in 2003. From 2003 until 2024, Saatzucht Donau registered 428 varieties in Austria, 190 of them from its own breeding programs. At the same time, 328 varieties from Saatzucht Donau breeding programs were registered within EU countries and 217 registered outside the EU. An updated list can be found on <https://www.saatzucht-donau.at/englisch/varieties/>. Winter wheat is the most important crop in terms of number of varieties (286 registrations) followed by soybeans (149

registrations), winter barley (115 registrations), winter oilseed rape (89 registrations) and durum wheat (47 registrations).

With regard to market position, Saatzucht Donau is EU leader in soybeans with 20% market share, in winter durum with 58% market share and in organic wheat with 20% market share. Saatzucht Donau also has the leading position in winter wheat in Austria (conventional and organic) and in HRW (hard red winter wheat) in Ontario, Canada.

Concerning breeding goals, yield and yield stability will remain as important in the future as they have been in the past. Quality may lose some importance if processors do not pay enough premiums for high quality. Resistance against biotic stress will become more important because of reduced input of chemicals, especially fungicides. The importance of resistance against abiotic stress will also increase because of climate change, *e.g.* heat stress and drought.

Crossbreeding will remain the breeding method of choice, but speed breeding (DH, SSD, counter season) will become more important to stay competitive with big multinational breeding companies. Genomic selection will be a very helpful tool for all breeding programs and will support selection decisions especially in years with poor field data. AI will help breeders in the selection process and in choosing the genotypes best suitable for specific target regions. Hybrid breeding will not become the dominating breeding method in cereal and soybean breeding in the near future. The use of NBT (new breeding techniques) will depend on political decisions in the EU.

Keywords

Breeding strategy · breeding target · cereal breeding · market share · soybean

Further reading

Birschitzky J (2025) 25 Jahre Saatzucht Donau. Inform - Magazin für Pflanzenzüchtung und Saatgutproduktion 02/25:13-15.

Saatzucht Edelfhof - Cereal breeding since 1903: A century of innovation and progress

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Abstract

1903 – 1948 Early regional breeding efforts

Plant breeding at Edelfhof began in 1903, as documented in the respective yearbook of the Agricultural School Edelfhof. A nursery garden for rye, oats, and potatoes was established. Rudolf Ranninger and Gustav Pammer initiated selection programs resulting in the rye variety 'Edelhof Roggen'. In 1920, the "white" oat variety 'Edelhof Hafer' was successfully registered, marking a significant progress in regional breeding.

1949 – 1974 Breeding for Lower Austria

In 1949, Johann Boden became breeding manager and focused on individual plant selection and progeny testing for rye and oats. In collaboration with Konrad Schulmeister key achievements were the registration of winter rye 'Edelhof Neu' in 1965 (renamed 'EHO-Kurz' in 1970) and the development of oat variety 'Edelhof Früh' in 1968. The introduction of spring barley breeding in 1973 further diversified the breeding activities at Edelfhof.

1975 – 1989 National breeding for Austria

In 1975, the first contract with the Association of Rural Cooperatives (VLG – *Verband Ländlicher Genossenschaften*) and the Province of Lower Austria expanded breeding activities nationwide. The number of trial locations increased and winter wheat breeding was started, supported by enhanced mechanization such as the use of the first plot combine. Under the leadership of school director Adolf Kastner and head of breeding Konrad Schulmeister, the breeding team grew with Hubert Hofbauer and two more technicians, and new varieties were developed, including the spring barley variety 'Ebra' and the breadseed poppy varieties 'Edel-Rot' and 'Edel-Weiß'.

1990 – 2000 European expansion

In the 1990s, Edelfhof expanded its market into Europe. Two-row winter barley breeding began in 1990, and off-season nurseries were initiated in Chile in 1993 through a collaboration with Semillas Baer. The Association for the Promotion of Poppy and Grain Breeding (*Verein zur Förderung der Mohn- und Getreidezüchtung*) was founded, and a dedicated seed breeding facility was opened in 1996. These advancements allowed for more extensive trials, improved quality analysis, and strengthened the co-operation with BOKU University (*Universität für Bodenkultur Wien*). In 1997, responsibilities were allocated between farm manager Hubert Hofbauer and head of breeding Elisabeth Zechner.

2001 - 2024 Breeding for a competitive European market

During this period, Edelfhof established winter oat breeding and focused on varieties for organic farming. New breeders, *i.e.* Sandra Berger (winter oats) and Franz Wieser (winter rye), joined the team. Partnerships with RWA Raiffeisen Ware Austria AG and its subsidiaries and international partner companies enabled the registration and marketing of Edelfhof varieties across Europe. Technological advancements, such as the introduction of double haploids in winter barley breeding in 2008, further enhanced breeding efficiency. Significant anniversaries, such as the centennial in 2003 and the 120th anniversary in 2023, celebrated Edelfhof's rich history. In 2019, new contracts were established to strengthen the co-operation between the breeding at the Agricultural School and the marketing with Saatzucht Edelfhof GmbH, a subsidiary of RWA. This collaboration brought new breeders to Edelfhof, *i.e.* Mina Zamini who began working on winter barley in 2019, and Lukas Koppensteiner who joined in 2022 to focus on winter wheat. After 44 years of dedicated service, H. Hofbauer retired, and Andreas Jager stepped into the role of farm manager. In 2024, Edelfhof continues its active collaboration on breeding projects with renowned scientific partners such as BOKU University and AIT Austrian Institute of Technology. Today, Edelfhof varieties are successfully grown across a wide range of regions, from Turkey to Canada, Bosnia to France, Italy to Russia, and Romania to Great Britain.

Crops and breeding focus

Our breeding efforts focus on the following crops ranked by their importance:

- winter wheat: top-quality wheat for Europe and high-yielding varieties with excellent baking quality;
- winter barley: two-row varieties for malting and feeding;
- spring oats: high-yielding varieties with superior quality;
- spring barley: high-quality varieties for feeding and malting purposes;
- winter rye: traditional open-pollinated population varieties;
- winter oats: good winter hardiness and high quality;
- spring wheat: productive and versatile varieties.

We focus on ensuring all these crops are suitable for organic farming systems.

Our success lies in strong partnerships with Austrian and international collaborators. These include breeding partners, seed exchanges, trial networks, scientific research projects, and experts in multiplication, marketing, and distribution.

2025 and beyond: breeding for global challenges

Edelhof's future breeding efforts aim to address global agricultural challenges, such as climate change and food security. The focus will include resilience to extreme conditions, increased yields with limited resources, improved nutritional profiles, and sustainable agricultural practices. Innovations like artificial intelligence, drone technology, and machine learning will be integrated to breeding activities. Innovative methods to support and enhance the efficiency of breeding are continuously being developed and evaluated. Collaborative projects with scientific institutions such as BOKU University and AIT Austrian Institute of Technology will further enhance research and development.

Keywords

Avena sativa · barley · *Hordeum vulgare* · oats · quality · rye · *Secale cereale* · *Triticum aestivum* · wheat · yield

Further reading

Greisinger M, Pötscher F (1998) Edelhof, 125 Jahre Landwirtschaftliches Bildungs- und Innovationszentrum im Herzen des Waldviertels. Waldviertel Projektmanagement, Zwettl.

Saatzucht Gleisdorf 1947-now-future: The development into a successful diversified breeding station

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Abstract

After World War II, the European industry and agriculture was in ruins. The main goal was to ensure food supply by increasing yields, especially in corn (*Zea mays*). The Styrian Chamber of Agriculture decided in 1947 to establish an own breeding station in Kornberg which was the beginning of the first corn breeding program in Styria. New methods, e.g. back-cross breeding was used ensure the success of the program. The source material were over 100 open-pollinated varieties including populations from East-Germany, Czechoslovakia, Hungary and the Soviet Union.

The first success was in 1955, when the Proso millet (*Panicum miliaceum*) cv. 'Kornberger Mittelfrühe' was registered in the Austrian variety list. In 1957, the Chamber of Agriculture decided to move the breeding station to Gleisdorf. Saatzucht Gleisdorf was born. Gleisdorf is situated in the Illyrian climate zone at an altitude of 380 m a.s.l., has an average annual rainfall of 820 mm, an average temperature of 8.2°C, and medium to heavy (pseudo-)gley soils. The combination of humid warm weather conditions and a heavy soil favors the occurrence of a broad range of pests, in particular fungal diseases, which is of advantage for the selection of disease resistances under conditions of natural infections.

In 1960, the first corn double-hybrid cv. 'Austria 420' was registered in the Austrian variety list, and the oilseed pumpkin (*Cucurbita pepo* var. *styriaca*) breeding program was established. In 1969, cv. 'Gleisdorfer Ölkürbis', the first oilseed pumpkin variety was released. Between 1967 and 1973 new corn hybrid varieties have been registered.

In the 1970s, sales organizations took over parts of Saatzucht Gleisdorf from the Chamber of Agriculture. So, the shareholders changed to ⅓ Styrian Farmers Association, ⅓ ÖRWZ (former organization of RWA) and ⅓ Styrian Chamber of Agriculture. The successful oilseed pumpkin breeding program had a setback in 1997 with the first appearance of Zucchini yellow mosaic virus (ZYMV). The breeder at this time, Mrs. Johanna Winkler, together with Prof. Tamas Lelley, IFA Tulln, established a new breeding program with focus on virus resistance. In 1999, a first oilseed pumpkin hybrid variety was registered in Austria.

From 2012 onwards, Saatzucht Gleisdorf was expanded. A new cold storage was built and an area of 1.2 ha, including offices and outbuildings were purchased from the Chamber of Agriculture. In 2024, the office buildings have been renovated and updated. Currently, Saatzucht Gleisdorf has about 90 ha of breeding area, variety testing and production of basic seeds, with additional

areas around Austria for testing, selection and production. Saatzucht Gleisdorf is market leader in oilseed pumpkin in Central Europe, has a corn breeding program together with DSP AG, Delley-Portalban, Switzerland, and is one of the last breeders of faba bean (*Vicia faba*) in Europe. A soybean (*Glycine max*) breeding program was also established a few years ago with focus on maturity groups 0, 00, 000 and I.

Today, the cultivation of corn, oilseed pumpkin, faba bean, soybean and winter turnip rape (*Brassica rapa*) and the production of breeders seed stock is carried out at the Gleisdorf site on an area of 66 ha. In addition to this, Saatzucht Gleisdorf conducts test exchanges with foreign breeding companies. In order to shorten the long breeding process: a winter breeding program is carried out each year in Chile or in Tenerife.

Keywords

Faba bean · hybrid breeding · oilseed pumpkin · corn · soybean · Styria · ZYMV

Further reading

Hinterholzer J (1999) Produktionserfolge im österreichischen Maisbau. Bericht über die 50. Arbeitstagung der Vereinigung österreichischer Pflanzenzüchter, 23.-25. Nov, pp 147-151. BAL Gumpenstein, Irdning.

Pachner M, Paris HS, Winkler J, Lelley T (2015) Phenotypic and marker-assisted pyramiding of genes for resistance to zucchini yellow mosaic virus in oilseed pumpkin (*Cucurbita pepo*). Plant Breed 134:121-128. DOI: 10.1111/pbr.12219

Suso MJ, Hunady I, Solis I, Mondragão-Rodrigues F, Winkler J (2008) Germplasm management of *Vicia faba* L.: Comparative study of the mating system of local and common cultivars growing under different agro-ecological conditions. Plant Genet Resour Newsl 155:45-51.

Corteva's corn breeding efforts in Austria

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Abstract

As part of a global leading corn company, Corteva Agriscience GmbH conducts in Parndorf, Austria, a comprehensive conventional corn (*Zea mays*) breeding program serving primarily Austria and neighbouring countries. The program is focused on hybrids in the range of maturity groups FAO 280–380 (85-95 CRM; comparative relative maturity). The program has been established in 1986 and has currently 16 full time employees and up to 50 seasonal support staff entirely focused on conducting all areas of modern corn breeding, combining them into an integrated system driven from commercial hybrid successes in a very competitive global environment. The major components of the program are:

(1) Rapid re-cycling of breeding material by generating doubled haploid (DH) inbred lines with superior general (GCA) and specific combining abilities (SCA) utilizing Corteva's global germplasm collection from almost hundred years of breeding activities in hybrid corn;

(2) A high-capacity hybrid creation "machine" predicting and field testing commercially successful hybrids over a wide range of environments with clear targets on various traits. While high yield and low grain moisture remain fundamental, the stability of performance across a large range of environmental conditions as a result of climate change became more important. As early as 2005, the scientists in Parndorf focused on hybrids with improved heat and drought tolerance resulting in the AQUAmax[®] trademark. Today Corteva's AQUAmax[®] corn hybrids are highly successful on the market;

(3) High capacity, large scale (precision) phenotyping for multiple traits serves as the base for selection as well as repeatable genomic selections in the entire process of inbred and hybrid development. Activities in precision phenotyping and envirotyping have been largely expanded over the course of the last 10 years and have contributed significantly to improvements in critical trials, e.g. tolerance to ear mold, and overall progress in agronomic traits and overall stability of performance.

The site in Parndorf also serves as a central research production site for Europe, producing thousands of new crosses as well as hybrids in advanced stages for internal and official registration testing. The work is performed either in nursery plots via hand pollinations for small isolation fields in the surrounding areas with high success rates. In 2023 and 2024, Corteva further expanded its research activities at the Parndorf campus by centralizing its breeding and yield testing seed storage to allow rapid access and distribution for all local and winter nursery activities throughout the entire year. In 2025 and beyond, the team focuses on reducing the cycle time to further progress on the genetic gain for key traits. Yield stability but also parental traits are of focus considering the changes in the growing conditions.

Keywords

Doubled haploid inbred lines · drought tolerance · grain moisture · heat tolerance · hybrids · precision phenotyping · yield · *Zea mays*

Always needed – never finished. Research on disease resistance in cereals at BOKU

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Abstract

Plant diseases have been a threat to food security since the onset of agriculture. Major plant disease epidemics have caused hunger, illness and economic losses. The use of resistant cultivars is a key component in sustainable cropping. Luckily most potential pathogens are non-hosts to most plants, thus lack basic compatibility. However, in numerous cases microbes possess mechanisms that allow colonization of living plants and in many cases this compatible plant-pathogen interaction is highly specific and therefore breeding for resistance needs to be specific as well. Even if disease resistance has been a breeding target in many crops since more than a century, the mission has not been completed until today, and will demand ongoing investments in the future. This paper summarizes the work of the plant breeding group at BOKU for resistance to cereal diseases as one of our key focus points.

Fusarium head blight

The work on resistance to *Fusarium* diseases in bread wheat, durum wheat and to a lesser extent in triticale, barley and oat, is very visible with 90 SCI referenced publications in this field (ISI Web of Science, 2024). We started with basic work on establishing a reproducible testing system and assessing genetic diversity in breeding and exotic germplasm; we moved to genetic and genomic analysis, and transcriptomics, and now employ mutant populations and Crispr editing for understanding *Fusarium*-wheat interactions. We also explore more automated field phenotyping employing high resolution drone images (Kinz *et al.*, 2024). In parallel we developed pre-breeding lines with exceptional FHB resistance in bread wheat, which represent promising crossing candidates for advanced breeding. New cooperations have been established with partners in sub-Saharan Africa and we are now exploring into diversity for FHB resistance in regional germplasm for Kenya, Zimbabwe and Ethiopia. The resistance breeding tools and the germplasm available for bread wheat is highly advanced and ready to use for cultivar development. The situation is lagging a bit behind in durum wheat, but we are on a good track for both spring and winter durum. Apart from numerous research papers, highly cited reviews are available from our team (Buerstmayr *et al.*, 2009; Prat *et al.*, 2014; Steiner *et al.*, 2017; Haile *et al.*, 2019; Buerstmayr *et al.*, 2020).

Leaf rust and stripe rust

On top of our work on FHB we worked on resistance to stripe rust (*Puccinia striiformis*) and leaf rust (*P. recondita*). An interesting example of durable rust resistance is the more than 30 years old winter wheat 'Capo', bred by H. Hänsel. Its rust resistance is oligogenic and several Capo-QTL confer simultaneously resistance to leaf rust and stem rust (Buerstmayr *et al.*, 2014). More recently we evaluated current breeding material and discovered a few promising QTL for stripe rust in adapted winter wheat (Shahinnia *et al.*, 2022), but at the same time had to learn that genomic selection for resistance to stripe rust across seasons is unreliable (Morales *et al.*, 2023). A strategy to include both large effect major genes and at the same time multigenic background resistance in breeding has been proposed recently (Michel *et al.*, 2023).

Common bunt and dwarf bunt

An addition to our resistance breeding portfolio are bunt diseases caused by *Tilletia* species. Bunt is back at our wheat fields and poses an economic threat for organic wheat production, including seed production. Breeding for *Tilletia* resistance has been a niche topic over decades, but is gaining momentum. In the BOKU group we mapped and published selection markers for the currently fully efficient resistance genes *Bt12* (Muellner *et al.*, 2020) and *Bt11* (Lunzer *et al.*, 2023), both descending from old landraces, and for strong QTL in the resistant North-American cultivars 'Blizzard' and 'Bonneville' (Muellner *et al.*, 2021). Pre-breeding lines harboring these resistance loci in an agronomically improved background have been developed.

Wheat dwarf virus (WDV) and barley yellow dwarf virus (BYDV)

Insect transmitted virus diseases in winter cereals are climate change winners. Prolonged periods of mild temperatures in autumn result in high disease pressure by insect transmitted viruses, such as WDV (vector: leaf-hoppers) and BYDV (vector: aphids). By chance we discovered that the Dutch experimental line SVP-72017-17-5-10 (Marzotto // Dippes Triumph / Mironovskaya 808) shows unique resistance to WDV in field experiments. Based on this discovery we established mapping populations, tested these in early sown (around 20th September) field trials and mapped a large effect QTL on chromosome 6A and a smaller effect QTL at

the 1BL-1RS translocation chromosome (Buerstmayr & Buerstmayr, 2023). As follow up research and implementation we now move WDV resistance into modern winter wheat breeding lines and cultivar candidates, in close cooperation with Austrian breeders using an accelerated marker assisted back-crossing approach. Further breeding projects focus on the incorporation of resistance to BYDV in winter malting barley and the evaluation of virus resistance in winter durum wheat.

Septoria leaf blotch

Our latest addition is the utilization of multi-season field scores of Septoria leaf blotch severity in advanced breeding lines collected by Saatzucht-Donau. Genome-wide markers permitted association mapping of interesting QTL and deriving genome-wide predictions for use on breeding (Berisha *et al.*, 2025).

Breeding for resistance to fungal and viral diseases is an ongoing necessity. Pathogens can adapt to resistance genes and may render genes un-effective. New pathogens are gaining relevance and need to be addressed, and even durable types of resistance must be included in any new cohort of released cultivars. Therefore, resistance breeding is never completed, just like selection for yield performance and quality.

Material availability

The pre-breeding lines developed in our research projects are available to breeders and cooperators upon request and we are more than happy to share breeding lines. We want the discovered resistance loci not only residing in publications and library shelves, but reaching the farmer's fields via improved cultivars.

Acknowledgements

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Keywords

Fusarium head blight · bunt diseases · *Puccinia* · resistance breeding · *Septoria* · *Tilletia* · *Triticum* · virus diseases · wheat rusts

References

Berisha P, Michel S, Löschenberger F, Ametz C, Bistrich H, *et al.* (2025) Genome-wide association mapping and genomic prediction of *Septoria nodorum* blotch resistance in Central European winter wheat (*Triticum aestivum* L.). *Plant Breed* 144:182-191. DOI: 10.1111/pbr.13233

Buerstmayr H, Ban T, Anderson JA (2009) QTL mapping and marker-assisted selection for *Fusarium* head blight resistance in wheat: a review. *Plant Breed* 128:1-26. DOI: 10.1111/j.1439-0523.2008.01550.x

Buerstmayr M, Buerstmayr H (2023) Two major quantitative trait loci control wheat dwarf virus resistance in four related winter wheat populations. *Theor Appl Genet* 136:103. DOI: 10.1007/s00122-023-04349-3

Buerstmayr M, Matiasch L, Mascher F, Vida G, Ittu M, *et al.* (2014) Mapping of quantitative adult plant field resistance to leaf rust and stripe rust in two European winter wheat populations reveals co-location of three QTL conferring resistance to both rust pathogens. *Theor Appl Genet* 127:2011-2028. DOI: 10.1007/s00122-014-2357-0

Buerstmayr M, Steiner B, Buerstmayr H (2020) Breeding for Fusarium head blight resistance in wheat - Progress and challenges. *Plant Breed* 139:429-454. DOI: 10.1111/pbr.12797

Haile JK, N'Diaye A, Walkowiak S, Nilsen KT, Clarke JM, *et al.* (2019) Fusarium head blight in durum wheat: Recent status, breeding directions, and future research prospects. *Phytopathology* 109:1664-1675. DOI: 10.1094/phyto-03-19-0095-rww

ISI Web of Science (2024) <https://www.webofscience.com/wos/woscc/basic-search/>; search query: author=Buerstmayr H*/Burstmayr H*/BÜRSTMAYR H*; accessed on Dec 17, 2024.

Kinz G, Buerstmayr H, Roth PM (2024) Postprocessing and geopositioning of drone images to detect fusarium head blight. 74. Tagung der Vereinigung der Pflanzenzüchter und Saatgutkaufleute Österreichs, pp 15-16. BOKU University, Vienna. DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.12015402

Lunzer M, Buerstmayr M, Grausgruber H, Müllner AE, Fallbacher I, *et al.* (2023) Wheat (*Triticum aestivum*) chromosome 6D harbours the broad spectrum common bunt resistance gene *Bt11*. *Theor Appl Genet* 136:207. DOI: 10.1007/s00122-023-04452-5

Michel S, Löschenberger F, Ametz C, Buerstmayr H (2023) Toward combining qualitative race-specific and quantitative race-nonspecific disease resistance by genomic selection. *Theor Appl Genet* 136:79. DOI: 10.1007/s00122-023-04312-2

Morales L, Ametz C, Dallinger HG, Löschenberger F, Neumayer A, *et al.* (2023) Comparison of linear and semi-parametric models incorporating genomic, pedigree, and associated loci information for the prediction of resistance to stripe rust in an Austrian winter wheat breeding program. *Theor Appl Genet* 136:23. DOI: 10.1007/s00122-023-04249-6

Muellner AE, Buerstmayr M, Eshonkulov B, Hole D, Michel S, *et al.* (2021) Comparative mapping and validation of multiple disease resistance QTL for simultaneously controlling common and dwarf bunt in bread wheat. *Theor Appl Genet* 134:489-503. DOI: 10.1007/s00122-020-03708-8

Muellner AE, Eshonkulov B, Hagenguth J, Pachler B, Michel S, *et al.* (2020) Genetic mapping of the common and dwarf bunt resistance gene *Bt12* descending from the wheat landrace PI119333. *Euphytica* 216. DOI: 10.1007/s10681-020-02614-w

Prat N, Buerstmayr M, Steiner B, Robert O, Buerstmayr H (2014) Current knowledge on resistance to Fusarium head blight in tetraploid wheat. *Mol Breed* 34:1689-1699. DOI: 10.1007/s11032-014-0184-2

Shahinnia F, Geyer M, Schurmann F, Rudolphi S, Holzapfel J, *et al.* (2022) Genome-wide association study and genomic prediction of resistance to stripe rust in current Central and Northern European winter wheat germplasm. *Theor Appl Genet* 135:3583-3595. DOI: 10.1007/s00122-022-04202-z

Steiner B, Buerstmayr M, Michel S, Schweiger W, Lemmens M, *et al.* (2017) Breeding strategies and advances in line selection for Fusarium head blight resistance in wheat. *Trop Plant Pathol* 42:165-174. DOI: 10.1007/s40858-017-0127-7

Development of the Austrian baking quality model of bread wheat in the last 30 years - A comparison of methods and their impact on the baking volume of Kaiser rolls

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Abstract

Baking quality of wheat remains an important criterion for determining the wheat price on stock markets and, thus, guides decision-making of breeders, farmers, traders and millers. Baking tests are an essential part of the Austrian VCU testing procedure of common wheat. The Austrian baking quality classification was established in 1994. In the past years, some changes have been adopted. From 2020 to 2023, the Spiral Mixer Test (SMT) was introduced besides the Rapid Mix Test (RMT) in order to assess its suitability for the baking quality classification. Baking volume of Kaiser rolls, the main determinant for baking quality in the Austrian system, from the two mixing methods was compared. Correlation between RMT and SMT volumes is highly significant ($r = 0.99$). The SMT baking volume is generally higher ($b = 1.06$), due to less intensive mixing. For each year and baking quality group, similar trends are observed, although a slightly lower regression coefficient was found for 2021. The factors test site and market class have no influence on the regression between the two methods. The comparison between the mixing methods indicates that SMT can be introduced without any objections as alternative to RMT in the baking quality classification.

Keywords

Baking tests · quality parameters · Rapid Mix Test · spiral mixer · intervarietal correlation · *Triticum aestivum* · VCU test

Introduction

Baking quality is a highly complex characteristic of wheat varieties, composed of a range of factors that expose many interactions. Genotype by environment interactions (G×E) may further complicate the complexity. Baking quality classifications are used to examine the baking quality of individual wheat varieties and summarize this overarching trait in a single baking quality group (BQG) for an easier and simplified interpretation.

A baking quality classification informs breeders, farmers, traders and millers of a wheat variety's value in the processing to bread, and supports their decision-making. A good classification is required to reliably assign the released varieties to BQGs.

Wheat quality can be regarded from many perspectives: from the consumer's side there are nutritional value, safety aspects (e.g. pesticide residues or mycotoxin contamination), sensory properties and even immaterial values (e.g. culture, idealism) which may be important. For bakers, processability is important. Considering the value chain, quality-related traits can be assigned to one of the five processing/product steps: grains (grading and storage), milling, flour, dough, and baking. There is an extensive list of traits that can be used to describe and characterize a wheat variety with respect to end-use quality. Dependence between traits leads to significant correlations between some of them. For example, crude protein content and wet gluten content display a strong positive relationship.

In the Austrian Value of Cultivation and Use (VCU) testing, wheat baking quality is defined as "the ability of a flour to produce a soft, voluminous and visually appealing roll". Furthermore, "a problem-free industrial processing of the dough is essential (AGES, 2024). The main determinants of quality are grain protein quantity and quality, and starch pasting properties. To characterise these three factors, a number of traits are assessed for each candidate variety in the VCU testing. After evaluation, a candidate variety is assigned a baking quality group (1-9), which is further grouped into one of three market classes: high (*Qualitätsweizen*), medium (*Mahlweizen*) and low (*Futter- & Sonstiger Weizen*) baking quality. The highest market class contains varieties of good baking quality, which can also be used to improve batches of lower quality through blending if certain quality parameters are high enough. Wheat of the lowest quality class is used for other purposes than breadmaking, e.g. biscuitmaking or feeding. Farmers receive a higher price for quality wheat that is expected to yield higher quality flours. The average quotation of high-quality wheat at the Exchange for Agricultural Products in Vienna is € 25.5 higher than medium quality wheat and € 50 higher than feed wheat (Börse für Landwirtschaftliche Produkte in Wien, 2025). Both high and

medium quality varieties are required to supply the bakers the whole year round with flours of good and stable quality.

Austrian baking quality classification

The Austrian baking quality classification was developed in 1994 to evaluate the baking quality of candidate varieties in the VCU testing process (Oberforster *et al.*, 1994). The analysis of baking tests from 1978 to 1993 was used to establish a list of 23 traits from indirect characteristics, farinogram, extensogram and the baking test. An extended list of historical and currently used grain and quality parameters can be found in Table 1.

Currently, baking tests for candidate varieties are integrated in VCU tests from the 1st year onward, although in the 1st year a smaller number of trials is included. The comprehensive results from the 3-year testing period form the basis of the initial variety description proposed to the variety release commission. After approval, the initial description is published in the Austrian Descriptive List of Varieties (*Österreichische Beschreibende Sortenliste*, BSL). After variety release, baking quality experiments continue for at least one additional year. In case of results deviating from the initial classification, changes in the BQG are made and published in the next following BSL.

Baking test: A **Rapid-Mix-Test** (RMT) is used to bake the traditional *Kaisersemmel* (Kaiser rolls), the most widely spread baked good in Austria. Due to its rosette-shape stamp, the dough is challenged during fermentation which supports varietal differentiation with respect to baking quality. The RMT uses a higher mixing speed than used in industrial baking. Thereby, doughs are exposed to a higher level of shear stress and the differentiation between varieties becomes more pronounced.

The original RMT recipe (Oberforster *et al.*, 1994) has been adjusted several times over the years to align with newer protocols, standards and techniques, and to come closer to the practice of industrial bakeries. The current recipe is as follows: in a Stephan UMTA 15 dough kneader (Stephan & Söhne GmbH, Hameln, DE), 1 kg of type W700 flour (ash content: 0.67-0.76% dm) is mixed with 2 g of wheat malt flour; 18 g of salt are added; the amount of water added depends on the extensogram and lies between 53.8% and 62.1%; 50 g of compressed yeast are dissolved in water which is kept at 4°C; 10 g of edible oil and 0.02 g of ascorbic acid in 0.1% solution (a total of 20 mL) are added to the mixture. The water containing the yeast and ascorbic acid is added to the kneader and the dough is mixed for 20 s after which dough sticking to the mixing bowl is returned and mixing continues for a further 40 s. Kneading is done at 700 rpm. The final dough temperature should be 25-26°C, otherwise the process is repeated.

Fermentation of the oil brushed dough is for 20 min at room temperature (25°C). Using a Fortuna Automat (Fortuna Maschinen GmbH, Bad Staffelstein, DE), the dough is divided and moulded at a pressure setting $\frac{3}{4}$ for 12 revolutions, and 30 rolls are formed. The rolls are dusted with a mixture of 50% maize starch and 50% rye flour and proofed for 20 min at room temperature. The rosettes are punched by machine, the dough pieces are placed with the rosette upside down in a proofing box for 20 min final proofing at 30°C and 80% humidity. Finally, the rolls are baked at

220°C (240°C and 215°C top and bottom heat, respectively) for 18 min with a steam injection of 0.8 L in the first minute of baking, 0.1 L between 14' and 14'30'', and vents closed until 15' (MIWE Backcombi, Michael Wenz GmbH, Arnstein, DE).

Compared to the original method described by Oberforster *et al.* (1994), the following modifications were made:

- the level of ascorbic acid in the recipe was increased from 0.01 g kg⁻¹ dough to 0.02 g kg⁻¹ dough in 2002;
- the amount of added water was changed from sensorial determination to +1% of extensograph water absorption in 2018;
- the mixing speed was reduced from 1400 to 700 rpm in 1996;
- for dusting of the rolls, originally 100% rye flour was used, which was replaced in 1996 by a 50:50 mixture maize starch/rye flour as used in industrial bakeries;
- the length of the 2nd proofing was increased from 15 to 20 min in 2019;
- the determination of the baking volume of 12-20 rolls by rapeseed displacement was changed in 2022 to laser-based scanning (Volscan Profiler, Stable Micro Systems, Godalming, UK) of 12 rolls.

The core parameters from the baking tests are **dough weight** which strongly correlates with flour water absorption; **bread weight** which is correlated to dough weight; and **baking volume**. Baking volume is the most important determinant for the baking quality score (BQS) of a variety. A high baking volume is usually associated with positive dough characteristics. Since 1994, the RMT was used in Austrian VCU testing, which uses intensive kneading and leads to lower baking volumes than realized in industrial processing. The SMT leads to higher baking volumes and approaches industrial processes better. Bread yield has been used in the past to reflect baking loss, but these traits have not been calculated anymore since 2007, despite that the parameters used for their calculations are still in use.

Additionally, several sensory and appearance characteristics of the Kaiser rolls are rated using different scoring scales: dough surface texture, structure, consistency and tolerance, overall dough workability, appearance of the rosette, roll browning, odour, shape, general roll appearance, crumb structure, and overall baking quality based on the baker's judgment. Although they do not directly impact the test results, they are occasionally used as a reference to explain unexpected results.

Besides the baking test, a large number of other traits are used to characterise the baking quality of a wheat variety directly and indirectly. Table 1 provides an overview of all traits that are currently used or were used in the past. A short description of these traits follows:

Grain parameters: **Thousand kernel weight** (TKGW) is a measure of average kernel weight. Flour yield is not linearly related to TKGW as smaller grains often have a thinner hull. **Hectolitre/test weight** is an important criterion for grading wheat in commodity futures, but its influence on baking quality is small. **Ash content** is the percentage of inorganic non-combustible material of the grain after burning of the grain at 900°C. Remaining grain minerals originate predominantly from the bran (pericarp and seed coat), aleurone layer and the embryo (Wozniak & Makarski, 2013; Fišteš

Table 1 Baking quality parameters used historically and currently in the Austrian baking quality model

Characteristics	Code	Parameter	Unit	Range ¹	Method used	History ²
Grain	TKGW	1000 kernel weight (86% dm)	g	30.3-43.9	ÖNORM EN ISO 520	O
	HLGW	Hectolitre mass	kg hL ⁻¹	75.7-83.7	ISO 7971-3:2009	O
	GKA%	Grain ash (mineral) content	% dw	1.72-2.01	ICC 104	O
Milling	MA55	Flour yield type W550	%	63.2-76.2	Meißner (2016)	MC
	MA70	Flour yield type W700	%	70.0-85.0		MC
	KHTE	Kernel hardness	%	33.5-57.6		O
Flour	RPRT	Protein content	% dw	11.4-15.4	ICC 105, ICC 167, ISO 15948	MC
	GLUT	Wet gluten content	%	20.5-35.4	ICC 137/1, ICC 155	MC
	SEDW	Sedimentation value	mL	16.2-64.0	ICC 116 & ICC 118	O
	FZAL	Falling number	s	239-395	ICC 107/1	O
	QZ00	Structural swelling no. (Q ₀)	mL	8.0-24.9	Berliner & Koopman (1929)	R 2019
	QZ30	Proteolytical swelling no. (Q ₃₀)	mL	4.5-18.2		R 2005
	KLAB	Gluten degradation	%	14.4-43.9		R 2005
	WZAL	Quality value		84.2-143	Fuchs (1952, 1953, 1954)	R 2019
Dough						
Farinograph	WAUF	Water absorption	%	56.3-65.6	ICC 115/1	O
	TEWI	Developing time	min	2.2-6.4		O
	TSTA	Dough stability	min	1.4-18.4		O
	TE12	Dough relaxation (12 min.)	FU	55.1-157		O
	QUZA	Quality number	mm	29.9-148		O
Extensograph	WAUE	Water absorption	%	52.2-60.8	ICC 114/1 ³	O
	B135	Extensibility (after 135 min.)	mm	121-214		O
	W135	Resistance to extension at 5 cm	EU	63.3-566		O
	M135	Peak resistance to extension		44.7-725		O
	V135	Ratio W135/B135	-	0.91-4.1		O
	X135	Ratio M135/B135	-	1.1-5.3		O
	TEEN	Dough energy at 135 min.	cm ²	17.6-165		O
	Alveograph	ALVP	Maximum overpressure (P)	mmH ₂ O	54.8-147	ICC 121
ALVL		Extensibility (L)	mm	67.0-195		N 1997
ALPL		P/L-ratio	-	0.53-1.9		N 1997
ALVW		Dough energy (W)	10 ⁻⁴ J	107-443		N 1997
ALVG		Extension index (G)	cm ³	17.8-29.8		N 1997
Bread	TVAE	Dough processability	1-9	4.3-5.0	Oberforster <i>et al.</i> (1994)	MC
	TEGE	Dough weight (RMT) ⁴	g	1611-1699		O
	TEGS	Dough weight (SMT)	g	1614-1705		N 2020
	GEGE	Bread weight (RMT; 30 rolls)	g	1318-1395	Oberforster <i>et al.</i> (1994)	O
	GEGS	Bread weight (SMT; 30 rolls)	g	1258-1440		N 2020
	GEAU	Bread yield	% fw	130-138	Oberforster <i>et al.</i> (1994)	R 2007
	AUVE	Baking loss	mg 100 g ⁻¹ dough	16.6-19.0	Oberforster <i>et al.</i> (1994)	R 2007
	VOLU	Baking volume (RMT)	mL 100 g ⁻¹ flour	424-609	Oberforster <i>et al.</i> (1994)	O
VOLS	Baking volume (SMT)	mL 100 g ⁻¹ flour	373-590		N 2020	

¹ Range of adjusted means of released winter wheat varieties tested in the Austrian VCU tests in the period 2011 to 2024; for traits/methods removed or newly adopted since 1994, the range refers to the respective trial period, *i.e.* 1994 to last year before abandonment of the trait/method and/or year of introduction of the new method to 2024

² O, parameter currently in use as originally in 1994; MC, parameter currently in use with minor changes compared to 1994; R, parameter removed from the baking quality model in the given year; N, parameter newly introduced to the baking quality model in the given year

³ ICC 114/1 alternative: 1 min kneading, 5 min resting, 2 min kneading

⁴ RMT = Rapid Mix Test, SMT = spiral mixer test

et al. 2014). From 2016 onwards, the combustion method for grains was replaced by NIRS.

Milling parameters: **Flour yield** of flour type W700 is the amount of flour extracted from 100 kg wheat of a defined ash and moisture content (flour type = ash content (%) × 1000). In Austria, it is the most common type of flour in bread baking. 5 kg of wheat,

adjusted to 15.5% grain moisture, is milled (Mahlautomat MLU 202, Bühler AG, Uzwil, CH) and enough bran is added to reach 0.7% ash content. Flour yield is essential for the profitability of a mill and depends on grain shape and size, depth of the crease, smoothness and thickness of pericarp and seed coat, adhesion of the bran to the endosperm and the bran's tendency to splinter, and the ash content of the whole grain. **Grain/kernel hardness** is

measured as particle size distribution determined by air classification as residue after 3 min sifting of W700 flour on a sieve of 75 µm mesh width. Grain hardness characterises the binding between starch granules and protein in the endosperm. In Austria, flours of medium to high kernel hardness are preferred.

Flour parameters: **Grain protein content** (RPRT) has a direct effect on baking quality with lower RPRT levels being only partly compensated by other flour characteristics. RPRT is calculated from the grain N content (determined by NIRS calibrated on the Dumas method) using a conversion factor of 5.7. High quality wheat has a RPRT >14%. RPRT is mainly determined by the genotype and the level of N fertilisation, and is negatively correlated with grain yield. Thus, varieties of the high BQGs do not always reach the required 14% in case of high grain yields. In Austria, the highest RPRT levels are reached in the more dry production area of the Pannonian plains and hills in the North-East, whereas up to 3% lower concentrations are realized in the Wald-/Mühlviertel region in the North. **Wet gluten content** (GLUT) is the remaining protein in the insoluble mass that remains after washing doughs in a saline solution. Gluten makes up ≈80-85% of total flour protein. GLUT correlates positively and significantly with RPRT but the ratio GLUT/RPRT varies between years and varieties (1.8-2.6). For high quality wheat, the minimum requirement is often 30%, while medium quality should exceed 28%. **Zeleny sedimentation value** is a flour's protein swelling capacity in a lactic acid-isopropyl alcohol solution and an indicator for protein quality. The sedimentation value is much stronger genetically determined than RPRT. High baking quality flours have sedimentation values >45-50 mL, whereas wheat batches <22 mL cannot even be used for blending. **Hagberg falling number** is an indicator for pre-harvest sprouting (PHS) and, thus, a variety's starch integrity and/or α-amylase activity. Low HFN values are associated with PHS and influence baking quality negatively by weakening dough elasticity. Flours with falling numbers <220 s cannot be improved by blending. PHS is especially associated with unfavourable conditions (*i.e.* high precipitation) before harvest, but genotypic variation can have a significant influence. In hot and dry conditions during grain maturation, the falling number can be too high for optimal baking results. The **swelling index of glutenin** (Q_0), the proteolytical swelling number and the gluten degradation were determined by the Berliner-Koopman test until 2019 and 2005, respectively, to describe gluten quality. The **quality value** ($2 \times \text{GLUT} + 3 \times Q_0$) was a former criterion to differentiate between high (≥ 119) and medium quality wheat; this criterion was abandoned in 2019.

Dough parameters: The **farinograph** analyses the behaviour of a dough under the stress of mechanical kneading in a force-time diagram, the farinogram. The consistency of the dough is adjusted to 500 farinograph units (FU) by the appropriate amount of water added. The higher the **water absorption**, the higher the product weight per unit of flour and the longer the freshness of bread. For W700 flours, a farinograph water absorption >63% of flour weight is considered high, the optimum lies between 58 and 61 (Cauvain & Clark, 2017). For a high baking quality, the farinogram parameters water absorption, dough developing time, dough stability and quality number should be high, whereas dough softening should be low. Desired values for **dough developing time** lie between 2 and 6 min, for **dough stability** above 4 min,

and for **dough softening** 12 minutes after peak preferably around 80 (Cauvain & Clark, 2017). The farinograph **quality number** corresponds to the distance between start and the point where the central curve has fallen by 30 FU after the peak, thus, combines all three before mentioned parameters in one value.

The **extensograph** tests the extension properties of a dough by uniaxial stretching. It can be used to draw conclusions about the volume and shape of the baked goods. The dough is prepared in the farinograph following the baking test recipe. The dough is moulded in the machine's ball homogenizer and dough roller. After resting at 30°C in the fermentation chamber for 135 min, a dough sample is stretched by a hook and the force-distance diagram until dough rupture, the extensogram, is recorded. The **water absorption** to reach an optimal dough consistency of 500 FU after 1 min mixing, 5 min resting and another 2 min mixing is determined. For W700 flours a water absorption >60% is considered high. The further parameters extracted from the extensogram are: **extensibility**, **resistance to extension at 5 cm**, **peak resistance** to extension, **energy** defined as the area under the curve, and the **ratio number** between resistance at 5 cm and extensibility or peak resistance and extensibility. For baking, a high peak resistance (400-600 extensograph units; EU) and a ratio between 2.5 and 3.5 is preferable (AGES, 2024). Optimal stretching properties can be also reached by blending flours with different extension characteristics.

The **alveograph** is considered in the evaluation of baking quality with respect to Austria's export market in South Europe. Contrary to the extensograph, it tests the extensibility of dough by biaxial stretching. The dough is prepared from 250 g flour (15% moisture) and 125 mL water (0.025% NaCl). The **maximum overpressure** (P) corresponds to the height of the recorded curve and, thus, the maximum pressure inside the dough bubble; the **extensibility** (L) is measured as the length of the curve and the **deformation energy** is the area under the curve which corresponds to the energy used to inflate the bubble and should ideally be between 150 and 250 mm². Additional parameters extracted from the alveogram are the **configuration ratio** (P/L) which reflects the relationship between elastic and plastic properties of the dough and should be between 0.4 and 0.8 for most end-uses given that a high energy is also reached, and the **extension index**, *i.e.* the maximum dough bubble size (IREKS, 2025).

Dough processibility is rated on a 1-9 score and summarises scores for dough surface (dry to sticky), dough elasticity (strong to soft) and dough tolerance (short to long).

The most evident correlations between traits evaluated in the VCU tests are between traits that measure the same characteristics by different methods/procedures, *e.g.* water absorption in extensograph and farinograph ($r = 0.97$), or baking volumes of RMT and SMT rolls ($r = 0.96$) (Fig. 1). Strong correlations are also found between farinogram parameters and farinograph quality value, between dough energy and peak resistance from the extensogram, and between extensogram dough energy and farinogram dough stability. With $r > 0.7$, crude protein content and sedimentation value are similarly good predictors of baking volume as parameters from the dough rheological tests.

Figure 1 Intervarietal correlation of estimated marginal means of selected baking quality traits from 637 wheat varieties in the period 2011-2024 (pairwise complete observations). Colour and values correspond to correlation strength, non-significant correlations ($p > 0.05$) have been removed. Abbreviations see Table 1.

Baking quality score and group

The Kaiser rolls' baking volume and dough processability are most important in assigning a BQS to a wheat variety. Furthermore, protein content, wet gluten content, sedimentation value, falling number, farinogram quality value, and extensogram water absorption and dough energy contribute to the final classification (Table 2). The data of these parameters is evaluated using estimated marginal means (EMMs) to allow for comparison of the varieties in a non-orthogonal data set. Calculating EMMs considers possible differences between the number of data available per variety and compensates for possible extraneous factors influencing a variety's data, e.g. climatic and soil differences between field trials. Varieties are then assigned a performance value on a 1 to 9 scale for each parameter. The full range of EMMs is divided in generally equally large bins for each performance value and varieties are categorised accordingly.

The 1 to 9 scores are corresponding to very low and very high performance, respectively, for the individual traits. In the original baking quality model, the direction of the scores was not standardised, i.e. a score 1 was "very bad" and 9 was "very good". However, whether a high score is good or bad can differ between varieties and their purpose (e.g. bread vs. biscuit/cookie making). In 2019, the scales were harmonised, that means that for some traits the scores were turned around, e.g. for dough softening. The BQS is finally assigned using minimum scores for each trait (Table 2). First, a variety's BQS corresponds to its baking volume score. To stay with this score, the minimum scores for the other traits need to be reached. A variety can compensate for a single underperforming trait of one level by overcompensation of one level in two other traits or an overcompensation of two levels in a single trait. Underperformance of two levels cannot be compensated for, the variety is then downgraded to a lower BQS.

Table 2 Minimum scores required for each Baking Quality Score (BQS) assignment, before possible compensation.

BQS ¹	Indirect Parameters ²				Dough			Baking	
	RPRT	GLUT	SEDW	FZAL	QUZA	WAUE	TEEN	TVAE	VOLU
9	7	7	8	6	8	7	8	9	9
8	6	6	7	5	7	6	7	8	8
7	5	5	6	5	6	6	6	7	7
6	4	4	5	5	5	5	5	6	6
5	4	4	5	4	4	4	4	5	5
4	3	3	4	4	3	3	4	4	4
3	3	3	4	3	3	3	4	3	3
2	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	2	2
1	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	1	1

¹ Baking quality scores 7-9 make up the highest market class of Austrian wheat varieties (i.e. *Qualitätsweizen*, used to improve medium quality flours), scores 3-6 fill the medium market class (i.e. *Mahlweizen*), and scores 1-2 are of the worst baking quality (i.e. feed and other purpose wheat, including biscuit/cookie flours). Varieties with a flour yield score of 1 or 2 are downgraded to "feed wheat" irrespective of their original BQS.

² Abbreviations see Table 1

In case of a potential second downgrade, three levels of overcompensation are necessary, in one or multiple traits. A failing baking volume and flour processability, however, cannot be compensated at all. In the Austrian Descriptive List of Varieties 2024, six out of 68 winter wheat varieties were assigned a lower final BQS than their baking volume justified (AGES, 2024). A baking quality group (BQG) is assigned based on a variety's baking quality score (Table 2). Hence, the BQS corresponds to the BQG unless a variety is downgraded to "feed wheat" due to inferior flour yield.

As outlined, baking volume is the core trait in assigning wheat varieties a BQS and/or BQG. Originally, the RMT was used. In 2020, the SMT was introduced. Since then, both methods were used in parallel but until 2022 only the RMT results have been used for determining the baking volume score in the Austrian VCU testing process, as published in the Austrian Descriptive List of

Table 3 VCU trials included in the determination of baking volume of winter wheat varieties (O, organic management; C, conventional management; F, conventional management with fungicide use).

Location and post code	2020	2021	2023
Andau, 7163	C		
Bad Wimsbach, 4654	F	F	F
Berg, 2413	C		
Eltendorf, 7562		C	
Flinsbach, 3110	F	F	
Fuchsenbigl, 2286		C (2x)	
Gerhaus, 2471	F	F	
Großnondorf, 2042	C	C (3x)	
Loosdorf bei Mistelbach, 2133	O	O	O
Mistelbach, 2130	C		
Pottendorf, 2486	C / F	C / F	
Reichersberg, 4981	F		
Ritzlhof, 4053		F	
Sitzendorf an der Schmida, 3714	O	O	O
Weikendorf, 2253	C		
Zinsenhof, 3244	C / F		F

Varieties. Here, we report the results of a comparison between RMT and SMT, and how these methods relate to each other and to other parameters in the baking tests.

Materials and methods

Field trials

In total, 33 wheat (*Triticum aestivum*) VCU trials from 2020, 2021 and 2023 were used for statistical analysis (Table 3). Six trials were under organic management. From the remaining trials, 16 were grown in the Pannonic, and 11 in the Alpine and Illyric climate zones. In 13 trials, a fungicide was applied. Six trials were sown at an extra early sowing date. In total, for 110 wheat genotypes (both released and VCU candidate varieties) both RMT and SMT data are available, with a total of 625 genotype by location by year observations and a maximum of 33 traits per entry.

Baking test

The spiral mixer used in the SMT is the Diosna SP-12 (DIOSNA Dierks & Söhne GmbH, Osnabrück, DE). The recipe used for the SMT is largely equal to the RMT with the following modifications:

- all ingredient amounts are increased by 50%, as the spiral mixer requires a larger minimum dough volume due to its larger mixing bowl to function properly;
- mixing of the ingredients is done for 2 min on speed I (60 rpm) and 2-8 min on speed II (100 rpm) with the actual time depending on the farinogram, *i.e.* 50% of dough stability;
- the final dough temperature after mixing should be 25-27°C;
- after bulk proofing, 1/3 of the dough is discarded to have the same dough amounts (*i.e.* 1 kg) as in the RMT recipe for further processing.

Statistical analysis

The varieties that were used in the baking tests were processed according to the current baking quality model. If possible all traits listed in Table 1 were evaluated. The data were processed in R 4.4.0 software. No normalisation or imputation was carried out, as this could interfere with the relationship between the baking volume of the two baking tests. Data was reduced to data points that contained at least both RMT and SMT observations. For 82 observations (originating from 34 varieties) no baking quality score was available. For 227 observations no alveograph data was available. Other than that, no more than 4 observations were missing for any parameter. The following R packages were used: *stringr*, *dplyr*, *tidyr* and *reshape2* for data reorganisation; *ggcorrplot* for creating the correlation matrix; *lmtest* for the Breusch-Pagan test (against heteroscedasticity); *car* for ANOVA table; and *ggplot2*, *gridExtra*, *ggpmisc* and *RColorBrewer* for creating graphs.

Results and discussion

For both methods, baking volumes range from about 300 mL 100 g⁻¹ upwards. SMT volumes can be a little higher than RMT volumes, with a maximum of 690 and 726 mL 100 g⁻¹, respectively (Fig. 2). Baking volume was distributed non-normally in both baking tests as revealed by Shapiro-Wilk test (RMT: $p = 9.892 \times 10^{-5}$; SMT: $p = 3.936 \times 10^{-5}$) and kernel density plots (Fig. 2). The bimodal distribution is most likely the result of two distributions: one for

the varieties with high baking quality and one for medium-quality wheat varieties. The distribution peak of the latter group is about 100 mL 100 g⁻¹ flour lower than that of the high-quality group. Although intravarietal baking volumes can differ largely, SMT consistently leads to higher baking volumes within varieties (Fig. 3). The trend of higher SMT than RMT baking volumes is also visible in all subgroups when the varieties are grouped according to their baking quality score and group (Fig. 4). The large overlapping between the BQGs originates largely in environmental effects. For variety differences, ranking within trials is more indicative. The two data points with high volume from a low quality variety belong to 'Enrico', a variety downgraded to BQS 2 due to low flour yield. The highest medium quality variety volume stems from 'Tillsano' (BQS 6), for which its low water absorption led to a lower BQS.

Figure 2 Kernel density plot for baking volumes from RMT and SMT baking tests.

Correlation

Correlation analysis between the two kneading methods performed on the same flour/wheat variety show that the methods lead to comparable results. A very high correlation between RMT and SMT baking volume was found ($r = 0.99$; $p < 0.001$), slightly higher than the intervarietal correlation on the adjusted means found in the long-term data ($r = 0.98$, 2011-2024). To investigate the dependence of the RMT-SMT baking volume relationship of other factors, the correlation was also calculated on subgroups, *e.g.* variety baking quality group, VCU trial series (*i.e.* western, eastern, organic or early nursery) and field trial location. The variety itself was excluded as factor, as not enough data was available for most individual varieties. The results show that the high correlation between RMT and SMT baking volume is present in all subgroups (Table 4).

Despite the high correlation between RMT and SMT baking volume, a difference in variety ranking was observed by Wilcoxon signed rank test with continuity correction ($p < 0.001$). Some difference in variety ranking is expectable considering the high number of 110 varieties, nor is it problematic *per se*, as absolute values are evaluated in the VCU data analysis rather than rank values. Besides, the wide range of baking volume (≈ 300 -725 mL 100 g⁻¹) are translated to a 1-9 scale, reducing differences in the absolute values and/or the ranks. On average, the difference between the two baking tests is ≈ 20 mL 100 g⁻¹ flour.

Figure 3 Variation in RMT and SMT baking volume in winter wheat varieties tested in at least 10 VCU trials in 2020, 2021 and 2023. Baking quality scores of varieties in brackets.

Figure 4 RMT and SMT baking volume from winter wheat varieties tested in at least four Austrian VCU trials in 2020, 2021 and 2023 grouped by baking quality score.

Table 4 Summary of regression analysis between RMT and SMT baking volume per within each subgroup of four grouping factors. Minimum and maximum adjusted R^2 values are reported.

Factor	Subgroups (n)	Observations (n)	min. corr. adj. R^2	max. corr. adj. R^2
Baking quality score	9	543	0.839	0.988
Baking quality group	3	543	0.938	0.964
VCU trial series	3	625	0.945	0.978
Field trial location	16	625	0.847	0.997

Stability analysis

Environmental conditions can differ strongly between field trials, strongly affecting baking volumes. It is, however, required that the SMT results do not have a larger variability or lower stability than the RMT results, as a new method needs to be equally consistent as the hitherto used standard method, *i.e.* the RMT. The relationship of the variety mean to its coefficient of variation (CV)

is expected to be stable. After excluding varieties only tested in 1 or 2 field trials, linear regression of the CV on variety mean baking volume shows a stable CV. The slope did not differ significantly from 0 ($p = 0.532$ and $p = 0.844$ for RMT and SMT, respectively), showing that the SMT leads to data of equal variability as the RMT.

Figure 5 Regression plot between SMT and RMT baking volume by baking quality group of VCU tested winter wheat varieties in 2020, 2021 and 2023 ($n=543$). Adjusted R^2 was 0.938, 0.945 and 0.964 for high (H), medium (M) and low (L) quality wheats, respectively. Linear regression lines have similar slopes, indicating a similar RMT-SMT baking volume relationship for the three baking quality groups.

Regression

For regression analysis between RMT and SMT baking volume, some outliers were removed and homoscedasticity was checked. Variance did not differ between the two parameters ($p = 0.164$). A linear model according to the formula $VOLS = \beta_0 + \beta_1 \times VOLU + \varepsilon$ was composed, showing a significant positive relation between the two ($p < 0.001$), aligning well with the correlation calculation above. The estimated slope of the model is $b = 1.055$, indicating an average 5.52% higher SMT volume per mL RMT volume. Within the different quality groups, regression also shows to be highly similar, with b varying between 1.042 and 1.050 (Fig. 5).

Regression within individual field trials is less uniform ($b = 0.91$ to 1.24 ; $p < 0.01$). After the removal of 3 trials with adjusted $R^2 < 0.7$ (Loosdorf 2020 and 2023; Sitzendorf 2023), in 22 out of 30 field trials, SMT volumes were higher than RMT volumes, while in 8 field trials it was vice versa. Adjusted R^2 ranged from 0.786 to 0.998, showing a strong to very strong relation between the two methods in all experiments. The fact that the direction of the relationship can differ between trials (*i.e.* an estimate or slope from both <1 and >1) is a worrying indication. Summarising all trials per year, however, shows the required consistency in this regard with slopes between 1.02 (2021) and 1.1 (2020) ($p < 0.01$ for all years, adj. R^2 between 0.90 and 0.98).

Furthermore, to inspect interactions, a linear model of SMT baking volume by RMT baking volume was built with inclusion of each of the following factors, respectively: year, VCU series (western, easter, organic and/or early maturity nursery) and field trial location. Significant interactions of the year on the relationship between RMT and SMT baking volume were found. A model built using the formula $VOLS = \beta_0 + \beta_1 \times VOLU + \beta_2 \times \text{year} + \beta_3 \times VOLU \times \text{year} + \varepsilon$ estimates the effect of VOLU on VOLS ($b = 1.06$; $p < 0.001$). It also finds a significant but very small interaction between VOLU

and year 2021 of size $-0.04 \text{ mL } 100 \text{ g}^{-1}$ ($p = 0.015$), which likely relates to the significant positive effect of year 2021 on VOLS (estimate = $24.77 \text{ mL } 100 \text{ g}^{-1}$, $p = 0.002$). Apparently, in 2021, SMT volume was generally higher ($507.7 \text{ mL } 100 \text{ g}^{-1}$) than in 2020 and 2023 (501.8 and $496.7 \text{ mL } 100 \text{ g}^{-1}$, respectively), but in interaction with RMT, SMT volumes were slightly reduced. In other words, a highly significant positive relationship between RMT and SMT baking volumes exists, but in 2021 – a year in which the positive VOLU-VOLS relation is even stronger than in other years – the regression is slightly less positive for increasing RMT volumes. However, the year effect is relatively small and does not affect the long term relationship.

Field trial, VCU series and field trial location did not influence the RMT-SMT baking volume relationship, meaning it is stable throughout these factor levels. Especially the absence of an effect of individual field trials on the regression is reassuring, considering the instability of the direction of the RMT-SMT baking volume relationship between field trials described above.

Summary

Since the development of the Austrian baking quality model in 1994, some minor changes to the baking test recipe and evaluation of quality traits have been implemented. A few traits that were never officially implemented in the model have been abandoned. Additions to the model include the alveograph and the spiral mixer baking test. The SMT has shown to be equally reliable as the RMT and correlates extremely well with the traditional RMT ($r = 0.99$). The volume values resulting from SMT are on average 5.5% higher than the RMT volumes from the same variety. An additional effect of the year was found to influence the relationship between the two baking tests, but its effect is

negligible. The SMT has the advantage of being more representable of the industrial baking process. The RMT, on the other hand, was once introduced especially to challenge flours to an extent where the largest differentiation between varieties could be observed.

This analysis has shown that the two baking tests do not differ in their stability nor in their data variability, which relates to the variety differentiation. In the absence of any objection to introduce the spiral mixer into the Austrian baking quality model, starting in 2025, baking volume from SMT will be used in the Austrian Descriptive List of Varieties combined with RMT baking volume under the parameter "baking volume". Baking tests will be executed using either of both methods, rather than using them in parallel. Single field trials will always be completely analysed with one of the two methods. The average baking volume increase using the spiral mixer will not erode the appropriateness of the baking volume data, due to the use of estimated marginal means to reduce the effect of non-variety factors from field trial data. This way, the analysis of long-term data is also safeguarded.

References

AGES (2024) Österreichische Beschreibende Sortenliste 2024 Landwirtschaftliche Pflanzenarten. Schriftenreihe 21/2024. Österreichische Agentur für Gesundheit und Ernährungssicherheit (AGES) GmbH, Vienna, Austria. [<https://bsl.baes.gv.at/pdf-version>; accessed 28 Apr 2025]

Berliner E, Koopmann J (1929) Kolloidchemische Studien am Weizenkleber nebst Beschreibung einer neuen Kleberprüfung. *Z ges Mühlenw* 6: 57-63.

Börse für Landwirtschaftliche Produkte in Wien (2025) Kurs Premiumweizen, Qualitätsweizen, Mahlweizen 2015-2025. [<https://www.boersewien.at/kursblatt+2400+++1013>; accessed 6 Mar 2025]

Cauvain SP, Clark R (eds, 2017) *The ICC handbook of cereals, flour, dough & product testing. Methods and applications*, 2nd ed. DEStech Publications, Inc, Lancaster, PA.

Fišteš A, Došenović T, Rakić D, Pajin B, Šereš Z, *et al.* (2014) Statistical analysis of the basic chemical composition of whole grain flour of different cereal grains. *Acta Univ Sapientiae Aliment* 7: 45-53.

IREKS (2025) Alveograph. [<https://www.ireks-kompendium.com/mehlanalytik/analyse-methoden-zur-untersuchung-der-proteinqualitaet/alveograph>; accessed 21 March 2025]

Meißner M (2016) *Standard-Methoden für Getreide, Mehl und Brot mit allen aktuellen ICC-Standards*, 8. Aufl. Arbeitsgemeinschaft Getreideforschung (AGF), Detmold. Verlag Moritz Schäfer.

Oberforster M, Schmidt L, Werteker M (1994) Bewertungsschema '94 der technologischen Qualität von Weizensorten (Weichweizen). *Jahrbuch 1993, Bundesanstalt für Pflanzenbau*, pp 257-280. Bundesamt und Forschungszentrum für Landwirtschaft, Wien.

Wozniak A, Makarski B (2013) Content of minerals, total protein and wet gluten in grain of spring wheat depending on cropping systems. *J Elementol* 18:297-305. DOI: 10.5601/jelem.2013.18.2.09

Further reading

Wagner K (1990) *Neuabgrenzung landwirtschaftlicher Produktionsgebiete. Schriftenreihe 61 (Teil I: Burgenland, Niederösterreich, Wien, Steiermark, Kärnten) & Schriftenreihe 62 (Teil II: Oberösterreich, Salzburg, Tirol, Vorarlberg)*. Bundesanstalt für Agrarwirtschaft, Wien. [<https://bab.gv.at/>; Home - Das Institut - Publikationen - Archiv]

Breeding progress and weather dependency in maize trials: Insights from 30 years of VCU testing

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Abstract

Maize breeding and production have undergone significant changes over the last century, evolving from open-pollinated varieties to double hybrids, then to three-way hybrids, and now almost exclusively to single hybrids. In Austria, new hybrids undergo 2-3 years of intensive value for cultivation and use (VCU) testing before registration. This study investigates extensive data from the last 30 years of VCU testing to calculate current trends in breeding progress in Austria. Trial yield data, along with on-farm data from Statistics Austria, are analyzed using the SPARTACUS dataset to assess weather dependencies. The breeding progress of grain maize in Austria was calculated to be 147.4 kg ha⁻¹ year⁻¹ between 1994 and 2024. Despite this progress, yield data from Statistics Austria revealed an average increase of only 94.4 kg ha⁻¹ year⁻¹ from 1970 to 2024, with notable volatility in yields, particularly in recent years. The analysis indicated a strong dependence of yield on the Standardized Precipitation-Evapotranspiration Index (SPEI) in warmer regions, suggesting significant drought-induced yield dependencies that were previously unobserved. However, other regions appear to benefit from rising temperatures, as no strong impact on yield from heat and drought was found. These findings highlight that we are still at the beginning of climate change-induced yield reductions, as evidenced by stagnating on-farm yields in Austria, despite the annual release of superior varieties. This underscores the need for further adaptive strategies in maize cultivation to ensure food security in the face of ongoing climate variability.

Keywords

Climate change · drought · grain yield · *Zea mays*

Introduction

Trees don't grow to the sky (Koch *et al.*, 2004). This is a German proverb, but is it also true for maize yields? Maize breeding has seen significant progress since the introduction of hybrid breeding in the 1930s in the USA and since the 1960s in Austria (Hinterholzer, 1999; Duvick, 2005). Through the continuous improvement of inbred lines, breeding and seed production have

been simplified, evolving from primarily double hybrids to three-way hybrids, and now almost exclusively single hybrids (Hinterholzer, 1999; AGES, 2023). In Austria, approximately 20-25 new maize hybrids are registered annually. The hybrids originate from international breeding programs but must present a progress in the value for cultivation and use (VCU) in Austria. For the registration process in Austria, new maize varieties therefore undergo at least two years of field testing within replicated field trials at multiple sites across Austria, categorized by maturity groups. In these trials, currently relevant varieties are used as long-term check varieties. Thereby, the breeding progress in Austria is well represented.

However, the development of actual yields in agriculture depend on many additional factors, such as changes in cultivation areas, fertilization, or mechanical cultivation techniques (Lobell *et al.*, 2009). Weather conditions are particularly decisive for annual fluctuations. Accordingly, climatic changes are relevant for long-term trends (Almaraz *et al.*, 2008). The increasing frequency and intensity of extreme weather events due to climate change pose significant threats for maize yields and subsequently pose a threat to global food security (IPCC, 2023; Kornhuber *et al.*, 2023).

The aim of this work is to utilize the yield data from VCU maize trials in Austria over the past 30 years to calculate breeding progress and to correlate yield data with climate data from GeoSphere Austria.

Material and methods

VCU testing and breeding progress

The yield data for calculating breeding progress comes from the long-term dataset of the Austrian VCU testing. For the calculation of breeding progress, data from 1990 to 2024 were retrieved. The dataset included 1622 field trials for grain maize. Long-term check varieties are essential for the comparability of yields over the entire time period. In the grain maize trials, 98 varieties were tested for eight or more years. For the calculation of breeding progress, adjusted mean values for each variety were first calculated. This was accomplished using a linear model with fixed effects for trial and variety, with yield as the dependent variable, and weighted with the residual variance of the varieties from a prelim-

inary ordinary least squares (ols) fit. Finally, (weighted) least-squares means were calculated as described by Lenth (2025).

In the next step, the variety estimates were calculated in relation to the year of registration in another model. Varieties with at least 11 data points were considered, which comprised 600 varieties. The same dataset was used to calculate estimated trial means without varietal alteration. The same method as for the varietal estimates was used, but estimating the trial yield with weighted least-squares.

Yield data from Statistics Austria

All yield data from Statistics Austria for grain maize were downloaded from STATcube (Statistik Austria, 2025). Relative yields were calculated, and yield developments over time were estimated using linear models.

Weather data

The SPARTACUS dataset from GeoSphere Austria was downloaded on a daily basis (Hiebl & Frei, 2016). This includes 1 km² cell values for sunshine duration, maximum and minimum air temperature, precipitation, as well as the SPEI-Index and potential evaporation for all of Austria. Mean values for all cell values below 500 m above sea level were calculated for each federal state. Daily mean values were computed as the average of minimum and maximum air temperatures. Monthly values were then averaged or summed. Additionally, the number of days with maximum temperatures $\geq 33^{\circ}\text{C}$ was calculated for each month. A map of hot days (daily temperature $\geq 30^{\circ}\text{C}$, ÖKLIM 1971–2000) was downloaded, and trial sites were identified that were categorized as having more than 9 hot days (Hiebl *et al.*, 2011). Single sites in Styria were excluded because they were too far apart from the other test sites. For these sites, annual means of the estimated trial yields were calculated.

Correlation between weather data and yield data

The yield data from Statistics Austria and yield data of Austrian VCU-trials from “hot regions” were correlated with various weather parameters from the SPARTACUS dataset using graphical representation and linear regressions. All calculations were performed in R version 4.4.1 (<https://www.r-project.org/>).

Results and discussion

The VCU registrations for grain maize in Austria from 1994 to 2024 yielded an estimated breeding progress of 147.4 kg ha⁻¹ year⁻¹. Fig. 1 displays the estimates of varietal yield potentials in relation to the year of registration. Yield increases are not equally distributed across all years, but overall, a steady, mostly linear yield increase from 1994 to 2024 can be observed. This suggests that an asymptotic levelling or plateau of breeding progress has not yet been reached. The calculated breeding progress for Austria aligns with other studies, *e.g.* a yield increase of 159 kg ha⁻¹ year⁻¹ was calculated for the period 1983 to 2012 for variety tests in Germany (Laidig *et al.*, 2014). Somewhat lower values were calculated in trials in the Americas; *i.e.* 107 kg ha⁻¹ year⁻¹ for 1979–1998 in Argentina; 123 kg ha⁻¹ year⁻¹ for 1963–1993 in Brazil, and 77 kg ha⁻¹ year⁻¹ for 1991–2001 in the USA (Duvick, 2005). The calculation of genetic yield increase is often overestimated due to the so-called “aging effect” (Laidig *et al.*, 2014). This describes yield losses of older varieties due to the emergence of new races of pathogens that can overcome existing resistances, *e.g.* as demonstrated for *Helminthosporium turcicum* (Laidig *et al.*, 2014; Ahangar *et al.*, 2016). A similar effect can be expected with adaptations to altered climatic conditions. Additionally, the yield level of VCU trials is generally above on-farm values, as reliable test sites are chosen and severely impaired trials are discarded. This results in greater absolute differences between varieties than under suboptimal conditions (Duvick, 2005).

Figure 1 Breeding progress of grain maize in Austria (14% H₂O). Estimated variety performances displayed according to maturity group from 1994 to 2024, with a linear regression line.

Yield data from Statistics Austria are shown in Fig. 2. Average yield increases between 1970 and 2024 were $94.4 \text{ kg ha}^{-1} \text{ year}^{-1}$. Yields increased steadily between 1970 and 1991. In 1992, yields suddenly dropped below the regression line. That year showed high temperatures in August, only surpassed in 2024, when temperatures reached similarly high values. Ever since, maize yields in Austria have become more volatile, with significant yield drops in 2013 and 2015 when summers were also very hot. The years 2022 to 2024 marked three consecutive years with yields $<10 \text{ t ha}^{-1}$ for maize. From 2009 to 2024, there were 15 years without increases in yield. The discrepancy between steady breeding progress in VCU trials and stagnating yields on farm level clearly indicates the connection to ongoing climatic changes. The Statistics Austria data for 2003-2023 indicated that the SPEI index for August showed a stronger dependence of yield on the SPEI in the warmer regions of Lower Austria ($R^2 = 0.68$) and Burgenland ($R^2 = 0.74$), to a lesser degree in Carinthia ($R^2 = 0.36$) and Styria ($R^2 = 0.41$), while no significant relationship was found in Tirol and Upper Austria (Fig. 3).

These results suggest that, for some federal states of Austria, rising temperatures still benefit maize yields by promoting growth, thus compensating for occurring drought stress. In contrast, other regions are already experiencing strong yield penalties due to drought periods that were not observed a few decades ago, as indicated by the lack of a significant relationship between 1970 and 1990.

Regression of estimated trial means for Austrian VCU-trials conducted in hot test sites (defined as having more than 9 heat days per year) showed the strongest effect for the SPEI index in August ($p < 0.001$, $R^2 = 0.43$), while the summed values for July and August yielded an $R = 0.3$ (Fig. 4). The separate monthly mean temperatures for July and August had a lower effect, with an $R^2 = 0.26$ ($p = 0.002$), respectively, whereas the mean of the two monthly values yielded an $R^2 = 0.43$. Additionally, the summed number of days with maximum temperatures of at least 33°C for July and August showed an $R^2 = 0.4$ ($p < 0.001$).

Figure 2 On farm grain maize yield in Austria in the period 1970 to 2024 (Source of data: Statistik Austria)

Figure 3 Grain maize yield in relation to the standardized precipitation- evapotranspiration index (SPEI) for selected Austrian federal states. Displayed yield data represent the period from 1970 to 2024, the linear regression lines are based on data from 2003 to 2024 (Source of data: Statistik Austria).

Figure 4 Estimated trial means for Austrian VCU-trials conducted in hot locations (defined as having >9 hot days per year, *i.e.* temperatures >30°C) in relation to the standardized precipitation-evapotranspiration index (SPEI) considering harvests from the years 1992 to 2024.

These results underline the findings that hot regions of Austria are already experiencing significant drought and heat conditions, which were not present 35 years ago. Although July is commonly recognized in the literature as a critical period for heat and drought stress due to the sensitive phase around anthesis, this study highlights that drought conditions during this month are only the second most significant factor contributing to yield reduction in Austria (Luo, 2011). In contrast, climatic conditions in August appear to be the most significant contributors to yield reductions, likely due to even more pronounced heat and depleted soil water reserves during grain filling. On a global scale, Zampieri *et al.* (2019) found strong correlations between observed yields and estimated yields calculated by a plant growth model predicting heat and drought stress yield reductions between 1980 and 2010. Similar to the findings in this study, the authors observed increased yield reductions due to heat and drought starting in the 1990s, with a notable increase between 2000 and 2010. Projecting their model into the future, they predict that past significant losses in Europe will become the norm by the 2030s, with even more drastic increases in yield losses until the end of the century (Zampieri *et al.*, 2019).

References

- AGES (2023) Österreichische Beschreibende Sortenliste 2023 Landwirtschaftliche Pflanzenarten. Schriftenreihe 21/2023. Österreichische Agentur für Gesundheit und Ernährungssicherheit (AGES), Wien.
- Almaraz JJ, Mabood F, Zhou X, Gregorich EG, Smith DL (2008) Climate change, weather variability and corn yield at a higher latitude locale: Southwestern Quebec. *Clim Chang* 88:187-197. DOI: 10.1007/s10584-008-9408-y
- Duvick DN (2005) The contribution of breeding to yield advances in maize (*Zea mays* L.). *Adv Agron* 86:83-145. DOI: 10.1016/S0065-2113(05)86002-X
- Hiebl J, Reisenhofer S, Auer I, Böhm R, Schöner W (2011) Multimethodical realisation of Austrian climate maps for 1971–2000. *Adv Sci Res* 6:19-26. DOI: 10.5194/asr-6-19-2011
- Hiebl J, Frei C (2016) Daily temperature grids for Austria since 1961—concept, creation and applicability. *Theor Appl Climatol* 124:161-178. DOI: 10.1007/s00704-015-1411-4
- Hinterholzer J (1999) Produktionserfolge im österreichischen Maisbau. Bericht über die 50. Arbeitstagung der Vereinigung österreichischer Pflanzzüchter, pp 147-151. BAL Gumpenstein, Irdning.
- IPCC (2023) *Climate Change 2022 – Impacts, adaptation and vulnerability: Working group II contribution to the sixth assessment report of the intergovernmental panel on climate change*. 1st ed. Cambridge University Press. DOI: 10.1017/9781009325844
- Koch GW, Sillett SC, Jennings GM, Davis SD (2004) The limits to tree height. *Nature* 428:851-854. DOI: 10.1038/nature02417
- Kornhuber K, Lesk C, Schleussner CF, Jägermeyr J, Pfleiderer P, *et al.* (2023) Risks of synchronized low yields are underestimated in climate and crop model projections. *Nat Commun* 14:3528. DOI: 10.1038/s41467-023-38906-7
- Lenth R (2025). emmeans: Estimated Marginal Means, aka Least-Squares Means. <https://CRAN.R-project.org/package=emmeans>.
- Lobell DB, Cassman KG, Field CB (2009) Crop yield gaps: Their importance, magnitudes, and causes. *Annu Rev Environ Resour* 34:179-204. DOI: 10.1146/annurev.environ.041008.093740
- Luo Q (2011) Temperature thresholds and crop production: a review. *Clim Change* 109:583-598. DOI: 10.1007/s10584-011-0028-6
- Statistik Austria (2025) STATcube - Statistische Datenbank. Statistik Austria - Bundesanstalt Statistik Österreich, Wien. [<https://www.statistik.at/datenbanken/statcube-statistische-datenbank>; accessed 13 Mar 2025]
- Zampieri M, Ceglar A, Dentener F, Dosio A, Naumann G, *et al.* (2019) When will current climate extremes affecting maize production become the norm? *Earth Future* 7:113–122. DOI: 10.1029/2018EF000995

35 years of Austrian VCU testing in soybean – Breeding successes and future challenges

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Abstract

In the 1980s, the national program to promote the cultivation of alternative crops to cereals and maize brought soybeans back into the interest of growers for the first time in many years. However, in these early years of soybean cultivation on a larger scale, mostly (too) late maturing varieties were available. The first registration of a total of 6 varieties could be seen in 1989. From a farmer's view, soybean is convincing in cultivation due to the avoidance of N fertilization, the low need for pesticides, the domestic production of high-quality protein and its good suitability for organic cultivation. Nowadays, the area under cultivation is above 85,000 ha already for three years - with a high portion of organic farming (almost 40%). The main criteria for selecting soybean varieties are early and safe maturity in areas with higher rainfall, high yield potential, good lodging tolerance and at least only medium to low susceptibility to *Sclerotinia* stem rot (*Sclerotinia sclerotiorum*). In arid areas, lodging tolerance is less important; rapid seedling development is crucial for sufficient pod setting height and offers more favorable preconditions for surviving drought periods. Corn, oilseed pumpkin and sugar beet particularly compete with soybean for acreage in climatically suitable growing regions. Thus, sufficiently high soybean yields are needed to compete with these crops. The national list trials currently comprise 80 to 90 varieties and candidate varieties in three trial series per year, according to maturity. By January 15, 2025, the Austrian variety list contains 98 varieties from four maturity groups (000, 00, 0 and I), 47 of which from Austrian breeders.

The data for this study included results from the VCU trials since 1990 for varieties of the maturity groups 000, 00 and 0. The average annual breeding progress was determined by regression of

the variety performance, calculated as adjusted means from all available results of a variety in the period under consideration, on the year of registration. A similar approach is the regression of the variety performance on to the first year of the VCU test period (Laidig et al., 2017). In the very early maturity 7group (000), data from 86 listed or formerly listed varieties from a total of 239 trials (location by year combinations) were available from 1990 to 2024. In the medium-early maturity group (00), the combined analysis included 74 varieties with results from 244 environments in the same period. The acreage of medium-late to late varieties (group 0) is still rather limited and concentrated in the most favorable regions. As a result, the data set is relatively small for the last maturity group: 14 varieties, 57 environments since 2012.

The study showed an average annual yield increase of 57 kg ha⁻¹ for maturity group 000 until 2010 and 76 kg ha⁻¹ year⁻¹ over the last 14 years (Table 1). For maturity group 00 the average annual yield increase was 44 kg ha⁻¹ until 2010 and 51 kg ha⁻¹ year⁻¹ thereafter until 2024. The genetically determined annual increases for oil yield and protein yield are also shown separately for these two periods (Table 1). As the dataset for maturity group 0 is much smaller, the analysis focuses only on yield improvement, which amounts 59 kg ha⁻¹ per year. The nurseries each exhibit relevant cross-variety differences in protein (000: 38.1-47.1%; 00: 37.6-44.7%) and oil content (000: 18.1-22.5%; 00: 18.9-22.4%), but no significant genetic trend over time was observed (000: protein $b=0.019$; oil $b=0.005$; 00: protein $b=0.011$; oil $b=0.000$).

Over the observation period, improvements in lodging tolerance of 1.1 scores on the 1-9 scale can be inferred for the very early maturity group and 1.6 scores for the medium early varieties, but with considerable variation around the trend line. Breeding for

Table 1 Genetic improvement of soybean traits according to the AGES soybean national list trials 1990-2024

Traits	Maturity group 000			Maturity group 00		
	<i>n</i>	<i>R</i> ²	<i>b</i>	<i>n</i>	<i>R</i> ²	<i>b</i>
Grain yield (dt ha ⁻¹)	39 ¹	0.716 ***	0.566	37 ¹	0.685 ***	0.449
	47 ²	0.553 ***	0.759	37 ²	0.445 ***	0.512
Grain protein content (%)	86	0.013 n.s.	0.019	74	0.005 n.s.	0.011
	Protein yield (dt ha ⁻¹)	39 ¹	0.809 ***	0.221	37 ¹	0.633 ***
47 ²		0.523 ***	0.268	37 ²	0.389 ***	0.157
Oil content (%)	86	0.004 n.s.	-0.005	74	0.000 n.s.	0.000
	Oil yield (dt ha ⁻¹)	39 ¹	0.564 ***	0.091	37 ¹	0.636 ***
47 ²		0.440 ***	0.151	37 ²	0.314 ***	0.110
Plant height (cm)	86	0.148 ***	0.197	74	0.024 n.s.	0.094
Lodging tolerance ⁷ (1-9)	86	0.152 ***	-0.031	74	0.233 ***	-0.045
Sclerotinia stem rot (1-9)	62	0.014 n.s.	-0.007	65	0.329 ***	-0.047
Seed mass (g)	86	0.137 ***	0.576	74	0.174 ***	0.655

¹ 1990-2010; ² 2011-2024

*** $p < 0.001$; n.s., not significant

higher lodging tolerance is important in view of more frequent extreme weather events (*e.g.* heavy rainfall) and for higher end-use quality of the crop, especially in case of food use. Slight increases could be detected for plant height and very slight, not significant decreases in infestations by *Sclerotinia* stem rot.

Thousand grain mass was raised by 0.58 g and 0.65 g per year for the 000 and 00 maturity group, respectively. Remarkable breeding progress could be seen in the relationship between maturity requirements and corresponding yield potentials. Recently registered 000-varieties show ≈25% higher grain yields than those with comparable maturity registered 20 years ago.

Future challenges in breeding are associated especially with climate change. Drought tolerance, improved lodging tolerance, optimisation of maturity time and further differentiation of quality profiles in view of the increasing importance of soybeans in human nutrition in addition to their use in feeding. For variety testing, requirements will be derived from the proposal under discussion for the new EU regulation on plant propagating material (EU-Commission, 2023): Assessment of sustainability criteria in plant production and end-use by stressing variety resilience to biotic and abiotic stresses, nutrient efficiency, yield stability and further quality characteristics, particularly in relation to reduced content levels of antinutritive substances.

Keywords

Abiotic stress · *Glycine max* · lodging tolerance · nutrient use efficiency · yield

References

European Commission (2023) Proposal for a Regulation of the European Parliament and of the Council on the production and marketing of plant reproductive material in the Union. European Union, EUR-Lex-52023PC0414-EN [<https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=celex:52023PC0414>; accessed 15 Sep 2025]

Laidig F, Piepho HP, Rentel D, Drobek T, Meyer U, *et al.* (2017) Breeding progress, variation, and correlation of grain and quality traits in winter rye hybrid and population varieties and national on-farm progress in Germany over 26 years. *Theor Appl Genet* 130:981-998. DOI: 10.1007/s00122-017-2865-9

DurdusTools – An online genetic distance calculation tool for efficient variety testing in durum wheat (*Triticum turgidum* L. subsp. *durum* (Desf.) Husn.)

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Abstract

Uniformity, stability, and distinctness (DUS) are obligatory prerequisites for granting variety protection. According to the Convention of the International Union for the Protection of New Varieties of Plants (UPOV) and the Community Plant Variety Office (CPVO), a new variety must be distinct from any other variety of common knowledge. Distinctness is typically evaluated in two-years trials based on various, mainly botanical-morphological plant and grain characteristics. The growing number of varieties of common knowledge calls for alternative approaches to reduce time and money for DUS trials. To this end, the potential integration of molecular data into DUS testing is being discussed and evaluated. DurdusTools is a genetic distance (GD) calculation tool that allows to use molecular data to support the planning of field trials in durum wheat (*Triticum durum*). The tool was developed by the Austrian Agency for Health and Food Safety in close cooperation with its users for DUS testing purposes. Its use requires neither specific infrastructure nor molecular expert knowledge, making it easily accessible and user-friendly.

In total, 893 different durum wheat varieties and breeding lines were collected from the CPVO-entrusted examination offices (EO) in Austria, France, Hungary, Italy, and Spain. The seeds were genotyped by SGS Institut Fresenius GmbH - TraitGenetics Section, Gatersleben, DE, using commercially available 20 K and 25 K SNP wheat microarrays. From these, 3928 high-quality, polymorphic, and consistent SNP markers with high discriminatory power between the tested durum wheat lines were selected. The GD is calculated using the modified Roger's distance (MRD) and applying the pairwise deletion method for missing values. A separate variety file contains selected information of all the 893 durum wheat varieties and breeding lines. Data protection and confidentiality were given great importance. The raw genotypic data are carefully secured and protected, and only the results of the GD calculations are shared between the EOs.

The tool works with input from the molecular data database and the variety file to create the output. User-friendliness was an important principle in the development of the tool. The DUS experts were involved in all stages to ensure a good user experience. Its features foster their needs for both working with Excel

files and using general filter options. Before downloading the results of the GD calculation, filters may be applied. The DUS expert obtains an Excel workbook with the GDs that shows the most similar varieties at the top, the number of SNP markers used in the pairwise calculation, and relevant information about the individual variety that has been used for the comparison. The GD calculation results are used in the second year of DUS trials and support the decision-making process for pairwise comparisons. DurdusTools allows to use molecular data without the need for laboratory equipment and molecular expert knowledge, providing an integrative and easily accessible tool. In conclusion, DurdusTools shows how EOs can take advantage of the latest technologies in DUS testing to overcome challenges due to increasing reference collections. In addition, increasing the reliability of their choices and strengthening their understanding of the genetic structures of their collections. Notably, the tool provides information on candidate varieties that are tested in the EO network already in the first year of DUS testing. The experts mentioned that the DurdusTools approach increased the knowledge exchange and communication between the entrusted EOs.

Keywords

DUS · distinctness · microarray · single-nucleotide polymorphism · variety identification

Acknowledgement

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Further reading

Ribarits A, Bomers S, Zerk T, Alber O, Seereiter J, *et al.* (2024) DurdusTools – An online genetic distance calculation tool for efficient variety testing in durum wheat (*Triticum turgidum* L. subsp. *durum* (Desf.) Husn.). *Crops* 4:584-601. DOI: 10.3390/crops4040041

From chi-square to genomic selection

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Abstract

Agricultural systems need to be more resilient to environmental challenges posed by climate change. There is evidence from climate and crop models that crop yield is going to be negatively affected by climate change by 2050, leading to a strong decrease in yield. Plant breeding will play a central role in accomplishing these challenges in the coming decades and achieving this goal will depend heavily on the generation and use of new knowledge as well as the use of innovations in crop breeding.

The starting point of modern genetics was the discovery of the “laws of inheritance” by Gregor Mendel in 1865 and 1866 (Mendel, 1866), and their rediscovery in 1900. Afterwards, researchers studied “Mendelian inheritance” for many traits of practical interest and were successful as long as the inheritance was monogenic. Science of genetics was complemented for polygenically inherited traits by the advent of quantitative genetics starting with Fisher (1930).

In the mid-1980s, the first molecular marker system (*i.e.* restriction fragment length polymorphism; RFLP), was applied to wheat in the United Kingdom and the synteny of complementary DNA-RFLP probes among the *Triticeae* being the starting point of comparative genomics (Gale & Devos, 1998). Röder *et al.* (1998) published one of the first molecular maps in bread wheat with a worldwide use, originally comprising 279 SSR loci from the ITMI RILs (W7984×Opata 85). In 2001 the first genetic map of rye (*Secale cereale* L.) combining RFLP, isozyme, microsatellite and gene loci was published (Korzun *et al.*, 2001).

The first initiative towards whole genome sequencing (WGS) in hexaploid bread wheat (*Triticum aestivum* L.) was launched at the meeting of the International Genome Research on Wheat (IGROW) held in Winnipeg, Canada, June 1-4, 2003. The first milestone was the publication of the first draft sequence of the whole bread wheat genome (IWGSC, 2014). For rye, a WGS-based draft genome was published by Bauer *et al.* (2017) and its further improvement by Rabanus-Wallace *et al.* (2021).

The general progress in the development of genomic tools in crops promoted the development of genomic resources in the *Triticeae* species and their use for (a) uncovering the genetic architecture of qualitative and quantitative traits by QTL mapping, (b) achieving a targeted introgression of small genome segments from plant genetic resources, and (c) applying genome-based selection

in the breeding process. In this context, genomics and especially related molecular genetic technologies play an important role in the creation of new plant varieties that optimally combine high and stable yields with resistance to abiotic and biotic stress factors of the respective cultivation environment. Over the past decade, molecular marker technology has provided a wide range of innovative approaches to improve the efficiency of modern breeding strategies and methods. The availability of new molecular tools and technologies has a significant impact on the planning and development of the critical elements of breeding required to accelerate this time-consuming and laborious process.

For complex traits, marker assisted selection (MAS) proved to be too costly and ineffective. Thus, genomic selection (GS) is more efficient for predicting quantitatively inherited traits in non-tested breeding populations based on genomic models derived from extensive training populations. GS is an approach that uses whole-genome marker data to estimate breeding values of untested genotypes and holds the potential to improve the genetic gain in breeding programs by shortening the breeding cycle and increasing the selection intensity.

New genetic variation is urgently necessary for maintaining or even increasing genetic progress (Schulthess *et al.*, 2022). In 2012, the CRISPR/Cas nuclease was first introduced into eukaryotes. One year later, genome editing was published in model plants (*Arabidopsis thaliana*, *Nicotiana benthamiana*). Despite the existence of alternative tools, the CRISPR/Cas system became the most efficient and widely used tool for genome engineering. The first example in wheat was the simultaneous knockout of the three homoeoalleles of the *Mlo* gene in hexaploid bread wheat that confers durable powdery mildew resistance (Wang *et al.*, 2014).

The availability of new molecular tools and technologies is beginning to filter through the breeding programs to have a significant impact on plant variety development and is proving to be the essential element required to accelerate this process and increase the genetic gain.

Keywords

Breeding · genome editing · genomic selection · molecular markers · reference genome · *Secale cereale* · *Triticum aestivum*

References

- Bauer E, Schmutzer T, Barilar I, Mascher M, Gundlach H *et al.* (2017) Towards a whole-genome sequence for rye (*Secale cereale* L.). *Plant J* 89:853-869. DOI: 10.1111/tpj.13436
- Fisher RA (1930) The genetical theory of natural selection. Clarendon Press, Oxford. DOI: 10.5962/bhl.title.27468
- Gale MD, Devos K (1998) Plant comparative genetics after 10 years. *Science* 282: 656-659. DOI: 10.1126/science.282.5389.656
- IWGSC (2014) A chromosome-based draft sequence of the hexaploid bread wheat (*Triticum aestivum*) genome. *Science* 345:286 & 1251788-1 - 1251788-11. DOI: 10.1126/science.1251788
- Korzun V, Malyshev S, Voylokov AV, Börner A (2001) A genetic map of rye (*Secale cereale* L.) combining RFLP, isozyme, microsatellite and gene loci. *Theor Appl Genet* 102: 709-717. DOI: 10.1007/s001220051701
- Mendel G (1866) Versuche über Pflanzen-Hybriden. *Verhandlungen des Naturforschenden Vereins zu Brünn* 4: 3-47. [<http://vlp.mpiwg-berlin.mpg.de/library/data/lit26745>; accessed 27 Jan 2025]
- Rabanus-Wallace MT, Hackauf B, Mascher M, Lux T, Wicker T *et al.* (2021) Chromosome-scale genome assembly provides insights into rye biology, evolution, and agronomic potential. *Nat Genet* 53: 564-573. DOI: 10.1038/s41588-021-00807-0
- Röder MS, Korzun V, Wendehake K, Plaschke J, Tixier M-H *et al.* (1998) A microsatellite map of wheat. *Genetics* 149:2007-2023. DOI: 10.1093/genetics/149.4.2007
- Schulthess AW, Kale SM, Liu F, Zhao Y, Philipp N *et al.* (2022) GiPS: Genomics-informed parent selection uncovers the breeding value of wheat genetic resources. *Nat Genet* 54: 1544-1552. DOI: 10.1038/s41588-022-01189-7
- Wang Y, Cheng X, Shan Q, Zhang Z, Liu J *et al.* (2014) Simultaneous editing of three homoeoalleles in hexaploid bread wheat confers heritable resistance to powdery mildew. *Nat Biotechnol* 32: 947-951. DOI: 10.1038/nbt.2969

Further reading

- Korzun V, Melz G, Börner A, (1996) RFLP mapping of the dwarfing (*Ddw1*) and hairy peduncle (*Hp*) genes on chromosome 5 of rye (*Secale cereale* L.). *Theor Appl Genet* 92:1073-1077. DOI: 10.1007/BF00224051
- Miedaner T, Korzun V (eds., 2018) Applications of genetics and genomics research in cereals. Woodhead Publishing; Elsevier. DOI: 10.1016/C2016-0-04192-X

Comparing prediction accuracy of genomic and phenotypic selection in winter wheat

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Abstract

In early yield trial generations, selection decisions are often based on results from a single year and several locations. However, due to genotype by environment interaction (G×E) and variation in yearly conditions, phenotypic results from single years are only partly representative of any future years. As genomic selection (GS) models are trained on data from several years, we hypothesize that GS models produce more stable predictions across years than pure phenotypic testing.

To test our hypothesis, we compared three different selection scenarios for grain yield in the first year of multi-location yield trials (YT1) of our breeding program:

- (A) Phenotypic selection based only on the results from the yield trials (YT1);
- (B) Genomic selection based only on GS predictions, without any previous observations of the test lines included in the training model.
- (C) Genomic selection with updated model after harvest based on GS predictions after updating the model with results from the yield trials (YT1).

To assess, the efficiency of selection, we correlated the predictions from the different scenarios with the mean yield of the two following years (YT2 and YT3, including only selected lines), representing the best available estimate of performance in other years than the selection year.

Data were taken from the winter wheat breeding program of Agroscope and DSP. Yield trials are performed as lattice designs with 25 or 36 entries over three generations (YT1 approx. 250 lines, YT2 approx. 75 lines, YT3 approx. 30 lines). Trials are conducted in 4 to 5 locations across Switzerland with 2 (YT1 and YT2) to 3 (YT3) replications. Lines were genotyped with the 25k SGS-TraitGenetics SNP array. Means over replicates were first calculated per lattice within each location and year. Subsequently, means were calculated across locations (and years) with a mixed model with genotype and lattice as random effect. Genomic selection models were performed as GBLUP with the rrBLUP package in R (Endelman, 2011). YT data from the breeding program were used as training data and consisted of about 1600 to 1800 lines, depending on YT1 year and prediction scenario.

Over all years, predictions based on only phenotypic observations are slightly better than prediction from genomic selection ($r=0.58$ vs $r=0.51$; Fig. 1). However, yield trials are much more costly and only a limited number of lines can be assessed. Although slightly better, phenotypic prediction shows to be less stable across years than genomic selection as indicated by the greater spread of the prediction accuracies in Fig. 1. In some years, the prediction accuracy of phenotypic selection was very low (e.g. 2019 and 2021; Fig. 2). In these years, genomic selection would have been more precise. The selection scenario C, where the genomic selection models was updated with phenotypic observations, showed best prediction accuracies across all years.

Figure 1: Average prediction accuracy over all years. Each point represents one testing year of YT1. See text for description of the different prediction scenarios.

Figure 2: Prediction accuracies of the different selection scenarios (A, B, C) for the different YT1 years. N: number of lines. See text for description of the different prediction scenarios.

Keywords

Genomic selection · grain yield · prediction accuracy · *Triticum aestivum* · wheat

References

Endelman JB (2011) Ridge regression and other kernels for genomic selection with R package rrBLUP. *Plant Genome* 4:250-255. DOI: 10.3835/plantgenome2011.08.0024

Genomic selection for low deoxynivalenol (DON) content in winter wheat

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Abstract

Wheat contamination with *Fusarium* mycotoxins is an economic burden. Contemporary methods for *Fusarium* evaluation lack the comprehensive data needed to accelerate breeding. Therefore, we aim to lay the foundation for more efficient resistance breeding against *Fusarium* by targeting deoxynivalenol (DON) and using genomic selection (GS). A reference set of 300 genotypes was phenotyped over two years across three locations, using artificially inoculated trials. *Fusarium* resistance was evaluated by visual scoring and DON content measurement by HPLC. Additional traits, including plant height, heading date and anther extrusion were also scored. In the third year, a validation set of additional 225 genotypes were evaluated under the same conditions to assess the potential of GS by comparing observed phenotypes with genomic predictions from models trained. Satisfactory phenotypic results were obtained for all years and most locations, with high and homogeneous *Fusarium* pressure and DON accumulation. The correlation between *Fusarium* symptoms and DON was moderate ($r = 0.54$), confirming that DON measurement is a valuable asset for resistance breeding. Correlations with other traits confirmed that both height and earliness influence *Fusarium* infection and should be considered. For both *Fusarium* traits, the first independent validation of GS through the validation set yielded moderate prediction abilities ($r = 0.3-0.4$), while prediction abilities from cross-validation schemes with the full set of available data (525 genotypes, 3 years) reached values of 0.5 to 0.6. These results provide a solid basis for selecting more *Fusarium*-tolerant wheat based on genomic prediction, ultimately benefiting the entire wheat production value chain in Switzerland.

Keywords

Anther extrusion · deoxynivalenol (DON) · *Fusarium* · genomic selection · *Triticum aestivum* L.

Introduction

Fusarium infection and the resulting contamination of bread wheat (*Triticum aestivum*) with mycotoxins is both an economically important and a growing concern in Switzerland. Feedback from grain warehouses and mills, indicates that some recently released cultivars show increased susceptibility to *Fusarium*. While farmers have various management options for controlling *Fusarium*, the infection is ultimately measured by DON content when wheat is sold. Wheat lots with deoxynivalenol (DON) contents exceeding $1250 \mu\text{g kg}^{-1}$ are unsuitable for human consumption, and depending on the target animal species and DON content such lots may also be not acceptable for animal feed. This results in substantial economic losses for farmers. This issue extends beyond producers and processors to impact consumer food security. While strict food controls across the entire value chain are essential, preventing *Fusarium* infection by cultivating resistant cultivars is a highly effective strategy to minimize the risk of mycotoxin contamination.

In Swiss wheat breeding and cultivar testing, it has become apparent that the current method of *Fusarium* evaluation (single-location disease trial with artificial inoculation and visual assessment of the infection) lacks the data needed to generate adequate breeding progress. Resistance to *Fusarium* in wheat is a complex quantitatively inherited trait characterized by multiple mechanisms and, thus, difficult to assess in the field. Hitherto, classical approaches of marker-assisted selection relied on a few QTL with large and stable effects, e.g. *Fhb1* (Miedaner & Korzun, 2012). In the Agroscope/DSP breeding program, the introgression of this QTL improved resistance, but the resulting breeding lines were not sufficiently competitive for other traits such as grain yield and baking quality. Due to its quantitative inheritance, based on many gene loci with small effects, *Fusarium* resistance is suitable for genomic selection (GS). Several studies have reported the potential of GS for *Fusarium* resistance, including resistance to DON accumulation (Rutkoski *et al.*, 2012; Arruda *et al.*, 2015; Dong *et al.*, 2018; Herter *et al.*, 2019; Verges *et al.*, 2020; Larkin *et al.*, 2021; Nannuru *et al.*, 2025).

In 2018, Agroscope/DSP introduced GS in the wheat breeding program in collaboration with ETH Zürich. Over 6000 cultivars and breeding lines have already been genotyped with high-density SNP markers, and the initial results for complex traits such as grain yield or baking quality show promising predictive values. The aim of this project was to provide precise data on resistance to *Fusarium* as well as on DON content at three locations and across three years in Switzerland, and to develop a GS model to breed Swiss wheat with tolerance to *Fusarium* and accumulation of DON.

Material and methods

Field trials

Trials were conducted over three growing seasons (2021-2023) at three Swiss locations (Changins: 46°23'57" N, 6°14'09" E; Delley: 46°54'48" N, 6°58'03" E; Cadenazzo: 46°09'00"N, 8°56'60" E). At each location and year, 300 wheat genotypes were sown in single-row plots and two replicates. Four cultivars with well-known resistance or susceptibility to *Fusarium* were chosen as check and sown in additional ten replicates. All trials were artificially inoculated with spores of *F. culmorum* provided by the wheat pathology/pre-breeding team at Agroscope, with three to four inoculation dates per site. Because weather conditions (Table 1) are conducive for *Fusarium* infection (with frequent rainfalls during the flowering stage), only the trial at Cadenazzo was rainfed, whereas the other two trials were irrigated before and after each inoculation date in order to maximize the chances of a good and homogeneous infection.

Plant material

The 300 genotypes used for the 2021 and 2022 trials were 283 winter wheats and 17 spring wheats. Most of the genotypes were advanced lines (152) or registered cultivars (96) from the Agroscope/DSP Swiss breeding program. The 52 remaining genotypes were cultivars from other European breeding programs. The Swiss genotypes were chosen based on their pedigree, descending or not from resistant cultivars (*i.e.* 'Sumai 3', 'Frontana', 'Arina'), and based on previous observations to have a good balance between low, medium or good *Fusarium* resistant genotypes. The four check cultivars were 'CH Nara' (susceptible), 'Arina' (resistant) and two cultivars known to be moderately resistant, *i.e.* 'Molinera' and 'Zinal'.

In 2023, 25 resistant genotypes, 25 intermediate-resistant genotypes, and 25 susceptible genotypes were selected from the original 300 genotypes based on field and DON content data. They were tested again with 225 new advanced lines at the three locations described above. The new set was composed by 216 winter wheat and 9 spring wheats; 214 advanced lines and 11 registered

cultivars; 218 Agroscope/DSP genotypes and 7 from other European countries.

Traits scored

Resistance to *Fusarium* was assessed both by visual scoring of symptoms, and by measuring the DON content of harvested grain samples. Visual assessment was conducted over three to four scoring dates per location, with scores on a 1 – 9 scale (1 = no symptoms; 9 = complete infection of spikes). These data were integrated into a single parameter by calculating the area under the disease progress curve (AUDPC) which incorporates the growing degree days (GDD):

$$(1) \quad GDD = \frac{(T_{max} + T_{min})}{2} - T_0$$

where T_{max} and T_{min} are daily maximum and minimum temperatures and T_0 the base temperature which was assumed to be 5°C (McMaster & Wilhelm, 1997). From these data AUDPC was calculated using:

$$(2) \quad AUDPC = \sum_{j=1}^{N_j-1} \frac{y_j + y_{j+1}}{2} (GDD_{j+1} - GDD_j)$$

Here the visual *Fusarium* scores were transformed to a percentage scale y and the corresponding growing degree days GDD at date j . *Fusarium* score was assumed to be 1 (1%) at heading date.

DON content was measured using mature ears from individual plots. They were harvested and threshed minimizing the loss of small or *Fusarium*-damaged kernels (Agriculex LBT-2A Belt Thresher, Guelph, CA). The resulting grain samples were delivered to Romerlabs (Romer Labs Diagnostic GmbH, Tulln, AT), an external lab accredited for and specialized on mycotoxin analysis, to assess DON concentrations using quantitative HPLC-MS/MS method. In addition to the two *Fusarium* resistance traits, the following complementary traits were assessed, as they might influence *Fusarium* infection:

- (i) heading date (expressed as number of days after 1st January)
- (ii) final plant height without awns (cm)
- (iii) anther extrusion (1 = no extrusion; 5 = maximum extrusion), assessed over four to five scoring dates during the flowering period. For each plot the maximum anther extrusion score was used for further analysis. To limit the costs of DON analysis, the trials were conceived as facultative partially replicated (p -rep) designs, which allowed for one complete replicate and one third of the second replicate to be analyzed at each location for DON. All other traits were assessed using the two full replicates at each location.

Table 1 Precipitation and daily mean temperature for the three Swiss test sites (2003-2023)

Location (altitude)	Annual mean		April - July mean	
	Precipitation (mm)	Daily temperature (°C)	Precipitation (mm)	Daily temperature (°C)
Changins (430 m a.s.l.)	944	11.1	684	12.5
Delley (497 m a.s.l.)	809	10.1	654	11.3
Cadenazzo (215 m a.s.l.)	1635	12.3	1107	13.5

Statistical analysis

Analyses of phenotypic data were carried out using R software (v. 4.3.1) and the package SpATS for adjusting spatial inhomogeneity at individual locations (Rodríguez-Alvarez *et al.*, 2018). To achieve a normal distribution of residuals, both the traits AUDPC and DON were logarithm-transformed prior to analysis. Spatial adjusted plot data were subsequently used in a linear mixed model in R to obtain adjusted genotype means across locations and years and estimates of trait heritability. Due to significant correlations of the *Fusarium* resistance traits with both heading date and plant height, a statistical adjustment was implemented, whereby heading and plant height were used as co-factors in a multiple linear regression model, with the respective resistance trait as the response variable. The residuals from this multiple regression model were then taken as the new adjusted resistance trait.

All lines were genotyped using the 25K SNP chip by SGS-TraitGenetics (Gatersleben, DE). To remove heterozygous marker points, marker calls deviating from A, T, G, or C were classified as missing. After, any marker with >5% missing data or having a minor allele frequency (MAF) <5% was removed. The marker data was converted to numeric values alphabetically (0 or 1, by coercion using 'as.numeric(as.factor())', base R). To impute missing data, the markers were first anchored and ordered along the chromosomes. This was done by fitting a local polynomial regression ('loess', base R) between physical position and the 90K genetic map. A correlation matrix was then derived for all pairs of markers using the 'cor' function with 'use = "pairwise.complete.obs"' parameters. From these data, mapping position was taken from the marker with the highest correlation. Once all markers were ordered, missing data were imputed using the *k*-nearest neighbors method (Schwender *et al.*, 2012), from the "scrim" package ('knncatimpute', v1.3.5). Whereby missing values are imputed by finding the ten most similar records in the dataset for each record with missing values, and then using the values from those records to fill in the missing values.

After the quality check, 20 022 SNP markers were left for all genome-based analyses. Genomic selection accuracy was assessed through a 20×5 cross-fold validation. The cross-fold validation process, initiated by using cross numbers ranging from 1 to 20 as the seed for random number generation ('set.seed' in base R), divided the dataset into five folds using the 'crossv_fold' function from the "modelr" package (v0.1.11). However, the final model was trained using data from all 525 lines. The genomic selection prediction accuracy was tested a mixture of a point of mass at zero and a scaled-t slab BayesB (BayesB; Meuwissen *et al.*, 2001), using the "BGLR" (v1.1.0; Pérez & de los Campos, 2014) package with 20 000 iterations and a burn in of 5000. Cross validations were tested using observed (y) and predicted values (\hat{y}) using the correlation ('cor', base R). Marker effects were summarized as the mean (\bar{x}) effect over the 20×5 cross-fold validation.

Three prediction scenarios with different sizes and compositions of the training set were used in the cross-validation scheme:

- (i) a training set ($n = 466$) based on the total pool of genotypes available across the three years;
- (ii) a training set ($n = 240$) based on always different random subsets extracted from (i) to match the size of the reference set;
- (iii) a training set ($n = 240$) that used the genotypes of the original reference set exclusively.

Results and discussion

Population structure

Using the 25k SNPs markers data, the comparison of the 300 genotypes used in 2021 and 2022 with the new 225 genotypes used in 2023 showed a good overlap between the two panels. Nevertheless, the spring wheats formed a separate cluster (Fig. 1).

Phenotypic results

Figure 1 Principal components analysis (PCA) based on the 25k SNP-data. PC1 and PC2 explain 12.8 % and 3% of the variance, respectively.

We obtained satisfactory phenotypic results for all years and most locations, with generally high and spatially homogeneous *Fusarium* pressure in the trials and high levels of DON accumulation (Table 2). The last two trial years (2022 and 2023) encountered hot and dry conditions during flowering at Delley and Changins. The irrigation regimes at both locations were critical in establishing a high degree of *Fusarium* infection in the trials. An exception was the trial at Delley in 2022 that, despite the presence of obvious visual symptoms did not show a significant contamination with DON (more than half of the samples displayed DON concentrations below the detection threshold, while the remaining were at least a factor of ten below the concentrations recorded at the other two locations) (Fig. 2). A possible explanation for this unusual result might be that the ears dried too quickly after irrigation to allow *Fusarium* to establish itself and produce sufficient amounts of DON (Mesterhazy, pers. commun.). Consequently, results for DON content from the 2022 trial at Delley were removed from the analysis.

At Cadenazzo, the trials were always conducted without irrigation, as the natural weather conditions with frequent rainfalls during flowering were conducive for *Fusarium* infection. The results confirmed this by high DON concentrations in all three years, albeit mostly below the levels recorded in the two irrigated locations. When comparing to DON concentrations that are typically

Table 2 Mean values (2021-2023; 3 test sites; $n = 525$ genotypes) for evaluated traits and their heritability (h^2)

	Heading date (d after Jan. 1)	Plant height (cm)	Anther extrusion (1-5)	<i>Fusarium</i> symptoms (AUDPC)	DON content ($\mu\text{g kg}^{-1}$)
Minimum	130	66	1.4	916	1326
Mean	144	93	3.3	3,829	9456
Maximum	151	121	4.5	13,494	29144
Location/Year (n)	3	2-3	2	3	3 (p -rep)
h^2	0.94	0.93	0.64	0.84	0.77

reported in commercial wheat cultivation, the DON contents observed in the trials were high, often exceeding the legal limit for human consumption of $1250 \mu\text{g kg}^{-1}$. Despite these overall high levels of DON contamination, variations between the tested genotypes were important, where susceptible cultivars show high and resistant cultivars show lower concentrations of DON. We also observed significant genotype \times environment interactions, e.g. for the two moderately resistant check cvs. 'Zinal' and 'Molinera'. Their ranking was not always the same between locations or years and in one case 'Zinal' even displayed lower DON levels than resistant 'Arina'. Despite these genotype \times environment interactions, which are expected for quantitative resistance traits, the high genetic variances resulted in high heritabilities for both AUDPC and DON (Table 2). We are, thus, confident that the obtained phenotypic results are valuable both for GS application in the breeding program, as well as for a better characterization of current wheat cultivars and advanced candidate cultivars. The correlation between AUDPC and DON was moderate ($r = 0.54$), confirming that an assessment of the visual symptoms alone is insufficient for inferring DON accumulation reliably (Table 3).

Hence, the systematic measurement of DON as performed in this project, although expensive and time consuming, is a valuable asset for GS-based resistance breeding activities. Correlations of the two resistance traits with plant height and heading date were low to moderate but significant (Table 3), and confirmed that both plant height and earliness (measured as heading date) influence *Fusarium* infection, which should be taken into account when implementing GS (Moreno-Amores *et al.*, 2020) and evaluating the cultivars in the frame of the breeding program. We suggest using the adjusted versions of AUDPC and DON in the GS-framework to avoid the risk of selecting for infection avoidance artefacts arising from final height and earliness. Moreover, the statistical adjustment improved the correlation between DON and visual symptoms by more than 0.1, indicating the adjusted version of AUDPC may offer a better proxy for "true" *Fusarium* resistance, including resistance to DON accumulation (Table 3). As such, adjusted AUDPC, especially when combined with a high-throughput and reliable assessment of *Fusarium* damaged kernels (FDK%), might provide a good option for our future routine resistance breeding activities when we no longer can rely on expensive DON analyses.

We also reported significant ($p < 0.001$) negative correlations between the two *Fusarium* resistance traits and anther extrusion: these correlations were low ($r = -0.32$) for AUDPC and moderate ($r = -0.55$) for DON. The correlation of anther extrusion with DON was in the same magnitude as the correlation between DON and AUDPC, suggesting that anther extrusion probably has a more pronounced effect on DON accumulation than on visual symptoms. Negative correlations were experienced in other studies (Skinner

et al., 2010; Lu *et al.*, 2013; Buerstmayr & Buerstmayr, 2015; Xu *et al.*, 2019), where genotypes with more pronounced anther extrusion tend to show better resistance. Some of these studies suggest that anther extrusion could represent a useful morphological marker in *Fusarium* resistance breeding. However, visual scoring of this trait in the field is challenging. Surprisingly, heritability for anther extrusion was good in the present study ($h^2 = 0.64$), albeit lower than for all other traits. Because anther extrusion is a key trait in hybrid wheat breeding (Muqaddasi *et al.*, 2017), significant research efforts are currently being made to improve its assessment. It is possible that viable high-throughput, image-based phenotyping methods will be available for this trait in the near future (Winn *et al.*, 2021). Meaning selection for low anther extrusion can be used to indirectly select for low DON content.

Genomic prediction

Plant height was confirmed as the most predictable trait, both in the independent validation and in the cross-validation schemes, with a mean prediction ability around $r = 0.7$. While plant height can be easily phenotyped, it serves as a practical checkpoint in genomic selection. Plant height is primarily determined by two mutations: *Rht-B1*, which reduces height by ≈ 15 cm, and *Rht-D1*, which reduces height by ≈ 10 cm. These mutations should be identified in the genomic selection model, which was confirmed here (data not shown).

The prediction abilities for the other traits were in an intermediate range, and consistent with the more quantitative nature of these traits as compared to plant height. For both *Fusarium* resistance traits, the independent validation through the validation set yielded moderate prediction abilities in the range $r = 0.3 - 0.4$ (Fig. 3), while prediction abilities from the cross-validation scheme conducted with the full set of available data (525 genotypes, 3 years) reached values of $r = 0.5 - 0.6$ (Fig. 4). Realistically, in the implementation phase we can expect prediction abilities in the $Vr = 0.4 - 0.5$ range, which is sufficient for achieving important breeding progress through GS. Similar studies in terms of traits and number of genotypes reported prediction abilities in comparable ranges (Arruda *et al.*, 2015; Dong *et al.*, 2018; Verges *et al.*, 2020), and were all optimistic about the prospects of GS for improving *Fusarium* resistance. Two recent studies implementing more complex approaches, such as multi-trait genomic prediction models, reported prediction abilities consistently in the $r = 0.5 - 0.6$ range for both DON and visual symptoms, with values of up to $r = 0.8$ depending on the specific approach used (Larkin *et al.*, 2021; Nannuru *et al.*, 2025). The study by Nannuru *et al.* (2025) also included SNP markers with the largest effects on the trait as fixed factors in the model, reporting significant enhancements in prediction accuracy compared to the standard GS model.

Table 3 Pearson correlation coefficients (r) between traits, based on 2021-2023 cultivar means, ($n = 525$ cultivars). Significance is indicated by: ns = $p > 0.05$, * = $p < 0.05$, ** = $p < 0.01$ and *** = $p < 0.001$

	Heading date	Plant height	Anther extrusion	<i>Fusarium</i> -symptoms (AUDPC)	<i>Fusarium</i> symptoms adjusted	DON content
Plant height	-0.02 ^{ns}					
Anther extrusion	-0.33***	+0.22***				
<i>Fusarium</i> symptoms (AUDPC)	-0.24***	-0.36***	-0.32***			
<i>Fusarium</i> symptoms adjusted	+0.00 ^{ns}	+0.00 ^{ns}	-0.36***	+0.90***		
DON content	+0.39***	-0.30***	-0.55***	+0.54***	+0.58***	
DON content adjusted	+0.00 ^{ns}	+0.00 ^{ns}	-0.41***	+0.59***	+0.66***	+0.88***

Figure 2 DON-content of check cultivars ‘Arina’, ‘CH Nara’, ‘Molinera’ and ‘Zinal’ by location and year.

These approaches are worth exploring and may help in improving our prediction abilities as well. Finally, a further study by Herter *et al.* (2019) reported high prediction abilities ($r > 0.7$) for visually assessed *Fusarium* severity, but the training set exceeded 1,000 genotypes. Thus, the increase in accuracy is likely a consequence of increased training data size.

We also observed this effect in our results: when moving from the original RS with 300 genotypes to the new complete set with 525 genotypes, there was a large increase in mean prediction ability for most traits, and an even stronger improvement in the stability of the predictions (*i.e.* reduced variance of the prediction abilities) (Fig. 4).

A successful continuation of GS-use for *Fusarium* resistance in the breeding program depends on several factors, but its current form including systematic DON analyses is unfeasible due to resource constraints. However, the lessons learned from this research will guide future decisions. For example, there is always a compromise between the quality of phenotyping (intensity, accuracy) and the number of genotypes that can be phenotyped. Infection severity is highly dependent upon the year, making multi-trial testing necessary. We also found that increasing the number of training lines improves predictability, albeit with diminishing returns (doubling the number of lines does not double prediction ability). Studies have shown that GS models progressively lose their predictive power over successive breeding cycles if not refreshed with data from contemporary germplasm. Therefore, there is a need to refresh the model calibration periodically, but the frequency and scale of these activities remain to be determined. The knowledge gained in terms of correlated proxies and marker effects will guide future assessments and help optimize our approach.

Impact on sustainability of Swiss bread wheat cultivation

Fusarium is recognized globally as a devastating disease of wheat causing economic yield losses and, more critically, mycotoxin contamination of the grains. Breeding for resistance is the most cost-effective method to control *Fusarium* infection. This is parti-

cularly relevant for wheat cultivation in Switzerland, where approximately 70% of bread wheat is produced without fungicides, insecticides, or growth regulators under the low-input “Extensio” system and organic production methods. Even in the more conventional production system (Conventional and “PER/ÖLN” Ecological Performance Certificate system), only few farmers target *Fusarium* explicitly with fungicide applications during flowering. Instead, most favor earlier treatments that target leaf diseases such as rusts or *Septoria*, since they can be managed with a single application. In contrast, effective *Fusarium* control requires precise application timing.

Current trends in Swiss society and politics continue to push toward reducing chemical inputs in agriculture. As management options for treating *Fusarium* infection become more limited, developing resistant cultivars has become increasingly important. By improving the efficiency of *Fusarium* resistance breeding in the Agroscope/DSP program, the results will make a meaningful contribution for improving the sustainability of bread wheat production in Switzerland.

Characterization of cultivars and advanced candidates to the benefit of the Swiss wheat sector

All the important cultivars of the current Swiss market (recommended list), as well as the most advanced candidates in post-registration cultivar trials, were represented as test genotypes. Results enable a more precise characterization of these cultivars for their reaction to *Fusarium* infection, including resistance to DON accumulation as a novel, previously unavailable trait. Dissemination of these results has already started, to the benefit of the whole Swiss wheat sector. Based on our results, we proposed to evaluate the possibility of introducing DON accumulation as an additional descriptor for the cultivars on the Swiss recommended list, an effort that we deem financially feasible, because of the limited number of cultivars at this advanced stage, and the possibility to collect infected grain samples from Agroscope’s routine artificially inoculated *Fusarium* trial.

Figure 3 Comparison of phenotypic values observed in 2023 for the validation set of 225 new lines, versus predicted values based on a BayesB model trained using the 300 lines of the original reference set phenotyped in 2021 and 2022. Traits are **a** DON content (ln(DON)) and **b** *Fusarium* symptoms (ln(AUDPC)).

Figure 4 Prediction ability estimation for important plant traits based on a five-fold cross-validation scheme for two prediction models (Bayes B and GBLUP) and for three prediction scenarios with different sizes and/or compositions of the training set: (i) training set based on the total pool of genotypes available across the three years ($n = 466$ genotypes); (ii) training set based on a random subset from (i) to match the size of the original reference set ($n = 240$); and (iii) training set using only the genotypes of the original reference set ($n = 240$).

Good farming practices, such as crop rotations avoiding wheat after maize, particularly when no-till is used, and the choice of *Fusarium*-resistant cultivars, should resolve, if not greatly reduce, the risk of DON contamination of wheat grain. The effectiveness of selection is improved by the use of genomic selection for resistance to *Fusarium* with the prediction model developed for low DON content as developed in this study and complements the stacking / introgression of known quantitative *Fusarium* resistance genes. However, beyond DON, other toxins are produced by *Fusarium* (e.g. nivalenone, T2, HT-2, diacetoxyscirpenol, fumonisins B1 & B2, zearalenone, etc.). For the moment, there are fewer controls and legal limits concerning them, but it will be important to take them into consideration in the future, in order to continue selecting healthier cultivars.

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References

Arruda MP, Brown PJ, Lipka AE, Krill AM, Thurber C, *et al.* (2015) Genomic selection for predicting *Fusarium* head blight resistance in a wheat breeding program. *Plant Genome* 8 (3). DOI: 10.3835/plantgenome2015.01.0003

Buerstmayr M, Buerstmayr H (2015) Comparative mapping of quantitative trait loci for *Fusarium* head blight resistance and anther retention in the winter wheat population Capo × Arina. *Theor Appl Genet* 128:1519-1530. DOI: 10.1007/s00122-015-2527-8

Dong H, Wang R, Yuan Y, Anderson J, Pumphrey M, *et al.* (2018) Evaluation of the potential for genomic selection to improve spring wheat resistance to *Fusarium* head blight in the Pacific Northwest. *Front Plant Sci* 9:380423. DOI: 10.3389/fpls.2018.00911

Herter CP, Ebmeyer E, Kollers S, Korzun V, Miedaner T (2019) An experimental approach for estimating the genomic selection advantage for *Fusarium* head blight and *Septoria tritici* blotch in winter wheat. *Theor Appl Genet* 132:2425-2437. DOI: 10.1007/s00122-019-03364-7

Larkin DL, Mason RE, Moon DE, Holder AL, Ward BP, *et al.* (2021) Predicting *Fusarium* head blight resistance for advanced trials in a soft red winter wheat breeding program with genomic selection. *Front Plant Sci* 12:715314. DOI: 10.3389/fpls.2021.715314

Lu Q, Lillemo M, Skinnnes H, He X, Shi J, *et al.* (2013) Anther extrusion and plant height are associated with Type I resistance to *Fusarium* head blight in bread wheat line ‘Shanghai-3/Catbird’. *Theor Appl Genet* 126:317-334. DOI: 10.1007/s00122-012-1981-9

Meuwissen TH, Hayes BJ, Goddard ME (2001) Prediction of total genetic value using genome-wide dense marker maps. *Genetics* 157:1819-1829. DOI: 10.1093/genetics/157.4.1819

Miedaner T, Korzun V (2012) Marker-assisted selection for disease resistance in wheat and barley breeding. *Phytopathology* 102:560-566. DOI: 10.1094/PHYTO-05-11-0157

McMaster G, Wilhelm WW (1997) Growing degree-days: one equation, two interpretations. *Agric Forest Meteorol* 87:291-300. DOI: 10.1016/S0168-1923(97)00027-0

Moreno-Amores J, Michel S, Miedaner T, Longin CFH, Buerstmayr H (2020) Genomic predictions for *Fusarium* head blight resistance in a diverse durum wheat panel: an effective incorporation of plant height and heading date as covariates. *Euphytica* 216:22. DOI: 10.1007/s10681-019-2551-x

Muqaddasi QH, Brassac J, Börner A, Pillen K, *et al.* (2017) Genetic architecture of anther extrusion in spring and winter wheat. *Front Plant Sci* 8:229542. DOI: 10.3389/fpls.2017.00754

Nannuru VKR, Dieseth JA, McCartney CA, Henriquez MA, Buerstmayr H, *et al.* (2025) Assessing single and multi-trait genomic prediction model accuracies including significant GWAS markers for *Fusarium* head blight disease resistance in wheat (*Triticum aestivum*). *Plant Breed* 144:335-349. DOI: 10.1111/pbr.13245

Pérez P, de los Campos G (2014) Genome-wide regression and prediction with the BGLR statistical package. *Genetics* 198:483-495. DOI: 10.1534/genetics.114.164442

Rodriguez-Alvarez MX, Boer MP, van Eeuwijk FA, Eilers PH (2018) Correcting for spatial heterogeneity in plant breeding experiments with P-splines. *Spatial Stat* 23:52-71. DOI: 10.1016/j.jspasta.2017.10.003

Rutkoski J, Benson J, Jia Y, Brown-Guedira G, Jannink JL, *et al.* (2012) Evaluation of genomic prediction methods for *Fusarium* head blight resistance in wheat. *Plant Genome* 5:51-61. DOI: 10.3835/plantgenome2012.02.0001

Schwender H (2012) Imputing missing genotypes with weighted k nearest neighbors. *J Toxicol Environ Health A* 75:438-446. DOI: 10.1080/15287394.2012.674910

Skinnes H, Semagn K, Tarkegne Y, Marøy AG, Bjørnstad Å (2010) The inheritance of anther extrusion in hexaploid wheat and its relationship to *Fusarium* head blight resistance and deoxynivalenol content. *Plant Breed* 129:149-155. DOI: 10.1111/j.1439-0523.2009.01731.x

Verges VL, Lyerly J, Dong Y, Van Sanford DA (2020) Training population design with the use of regional *Fusarium* head blight nurseries to predict independent breeding lines for FHB traits. *Front Plant Sci* 11:1083. DOI: 10.3389/fpls.2020.01083

Winn ZJ, Larkin DL, Murry JT, Moon DE, Mason RE (2021) Phenotyping anther extrusion of wheat using image analysis. *Agronomy* 11:1244. DOI: 10.3390/agronomy11061244

Xu K, He X, Dreisigacker S, He Z, Singh PK (2019) Anther extrusion and its association with *Fusarium* head blight in CIMMYT wheat germplasm. *Agronomy* 10:47. DOI: 10.3390/agronomy10010047

Genome-wide association mapping and genomic prediction of *Septoria nodorum* blotch resistance in Central European winter wheat (*Triticum aestivum* L.)

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Abstract

Septoria nodorum blotch (SNB), caused by *Parastagonospora nodorum* (Berk.), is one of the most destructive fungal diseases affecting winter wheat (*Triticum aestivum* L.). The disease leads to significant yield losses and is exacerbated by warm and humid growing conditions. Resistance to SNB is inherited in a complex manner, making breeding for durable resistance a challenge. Given the increasing demand for sustainable wheat production and the limitations of fungicide-based control, identifying genetic resistance is crucial for breeding programs.

Genome-wide association studies (GWAS) and genomic prediction (GP) offer promising approaches for improving SNB resistance. A total of 1500 winter wheat breeding lines were phenotyped for SNB resistance across 19 locations over 5 years under natural infection. The trials covered a range of environmental conditions to capture genetic variation for resistance. Disease severity was

assessed on a scale from 1 to 9, with 1 representing high resistance and 9 high susceptibility. The genetic data were obtained using genotyping-by-sequencing (GBS), and single nucleotide polymorphism (SNP) markers were filtered for quality control. GWAS was conducted using a mixed linear model incorporating population structure and kinship to detect significant marker-trait associations. Genomic prediction was performed using ridge regression best linear unbiased prediction (RR-BLUP), and fivefold cross-validation was used to assess predictive ability.

Despite the unbalanced breeder's dataset, heritability for SNB resistance ranged from $h^2 = 0.47$ to 0.76 across individual trials, confirming the genetic control of resistance. GWAS identified 11 significant marker-trait associations for SNB resistance located on chromosomes 2A, 2B, 4B, 4D, 5D, and 7B (Fig. 1). These findings suggest the presence of stable resistance loci that could be used for marker-assisted selection. The highest association was detected on chromosome 2B followed by chromosome 2A. In some cas-

Figure 1 Genome-wide association study for *Septoria nodorum* blotch severity in winter wheat. Green dots above the threshold in the Manhattan plot indicate significant markers above $-\log_{10}(p) = 3$ in the studied wheat panel.

es, marker effects varied across years, highlighting the influence of environmental interactions. GP models achieved a predictive ability of 0.52, indicating the potential for GP to accelerate breeding by selecting resistant lines based on genomic information. Prediction accuracy varied across years (Fig. 2) due to environmental factors, with the highest accuracy observed in 2014 (0.53) and lower values in 2015 (0.28). These variations underscore the importance of integrating multi-year data to improve model robustness. The integration of GWAS and GP provides valuable insights into the genetic architecture of SNB resistance and enhances breeding efficiency. The identified SNP markers and resistant genotypes will be useful for developing wheat cultivars with improved resistance. By combining genomic tools with traditional breeding, the selection process can be optimized, reducing phenotyping costs and improving genetic gains for SNB resistance in winter wheat.

Keywords

Genomics · genotyping-by-sequencing · heritability · *Parastagonospora nodorum* · prediction ability

Further reading

Berisha P, Michel S, Löschenberger F, Ametz C, Bistrich H, *et al.* (2025) Genome-wide association mapping and genomic prediction of *Septoria nodorum* blotch resistance in Central European winter wheat (*Triticum aestivum* L.). *Plant Breed* 144:182-191. DOI: 10.1111/pbr.13233

Liu Z, El-Basyoni I, Kariyawasam G, Zhang G, Fritz A, *et al.* (2015) Evaluation and association mapping of resistance to tan spot and *Stagonospora nodorum* blotch in adapted winter wheat germplasm. *Plant Dis* 99:1333-1341. DOI: 10.1094/PDIS-11-14-1131-RE

Figure 2 Variation across and within years for the genomic predictions ability of RR-BLUP models using fivefold cross-validation.

Phan HTT, Rybak K, Bertazzoni S, Furuki E, Dinglasan E, *et al.* (2018) Novel sources of resistance to *Septoria nodorum* blotch in the Vavilov wheat collection identified by genome-wide association studies. *Theor Appl Genet* 131:1223-1238. DOI: 10.1007/s00122-018-3073-y

Piepho H-P, Möhring J (2007) Computing heritability and selection response from unbalanced plant breeding trials. *Genetics* 177:1881-1888. DOI: 10.1534/genetics.107.074229

Ruud AK, Dieseth JA, Ficke A, Furuki E, Phan HTT, *et al.* (2019) Genome-wide association mapping of resistance to *Septoria nodorum* leaf blotch in a Nordic spring wheat collection. *Plant Genome* 12:180105. DOI: 10.3835/plantgenome2018.12.0105

Potential of Genome Wide Association Analysis for major and orphan crop improvement

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Abstract

The world consumption of crops is steadily growing with human population and changing eating habits in the fast-changing environment. In the past 20 years the human population grew by ≈21% from 6.5 to 8.2 billion. Subsequently, the crop consumption grew from ≈2 to ≈2.9 billion tons what is an increase by 30.8%. This growing demand increases pressure on crop production. There are three possibilities how to satisfy the demand. The first could be intensification of the agronomic practices. For example, there are still countries with average wheat yield between 1.5-2 t ha⁻¹, whereas countries like Belgium or the Netherlands can reach to 10 t ha⁻¹. Such intensifications are always accompanied with heavy use of irrigation and agrochemicals. For example, the Czech Republic has grown wheat on 939 000 ha in 2024 and just for one fungicide application ≈560 tons of fungicides are needed and it costs ≈56.3 m €. Moreover, large doses of agrochemicals are threatening the environment and especially the drinkable water sources. The second possibility is expansion of agricultural land. To date, humans are already occupying 46% of the arable land. Nevertheless, additional expansion in cost of forests and wild grasslands is threatening stability of global natural environment. The most promising approach for producing healthy food from crops is breeding varieties with high and stable yield, and resistance to biotic and abiotic stresses. More than half of the world's food comes from three major crops, *i.e.* wheat, rice and maize. However, ensuring global food supply and food security

requires the implementation of other crops which can provide a wide range of nutrients.

The main obstacle for the fast production of new and more efficient cultivars is a time consuming and laborious breeding process. The implementation of new techniques based on genome knowledge can significantly increase the speed and efficiency of breeding. Such techniques, *e.g.* marker assisted selection (MAS), requires enough molecular markers with strong linkage to the desired traits. The standard genetic mapping and quantitative trait loci (QTL) mapping based on biparental populations can provide only a limited number of significant trait-associated markers. At the present time, the main limitation of available high-throughput genotyping pipelines based on reference genome sequences such as SNP chips or pipelines which do not need reference sequence knowledge such as genotyping by sequencing (GBS) or DArTseq, is the resolution of the mapping population. For example, in the wheat genome usually 2 to 4 recombinations per chromosome can be observed per meiosis. This results in the requirement of thousands of F₂ lines for mapping. Unfortunately, populations with such resolution would require enormous investments of resources in genotyping and especially phenotyping.

Another possibility provides the exploration of recombination events accumulated during the evolution of lines/cultivars. The analysis of such natural populations is called genome wide association studies (GWAS) and can provide significantly higher mapping

Figure 1 GWAS analysis of flowering time evaluated in 2018 at Stupice, Czech Republic. The associated locus at chromosome 5A overlaps with the position of *Vrn1A*. The green lines are Bonferroni thresholds at $p=0.05$ (dashed) and 0.01 (solid).

resolution. In light of this, we work on two projects focused on (i) genes available in the population of old cultivars and landraces of wheat (460 lines) from primarily Central Europe with emphasis on the Czech Republic and (ii) on the improvement and integration of orphan crops to the value chains and nutrition portfolio of human food.

In both projects the GWAS analysis is employed to identify markers tightly linked to important agronomic traits. In the first step, the wheat population was genotyped using the DArTseq approach resulting in more than 25 000 reliable SNP markers. The population will be phenotyped for 13 traits including powdery mildew (Pm) resistance and flowering time to verify population sensitivity and resolution. Later, resistance to biotic and abiotic stresses will be investigated and supplemented with yield and quality related traits.

Population analysis proved good homogeneity of the wheat population. Powdery mildew resistance was tested using three *Pm* isolates, *i.e.* *E* and *Tm258* collected in Czechia and *Galina* collected in Russia. GWAS analysis identified 16 significant associations on chromosomes 2B, 2D, 3B, 5B, 5A, 7A, 2D, 3B, Un, 1A, 2D, 3A, 4A, 1B, 1B and 6B. The loci on chromosomes 4A (LOD 6) and 6B (LOD 21.9) overlap with the positions of *Pm16/30* (Chen *et al.*, 2005) and *Pm54* (Hao *et al.*, 2015), respectively. The remaining associated loci are new. GWAS analysis of flowering time without vernalization identified 6 associated loci at chromosomes 5A, 5D, 6B, 7A and 7B which were reproducibly in at least three seasons (Fig. 1). Two loci at chromosome 5A (LOD 42.5 and 2.41, respectively) overlap with the positions of *Vrn1A* (Yan *et al.*, 2003) and *Q* (Faris *et al.*, 2003), the locus at 5D (LOD 11.5) overlaps with *Vrn1D*, and the locus on 7A (LOD 1.94) overlaps with the position of a *Vrn1* gene ortholog. Loci at chromosomes 6B and 7B are new. The identification of known loci with high LOD scores is a proof for the good and reliable detection power of the used GWAS models and the population.

A similar approach was adopted for the analysis of three minor crops, *i.e.* triticale, buckwheat and lupin. The populations with 122–180 lines were DArTseq genotyped. Diversity analysis identified two sub-population in buckwheat and lupin which are corresponding to wild and domesticated lines. These will be taken into account in the mapping of stress and yield related loci. Marker from identified associated loci based on the analysis of linkage

disequilibrium will be converted to PCR markers for the selection of breeding material and their offsprings using MAS.

Keywords

Fagopyrum esculentum · GWAS · *Lupinus angustifolius* · molecular marker · sequencing · *Triticosecale* · *Triticum aestivum*

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References

- Chen XM, Luo YH, Xia XC, Xia LQ, Chen X, *et al.* (2005) Chromosomal location of powdery mildew resistance gene *Pm16* in wheat using SSR marker analysis. *Plant Breed* 124: 225-228. DOI: 10.1111/j.1439-0523.2005.01094.x
- Faris J, Fellers J, Brooks S, Gill B (2003) A bacterial artificial chromosome contig spanning the major domestication locus *Q* in wheat and identification of a candidate gene. *Genetics* 164:311-321. DOI: 10.1093/genetics/164.1.311
- Hao YF, Parks R, Cowger C, Chen ZB, Wang YY, *et al.* (2015) Molecular characterization of a new powdery mildew resistance gene *Pm54* in soft red winter wheat. *Theor Appl Genet* 128: 465-476. DOI: 10.1007/s00122-014-2445-1
- Yan L, Loukouianov A, Tranquilli G, Helguera M, Fahima T, *et al.* (2003) Positional cloning of the wheat vernalization gene *VRN1*. *Proc Natl Acad Sci USA* 100:6263-6268. DOI: 10.1073/pnas.0937399100

Can we teach the machine to select like a plant breeder? A recommender system approach to support early generation selection decisions based on breeder's preferences

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Abstract

Plant breeding is considered to be the science and art of genetically improving plants according to human needs. Scientific breeding is thereby driven by various omics disciplines, while the art of breeding is determined by breeder's intuition and experience that leads to selection decisions by the so-called breeder's eye. Breeders are in this context oftentimes facing the difficult task to select among thousands of genotypes for dozens of traits simultaneously, whereas screening the available data more systematically by recommender systems can potentially ease selection decisions. Using a breeder's selection decisions from a commercial wheat breeding program as a case example this study investigated thus the possibility to implement a recommender system based on breeder's preferences to support early generations selection decisions in plant breeding. The target trait was the retrospective binary classification of selected versus non-selected breeding lines during a period of five years, while the selection decisions of the breeder were predicted by various methods of statistical and machine learning. The explained variance of these selection decisions was of moderate magnitude, and the models' precision suggested that the breeder's selection decisions were to some extent predictable, especially when some of the pending selection candidates were part of the training population. Training statistical or machine learning algorithms with breeder's selection decisions has thus large potential to aid breeders in their decision-making processes, particularly when integrating human and artificial intelligence in the form a recommender system to potentially reduce a breeder's effort and required time to find interesting selection candidates.

Keywords

Breeder's eye · decision support system · genome-wide prediction · machine learning · selection theory

Further reading

Crossa J, Montesinos-López OA, Costa-Neto G, Vitale P, Martini JWR, *et al.* (2025) Machine learning algorithms translate big data into predictive breeding accuracy. *Trend Plant Sci* 30:167-184. DOI: 10.1016/j.tplants.2024.09.011

Crossa J, Martini JWR, Vitale P, Pérez-Rodríguez P, Costa-Neto G, *et al.* (2025) Expanding genomic prediction in plant breeding: harnessing big data, machine learning, and advanced software. *Trend Plant Sci* 30:756-774. DOI: 10.1016/j.tplants.2024.12.009

Michel S, Löschenberger F, Ametz C, Bistrich H, Bürstmayr H (2025) Can we teach machines to select like a plant breeder? A recommender system approach to support early generation selection decisions based on breeders' preferences. *Crops* 5:31. DOI: 10.3390/crops5030031.

Michel S, Löschenberger F, Ametz C, Bistrich H, Bürstmayr H (2025) Towards streamlining the choice of crossing combinations in plant breeding by integrating model-based recommendations and plant breeder's preferences. *Crops* 5:5. DOI: 10.3390/crops5010005.

The long path to resistance: Breeding progress in durum wheat for Fusarium head blight resistance

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Abstract

Fusarium head blight (FHB) is a highly destructive disease in cereals caused by several *Fusarium* species. FHB significantly reduce grain yield and quality, leading to substantial economic losses. Moreover, *Fusarium* produces mycotoxins and other secondary metabolites that pose serious health risks to humans and animals when contaminated grain is consumed.

Durum wheat is widely used for pasta production, but currently, no commercially available variety is resistant to FHB. Unlike hexaploid common wheat, durum wheat has a narrow genetic base which hampers the development of resistant varieties against FHB. Developing resistant varieties is crucial not only for ensuring the safety and quality of pasta and its by-products but also for promoting sustainable agriculture by reducing the reliance on fungicides and minimizing yield losses.

Field-based disease screenings for FHB were conducted over four years (2021-2024) at BOKU. The plant materials used included durum wheat populations consisting of (i) progenies from the cross between 'Capdur' and BOKU breeding lines, both showing moderate resistance to FHB. 'Capdur' is an old French variety known for lower anther retention and short plant height; (ii) selected cultivars and breeding lines; and (iii) BOKU lines that do not include 'Capdur' in their parentage. These three durum wheat populations were phenotyped for FHB severity, anthesis date, anther retention, and plant height.

The phenotyping data across years revealed high genetic variation in FHB severity, expressed as AUDPC (area under disease progress curve), and anther retention among the test populations, indicating considerable genetic diversity. BOKU lines displayed the significantly lowest FHB disease severity compared to the other durum populations.

A significant positive correlation was detected between FHB severity and anther retention. Plants with higher percentage of retained anthers tend to have increased disease severity values. This finding suggests that floral trait contributes to resistance against initial infection of the pathogen. Additionally, anther retention is a trait which can be used for indirect selection to enhance FHB resistance in durum wheat.

This study also investigated the genetic architecture of anther retention within the progenies of the Capdur×BOKU experimental lines crosses. Populations were developed by crossing 'Capdur' with BOKU lines carrying the *Fhb1* allele, a major QTL for FHB resistance, as well as tall and short plants possessing the *Rht-B1a* (tall) and *Rht-B1b* (short) alleles. The results revealed high genetic variation, as indicated in the heritability estimates for FHB severity, anther retention, and plant height. Promising lines within the population that exhibited a desirable combination of moderate FHB resistance and short plant height were also identified, which is valuable for durum wheat breeding.

Keywords

Anther retention · *Fhb1* · resistance breeding · *Triticum durum*

Further reading

Buerstmayr M, Steiner B, Buerstmayr H (2020) Breeding for Fusarium head blight resistance in wheat - Progress and challenges. *Plant Breed* 139:429-454. DOI: 10.1111/pbr.12797

Skinnes H, Semagn K, Tarkegne Y, Marøy AG, Bjørnstad Å (2010) The inheritance of anther extrusion in hexaploidy wheat and its relationship to *Fusarium* head blight resistance and deoxynivalenol content. *Plant Breed* 129:149-155. DOI: 10.1111/j.1439-0523.2009.01731.x

Steiner B, Buerstmayr M, Wagner C, Danler A, Eshonkulov B, *et al.* (2019) Fine-mapping of the Fusarium head blight resistance QTL *Qfhs.ifa-5A* identifies two resistance QTL associated with anther extrusion. *Theor Appl Genet* 132:2039-2053. DOI: 10.1007/s00122-019-03336-x

Viviani A, Haile JK, Fernando WGD, Ceoloni C, Kuzmanović L, *et al.* (2025) Priority actions for Fusarium head blight resistance in durum wheat: Insights from the Wheat Initiative. *Plant Genome* 18:e20539. DOI: 10.1002/tpg2.20539

From Tillet to Tillecur – Historic milestones and current challenges in man’s race against the black dust

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Abstract

Bunt of wheat, also called “the black dust”, has been bothering farmers, breeders and researchers for almost 400 years based on historic documents. Two closely related diseases are summarized under the term “bunt of wheat”: common bunt, caused by the fungi *Tilletia caries* and *T. laevis*, and dwarf bunt, caused by *T. controversa*. They differ slightly in their infection characteristics: while common bunt is mainly seed-borne and not too sensitive when it comes to the environmental conditions it needs to invade its host, dwarf bunt is primarily soil-borne and requires the low temperature and high humidity provided by a continuous snow cover for successful infection.

Dwarf bunt, as its name suggests, causes pronounced reduction in plant height while plants infected with common bunt show less or even no stunting. Infections with bunt leads to losses in grain yield since kernels get replaced by so-called bunt balls – masses of fungal teliospores contained in a thin shell, shaped similar to wheat grains. These are shattered easily especially during harvest and release several millions of spores per bunt ball. Thereby, harvesting equipment and grain loads get contaminated, leading to losses in grain quality that can go as far as rendering the grain unmarketable. The fact that bunt infections happen at the seedling stage, but do not cause their typical symptoms until the grain-filling stage, posed a significant challenge for people in the past who were trying to discern the cause of the so-called “blackening of wheat”.

As early as 1637, reports about heavy losses in wheat harvests due to bunt infections are available from England and a hundred years later from Châtellerauld in France. Bunt was causing such severe problems, that a prize was set out at the Academy of Arts and Sciences of Bordeaux for the person, who could reveal the cause of this disease and find a cure for it. The winner was Mathieu Tillet who described the seed-borne origin of bunt and possible countermeasures in his dissertation in 1755. This was such a milestone that the smut fungi causing bunt were later named after Tillet and he is, even nowadays, the namesake for things like bunt resistant cultivars or treatments preventing bunt infections (e.g. Tillecur®). However, it took about 50 more years for people to find out that the organism infecting the wheat seeds was actually a fungus. This was achieved by Bénédict Prévost from Switzerland in 1807. Still,

the actual infection pathway remained unknown until 1859 when the German agricultural scientist Julius G. Kühn discovered that fungal hyphae penetrating the young wheat seedlings were the starting point for bunt infections. These gains in knowledge were, however, not immediately translated into effective countermeasures and the bunt problem remained a pressing one. In Canada, for example, bunt was even regarded as a potentially limiting factor for wheat production in general since losses of 30-40% of the total harvest were quite frequent at the turn to the 20th century.

In the early 1900s, systematic variety testing of all kinds of small grain cereals started with Otto von Kirchner and Carl Freiherr von Tubeuf in Hohenheim in Germany. As early as 1907, Joseph Faull in Canada discovered that the bunt pathogens are capable of causing partial infections in grains, making them a lot more difficult to detect and treat. Interestingly, this knowledge fell into oblivion during the second half of the century and is still not fully restored today.

Soon scientists realized that breeding for resistant cultivars was the best option they had in fighting bunt infections. One of the first breeding programs for bunt resistant cultivars was proposed by Adolf Gieseke from Germany in 1929. Only a few years later, Wallace Hanna and colleagues were able to discern the chemical compound trimethylamine as the cause of the distinct fishy smell bunt spores emit. In 1931, an important tool for bunt researchers was first introduced by Earl Norman Bressman: he proposed a differential set of wheat varieties to characterise the ten different resistance factors known at the time.

The year 1954 finally brought a major strike for mankind in the race against bunt: hexachlorobenzene was discovered as a systemically active fungicide compound that was for the first time also effective against soil-borne bunt infections. The technical advances in plant protection during the mid-1900s lead to an almost complete eradication of bunt in many parts of the major wheat growing areas, making research on resistance breeding appear rather superfluous. For scientists still working on bunt, the main focus during the following decades was the discrimination of bunt races and the classification of bunt resistance factors. For this purpose, they used the bunt differential set introduced in the early 1930s.

Between 1961 and 1976, differentials were exchanged, more lines were added, the classification system was modified and the today well-known *Bt*-designations for the individual factors were introduced. The last major update of the differential set took place in 1996 when Blair Goates described an expanded set of 15 differentials, all of which are still in use today. At the moment, efforts are ongoing to improve the set based on findings from recent years gained through molecular and genetic techniques that have become available since the last update.

Already during the 1980s, the organic movement began to gain ground and with it, interest in bunt resistance was renewed. Bans on pesticides in organic farming lead to the re-emergence of bunt in many wheat growing areas. This, in turn, fostered efforts in resistance breeding as well as research on alternative treatments for disease protection compliant with the organic standards. Since the early 2000s, methods like genetic mapping, genome-wide association studies and genomic selection have been applied in bunt research. Together with dropping genotyping costs, this lead to the localization of bunt resistance factors on specific wheat chromosomes and the development of molecular markers for these factors but also to new insights in pathogen genomics.

At BOKU, common bunt resistance has been a major research focus since more than a decade. Ongoing projects are dealing with

- selection schemes for developing high-performing and bunt resistant pre-breeding lines
- resistance gene isolation in mutant populations
- bunt resistance in *Aegilops tauschii* and *Triticum durum* and
- stacking of bunt resistance loci.

These benefit from a well-established phenotyping protocol and constant exchange with the international bunt community.

Keywords

Common bunt · dwarf bunt · *Tilletia caries* · *Tilletia laevis* · wheat

Further reading

Cherewick WJ (1953) Smut diseases of cultivated plants in Canada. Publ 887, Dept Agric, Ottawa. [<https://publications.gc.ca/site/eng/9.800905/publication.html>; accessed 28 Jan 2025]

Fischer GW, Holton CS (1957) Biology and control of the smut fungi. Ronald Press Co., New York. [<https://catalog.hathitrust.org/Record/001497647>; accessed 28 Jan 2025]

Goates BJ (1996) Common bunt and dwarf bunt. In: Wilcoxson RD, Saari EE (eds), Bunt and smut diseases of wheat: Concepts and methods of disease management, pp 12-25. CIMMYT, Mexico, D.F. [<https://repository.cimmyt.org/bitstream/handle/10883/1211/61965.pdf>; accessed 28 Jan 2025]

Holton CS, Purdy Jr LH (1954) Control of soil-borne common bunt of winter wheat in the Pacific Northwest by seed treatment. Plant Dis Rep 38:753-754. [<https://babel.hathitrust.org/cgi/pt?id=uc1.31175001860033&seq=767>; accessed 28 Jan 2025]

Tillet M (1937) Dissertation on the cause of the corruption and smutting of the kernels of wheat in the head and on the means of preventing these untoward circumstances (translated from the French by Humphrey HB). Am Phytopathol Soc, Ithaca, NY. DOI: 10.1094/9780890545201

Survey of potato growers' perception of climate change and its impacts on potato production in Germany, Switzerland and Austria

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Abstract

The DACH-region, referring to the German-speaking Central European countries Germany, Austria and Switzerland, has a long-standing tradition of potato cultivation and consumption. These three countries account for 21% of the potato growing area in the EU, including 44% of the organic potato growing area. Heat waves, droughts, heavy rainfall and floods associated with a changing climate pose challenges to potato production. Effective climate change mitigation strategies are needed to retain both high potato yield and quality.

In the frame of the Horizon 2020 project ADAPT (Accelerated Development of multiple-stress tolerant Potato; <https://adapt.univie.ac.at/>) we conducted a survey among European potato farmers. The survey was accessible online from December 2020 until April 2021 and was answered by 553 potato farmers from 22 different European countries. Responses from Austria ($n = 159$), Germany ($n = 79$), and Switzerland ($n = 53$) were scrutinized for regional similarities and differences.

DACH-region potato farmers reported in agreement that the changing climatic conditions had adversely impacted their potato production in the last ten years. Drought and heat were the most frequently mentioned environmental stress factors. That potato growers had noticed the impact of climate change on their potato production was reported by 98% of the respondents in Germany, 89% in Switzerland and 90% in Austria. Differences in the perception of these effects were observed between Austrian conventional (93%) and organic potato growers (83%), likely due to the geographical locations of the surveyed farms. Drought and heat are the most severe effects related to climatic changes in all three countries. In Austria, a total of 94% were affected by drought, with organic potato growers feeling the effects of drought more than conventional potato growers. The preferred adaptation strategy in all three countries was the planting of an adapted variety. Around 80% of the German and Swiss potato growers compared to 62% of the Austrian potato growers agreed that an adapted variety could mitigate climate change effects. The detailed analysis showed some notable regional differences. Drought was in the first place in Austria, whereas heat was mentioned more frequently in Ger-

many and Switzerland. More German and Swiss farmers reported to have access to at least partial irrigation. Although growing adapted varieties was favoured as a potential adaptation strategy in all three countries, more German and Swiss than Austrian potato growers count on adapted varieties. Overall, the results showed that effective and efficient climate change adaptation strategies need to be holistic and take into account regional differences and country-specific challenges.

Keywords

Climate change · farmer survey · *Solanum tuberosum*

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Further reading

Bomers S, Ribarits A, Kamptner A, Tripolt T, von Gehren P, *et al.* (2024) Survey of potato growers' perception of climate change and its impacts on potato production in Germany, Switzerland, and Austria. *Agronomy* 14:1399. DOI: 10.3390/agronomy14071399

von Gehren P, Bomers S, Tripolt T, Söllinger J, Prat N, *et al.* (2023) Farmers feel the climate change: Variety choice as an adaptation strategy of European potato farmers. *Climate* 11:189. DOI: 10.3390/cli11090189

Potato yield under drought and heat stress

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Abstract

The ADAPT (Accelerated development of multiple-stress tolerant potato) project investigated the molecular and phenotypic responses of potato to environmental stresses such as drought, heat and flooding. The goal of ADAPT was to develop new strategies to make potatoes fit for the challenging climatic conditions of the future. ADAPT combined the academic and applied expertise of 17 international project partners, including four potato breeders, the European Potato Trade Association (Europatat) and AGES. The work plan in six distinct work packages made use of methods in molecular biology, stress physiology, systems biology, analytics, molecular breeding and sophisticated engineering. Two of ADAPT's work packages (WPs) included field trials that were conducted in Austria and on other European sites. Here, we focus on the Austrian field trials.

From the ADAPT variety portfolio, 16 varieties were selected with a focus on representing a wide range of abiotic stress resistance (*i.e.* susceptible to tolerant). Varieties were obtained from the potato breeders involved in ADAPT: 'Acoustic', 'Lady Rosetta' and 'Musica' from Meijer Potato (Rilland, NL), 'Colomba' and 'Rosi' from HZPC (Joure, NL), 'Belmonda' from Solana (Hamburg, DE), and 'Erika', 'Valdivia', 'Chiara', 'Meireska', 'Ditta' and 'Graziosa' from NÖS (Meires, AT). In addition, 'Agata', 'Agria', 'Desiree' and 'Spunta' were tested as reference varieties. 'Graziosa' was replaced with 'Sound' in the second trial year. Three of the Austrian trial sites (Sierndorf, Großnondorf and Fuchsenbigl) are in the Pannonian climate zone with low annual precipitation and hot and dry summers. One trial site (Schwarzenau) is characterized by maritime-continental climate conditions with comparably higher annual precipitation. Sierndorf and Schwarzenau were managed according to organic farming practices, and in Fuchsenbigl the trials were either sprinkler-irrigated or received no irrigation. The trials were evaluated according to the Austrian VCU (Value for Cultivation and Use) programme. In addition to the standard programme, tuberization trials were set up. Additional plots with 2 replications per variety with 50 plants each were established under non-irrigated conditions. At three time points, 6 plants per replication were grubbed. All already formed tubers were counted and weighed. The assessment started in the first half of June, the second and third assessments followed about two and four weeks later. The following indices were collected by drones in cooperation with Blickwinkel Agrarconsulting (Kirchdorf am Inn, AT):

NDVI (Normalized Difference Vegetation Index), WDVI (Weighted Difference Vegetation Index), and CIRED (Chlorophyll Index based on NIR and RED band). Vegetation coverage was determined to investigate the development of the varieties. Environmental data were collected in cooperation with IoT Systems GmbH (Wolfsberg, AT).

Environmental sensors including soil sensors were installed at each trial site. Air and soil temperature, air humidity and soil moisture were measured every 20 minutes over the course of the growing season. Irrigation is a useful management strategy to increase potato yield in dry and hot years. Irrigation may help to overcome dry and hot conditions, especially under sandy soil conditions, and to keep soil temperatures at lower levels. Fig. 1 shows the temperature data obtained with the environmental sensors. The collected data clearly shows that the two trial years differed in particular concerning the onset of heat stress, showing comparably cold spring weather conditions.

The data collected by the drones was used to validate the observations on the other European sites, with the aim to evaluate how the data could contribute to indicate heat and drought stress tolerance of different varieties. Here, the major limitation was the difference between the conditions on the trial sites, which did not allow to make final conclusions on specific varieties. However, the correlation of drone data and obtained yield revealed promising possibilities to develop methods for yield prediction. As this is useful both for plant breeders and variety testers the outcome will be further evaluated.

The detailed examination of the onset of tuberization is not part of the standard VCU programme. Onset of tuberization can have a significant impact on the yield potential of potato varieties. The tuberization trials provided valuable gain in information concerning tuber development during the growing season and its impact on the final yield of different varieties (Fig. 2). Regarding the value of integrating tuberization into the regular VCU programme, the considerable additional effort for these assessments must be further evaluated.

The knowledge gained within ADAPT and the project's unique complementary expertise calls for continuing the work to bring the research results from this project into practice in breeding programmes or management recommendations for farmers.

Figure 1 Air temperature above crop canopy and soil temperature (20 cm depth) by trial site (FUC, Fuchsenbigl; GRO, Großnondorf; SIE, Sierndorf; SCH, Schwarzenau) and year (2022: left panels; 2023: right panels).

Figure 2 Development of tuber yield per plant for European potato varieties grown at Großnondorf, Austria, in 2022 (upper panels) and 2023 (lower panels). The varieties are grouped according to their maturity group classification. Tuber yield per plant (g) was assessed in the tuberization trials and in the VCU trial (harvested on 6th September of the respective year).

Keywords

Drone imaging · environmental stress · *Solanum tuberosum* · tuberization

Acknowledgement

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Project website

<https://adapt.univie.ac.at/>

Further reading

Kaier A, Beck S, Ingold M, Corral JM, Reinert S, *et al.* (2024) Identification of heat stress-related genomic regions by genome-wide association study in *Solanum tuberosum*. *Genomics* 116:110954. DOI: 10.1016/j.ygeno.2024.110954

Nicolas M, Torres-Pérez R, Wahl V, Cruz-Oró E, Rodríguez-Buey ML, *et al.* (2022) Spatial control of potato tuberization by the TCP transcription factor BRANCHED1b. *Nat Plants* 8:281-294. DOI: 10.1038/s41477-022-01112-2

Zagorščak M, Abdelhakim L, Rodríguez-Granados NY, Široká J, Ghatak A, *et al.* (2025) Integration of multi-omics data and deep phenotyping provides insights into responses to single and combined abiotic stress in potato. *Plant Physiol* 197:kiaf126. DOI: 10.1093/plphys/kiaf126

Differences in the yield-related phenotype between winter wheat lines in Japan and Germany

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Abstract

The average grain yield of winter wheat differs by approximately 20 dt ha⁻¹ between Japan and Germany. Japan's wheat production constitutes only 5% of Germany's, with the cultivated area accounting for merely 7% (DESTATIS, 2024). Consequently, over 85% of Japan's domestic wheat consumption relies on imports from the U.S., Canada, and Australia (Ministry of Agriculture, Forestry and Fisheries of Japan, 2024). To address this dependency, the Japanese government aims to enhance self-sufficiency by promoting the development of high-yielding, domestically adapted winter wheat varieties.

According to Walkowiak *et al.* (2020), Japanese wheat varieties are genetically isolated and show significant genetic divergence from European wheat varieties. Furthermore, there have been few efforts to incorporate European varieties into Japanese wheat breeding programs and no comprehensive comparative studies of the agronomic traits of Japanese and European varieties have been conducted. This lack of comparative research has led to an insufficient understanding of the specific agronomic traits of Japanese wheat varieties and which traits are required to improve grain yield.

In this study, we evaluated the differences in agronomic traits between 215 winter wheat breeding lines from the University of Hohenheim, Germany, and 200 winter wheat breeding lines from NARO Hokkaido, Japan. The aim was to identify key traits for improving the yield potential of Japanese varieties. We analyzed correlations among various traits to identify traits which are significantly impacting yield.

In total, 16 traits were investigated from March to August 2024 at the University of Hohenheim in Stuttgart (48.7°N, 9.2°E, 240 m a.s.l.): grain yield, heading date, maturity date, plant height, number of spikelets per ear, ear length, number of ears per m², leaf condition, NDVI and SPAD values. NDVIs were measured five times from March to May using GreenSeeker 2 (Nikon-Trimble Co.,

Ltd., Tokyo). NDVI1 was measured on 21st March, NDVI2 on 28th March, NDVI3 on 11th April, NDVI4 on 3rd May, and NDVI5 on 10th May. SPAD1 and SPAD2 values were measured immediately after heading and one month later using the atLEAF[®] device (FT Green LLC, Wilmington). Leaf condition (*i.e.* damage by diseases) was evaluated on a scale from 1 to 9 one month after heading. A score of 1 indicates fully healthy leaves, a score of 9 indicates fully damaged leaves (Agricultural Research Centre, 1986). Grain yield, ear length and number of spikelets per ear were also evaluated at Eckartsweier (48.3°N, 7.5°E). Field experiments were also conducted at NARO Hokkaido (42.8°N, 143.1°E, 90 m a.s.l.) from 2015 to 2019. In these trials 13 traits were evaluated: grain yield, grain protein content (GPC), thousand kernel weight (TKW), test weight (TW), heading date, maturity date, number of spikelets per ear, ear length, leaf condition, number of ears per m², plant height and SPAD values. SPAD values were measured immediately after heading and one month later using the SPAD-502plus (Konica Minolta Co., Ltd., Tokyo). Values for grain yield, ear length and number of spikelets per ear in the German field trials were as best linear unbiased estimators (BLUEs). For the other traits, only data from the Hohenheim trial were available in the German dataset. Estimates for heritability for yield, ear length, and number of spikelets per ear exceeded 0.50 in the German trials, while in the Japanese trials, heritability for the same traits exceeded 0.70. This result indicates a strong genetic dominance of Japanese breeding lines and can also be attributed to the larger number of trial sites in Japan.

The study revealed a significant difference in grain yield between German and Japanese germplasm. Mean grain yield in Eckartsweier and Hohenheim was 85.3 dt ha⁻¹ compared to 61.7 dt ha⁻¹ in Japan. Ear length of German lines was on average 10 mm longer than in Japanese lines and the number of spikelets per ear was 21 in German lines compared to 18 spikelets in Japanese lines. In contrast, Japanese lines exhibited a higher average number of ears per m² with 688 compared to 589 in the German lines. Additionally, the average plant height of German lines was 7.6 cm longer than that of the Japanese lines. These results highlight different

Figure 1 Correlation network plots between grain yield and yield-related traits for **a** German and **b** Japanese wheat germplasm

breeding strategies: grain yield of German wheats is more related to larger ears (*i.e.* longer ears with more spikelets), whereas in Japanese wheats the number of fertile tillers per unit area is more important. The higher grain yield in Germany may be also due to a shorter winter and a higher mean temperature, thus resulting in a longer vegetation period and higher growing degree days. We analyzed the correlations between yield-related traits and yield for the German and Japanese wheat lines (Fig. 1). For the German lines, no single trait showed a significant correlation with yield, including NDVI values, suggesting that yield results from a balanced contribution of various traits. In contrast, for the Japanese lines, yield showed a significant correlation with SPAD values and leaf condition one month after heading, indicating that chlorophyll content and leaf health during this critical growth period are essential for improving yield in Japanese varieties. In addition, while GPC and TW showed a negative correlation with grain yield, TKW showed a positive correlation. These results suggest that Japanese varieties tend to have higher yields when TKW is higher, and lower yields when GPC and TW are higher, indicating that improving TKW is also essential for improving yield in Japanese varieties.

Since this trial was conducted under different environmental conditions, future studies will be necessary under German and Japanese environmental conditions to investigate and clarify the differences in agronomic traits between German and Japanese wheat lines.

Keywords

SPAD · trait correlation · *Triticum aestivum* · yield components

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References

- Agricultural Research Centre (1986) Wheat survey standards, 1st Ed. (in Japanese). National Agriculture and Food Research Organization, Tsukuba. [https://www.naro.go.jp/publicity_report/publication/archive/files/komugi_chousakizyun.pdf; accessed 3 Feb 2025]
- DESTATIS (2024) Field crops and grassland. Arable land after the main groups and crops. Statistisches Bundesamt, Wiesbaden. [<https://www.destatis.de/EN/Themes/Economic-Sectors-Enterprises/Agriculture-Forestry-Fisheries/Field-Crops-Grassland/Tables/arable-land-after-the-main-groups-and-crops.html>; accessed 31 Dec 2024]
- MAFF (2024) Crop status survey (upland and flooded rice, wheat, soybeans, buckwheat, sweet potatoes, feed crops, industrial crops). Ministry of Agriculture, Forestry and Fisheries of Japan (MAFF), Tokyo. [https://www.maff.go.jp/j/tokei/kouhyou/sakumotu/sakkyou_kome/index.html#mugi; accessed 31 Dec 2024]
- Walkowiak S, Gao L, Monat C, Haberer G, Kassa MT, *et al.* (2020) Multiple wheat genomes reveal global variation in modern breeding. *Nature* 588:277-283. DOI: 10.1038/s41586-020-2961-x

Quality evaluation of einkorn from Austria for bread production

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Abstract

Einkorn has some nutritional advantages and appears to be better tolerable, but is more demanding in terms of processing. Furthermore, only little is known about its quality and processing properties. To overcome this knowledge gap, a total of 11 einkorn samples were examined in this study, nine from different cultivars grown under organic conditions in Lower Austria and two modern cultivars. The produced refined flours were analysed in respect to flour (flour yield, ash and protein content, sedimentation volume, falling number) and rheological properties by the farinograph method. Baking performance was evaluated based on baking trials adapted for einkorn with addition of dried sourdough and pregelatinised flour. Less high milling yields compared to common and spelt wheat were observed for einkorn. The obtained ash contents were largely consistent with the Austrian flour type W700. Furthermore, the results displayed low protein contents and very low values for sedimentation, except for variety 'Monomax'. In contrast, falling numbers were within an acceptable range, only one sample showing values below 200 s. The farinograph indices revealed low quality of flours from all samples, but again 'Monomax' showed superior properties among all the einkorn samples. The specific volumes of the breads ranged from 2.5 to 2.9 mL g⁻¹ with the highest values for 'Monomax' and 'Mv Alkor'. However, no relationship was found between flour quality indices and final bread volumes.

Keywords

Baking · flour quality · hulled wheat · organic farming · *Triticum monococcum*

Introduction

Einkorn (*Triticum monococcum* L. subsp. *monococcum*), a diploid hulled wheat (2n=2x=14), offers nutritional benefits and appears to be better tolerated by people suffering from non-celiac wheat sensitivity (NCWS) due to its altered protein profile, e.g. amylase-trypsin inhibitors (ATIs) are totally missing or can be found only in

marginal concentrations. Although the protein and gluten content is higher compared to free-threshing wheat species, in general less immunogenic proteins can be detected by immunosorbent assays (e.g. ELISA). Moreover, due to the different protein profile, gluten from einkorn can be digested to a higher extent resulting in less released T-cell epitopes and thus reduced allergenicity (Janovská *et al.*, 2021).

In addition to these advantages, the cultivation and use of einkorn also presents some challenges. Low yield, tall plant height and lodging are the major drawbacks of einkorn cultivation. Further, an additional step for dehulling contributes to significantly higher costs compared to common wheat and durum flours. And, einkorn has a weak gluten structure, which results in a very soft and sticky dough. On the other hand, it's high resistance to diseases and N efficiency makes einkorn perfectly suitable for low-input agriculture such as organic farming (Janovská *et al.*, 2021; Afzal *et al.*, 2022).

The production of einkorn in Austria is still very small and, thus, statistical data are collected together with emmer. Their organic cultivation area was 1313 ha in 2023, which is marginal compared to organic winter wheat (45840 ha in 2023) and organic spelt wheat (7111 ha in 2023). Furthermore, the production of einkorn varies considerably from year to year. The largest proportion (>80%) is produced under organic conditions and the major part is harvested in Lower Austria (AGES 2024). In contrast to spelt, no quality requirements are assessed for einkorn at all and it is not included in Austrian VCU (value for cultivation and use) trials. Therefore, information regarding agronomic performance and baking quality of individual varieties are scarce. These circumstances together with lower yields and difficult processability due to a low dough stability and high stickiness make wider commercialisation difficult.

Although a few research projects were focused on einkorn and emmer, data on einkorn quality are still insufficient, especially for Austria. The aim of this work was to fill this knowledge gap and to characterize the baking quality of einkorn produced directly by farmers in Austria.

Material and methods

Two modern varieties, ‘Monomax’ and ‘Monoverde’, were provided by Südwestdeutsche Saatzucht GmbH & Co. KG (Rastatt, DE). The other samples were all cultivated in Lower Austria by local farmers under organic management and harvested in 2023. These samples were kindly provided and dehulled by the Dyk Mill (Raabs an der Thaya, AT). Milling of dehulled kernels was performed by a MLU-202 roller mill (Bühler, Uzwil, CH). Due to the soft texture of einkorn compared to bread wheat and durum, the grains were conditioned to only 14% moisture. Flour yield was calculated based on the weight of obtained white flours in respect to the initial kernel mass.

The flours were analysed for ash content (ICC Stand. Meth. No. 104/1), crude protein content (ICC 159), Zeleny sedimentation volume (ICC 116/1) and Hagberg falling number (ICC 107/1). The rheological properties of the dough were determined by the farinograph (ICC 115/1). Baking tests were carried out according to D’Amico *et al.* (2024) with some minor modifications. Instead of individual settings based on the dough development time for each flour, a fixed kneading time of 7 min at low intensity (level 2/3 in a TEDDY Varimixer (Varimixer a/s, Broendby, DK) was applied. All samples were baked in duplicate trials, resulting in a total of six breads. Volume measurements of the final breads were made by a VolScan VSP600 instrument (Stable Micro Systems, Godalming, UK). Statistical evaluation was performed using SPSS vers. 26 software (IBM, Armonk, NY).

Table 1 Description of einkorn samples

Sample No.	Genotype	Flour yield (%)	Ash content (%)	Protein content (%)	Sedimentation test (mL)	Falling number (s)
1	Monomax	59.9	0.82	14.6	20.2	394
2	Monoverde	59.8	0.77	14.2	7.1	389
3	RLH*	58.0	0.60	13.5	6.7	225
4	RLH*	55.3	0.71	10.4	7.3	353
5	RLH*	60.1	0.60	13.0	5.3	289
6	RLH*	60.1	0.63	13.6	7.0	178
7	RLH*	54.6	0.60	10.9	5.9	288
8	Mv Alkor	62.4	0.62	9.8	6.2	239
9	Mv Alkor	58.0	0.65	12.9	6.1	361
10	unknown	60.6	0.73	10.5	6.6	402
11	unknown	52.0	0.61	11.1	9.0	374

*RLH: Raiffeisen Lagerhaus seed multiplication; genotype unknown

Table 2 Farinogram characteristics of einkorn flours

Sample No.	Genotype	WAC ¹ (%)	DDT (min)	Dstab (min)	DSoft12 (FU)	FQN
1	Monomax	60.2	1.89	1.98	111	32
2	Monoverde	58.1	1.21	1.02	122	19
3	RLH*	60.0	1.46	0.64	212	20
4	RLH*	57.0	1.18	0.83	158	17
5	RLH*	60.1	1.46	0.77	190	21
6	RLH*	61.6	1.24	0.52	233	16
7	RLH*	56.9	1.24	0.71	199	17
8	MV Alkor	55.2	1.18	0.92	142	18
9	MV Alkor	58.8	1.22	0.65	224	17
10	unknown	56.4	1.28	0.87	132	19
11	unknown	55.4	1.31	1.08	130	20

*RLH: Raiffeisen Lagerhaus seed multiplication; genotype unknown

¹ WAC, water absorption capacity; DDT, dough development time; Dstab: Dough stability; DSoft12, Dough softening 12 minutes after peak; FQN, Farinogram quality number

Results and discussion

The milling step was optimized for einkorn by adjusting the moisture for conditioning. The amount of water was reduced to achieve a moisture content of 14% due to the softness of einkorn grains. In industrial mills, yields of 79–82% are accomplished for common wheat, which are commonly lower at pilot or lab scale. In Austrian VCU trials milling yields of around 65–71% for bread and 58–69% (based on Austrian flour type W550) for spelt wheat were achieved using the same roller mill (AGES, 2024). The examined einkorn samples revealed distinctly lower flour yields of 52–62.4% (Table 1), which can be explained by the small grain size of einkorn. Similar results are reported by Afzal *et al.* (2022). Ash contents between 0.61 and 0.82% were determined, which mainly fit well with specifications of the Austrian flour type W700. No relationship was found between ash content and flour yield ($r = 0.018$, $p > 0.05$).

Grain protein content within the samples was quite low, ranging from 9.8% to 14.6%. In general, einkorn has a high grain protein content, which is usually significantly higher than that of bread wheat and even spelt (Janovská *et al.*, 2021; Afzal *et al.*, 2022). The organic production, climatic conditions of the growing season and the inferior soil fertility might be responsible for the obtained results. Sedimentation volumes were at a very low level for all samples, except for 'Monomax'. Other studies found similar low values for einkorn as well (Afzal *et al.*, 2022). However, extremely low values <10 mL were not reported by other studies and could be explained, as for grain protein content, by environmental conditions. Falling numbers showed high values and were at a similar level to spelt cultivated in Austria. For spelt, a minimum falling number of 220 s is required to ensure good baking performance (AGES, 2024), which has been reached by all einkorn samples except for No. 6.

Rheological measurements of einkorn doughs showed water absorption capacities of 55.4–61.4%. Similar water absorption capacities (*i.e.* 54–62%) were determined for 10 different spelt genotypes grown in the Austrian VCU trials from 2021 to 2023. All other parameters were at a very poor level compared to common wheat and even to spelt wheat. Very short dough development times and stability with a high degree of dough softening were observed during mixing. Only 'Monomax' reached a level comparable to spelt. The low dough stability and high softening behaviour confirmed the inferior dough processing quality of einkorn, which must be taken into account during processing. Generally, the differences in mixing properties within this sample set were small. The highest stability and lowest softening during mixing and, thus, the highest farinogram quality number, were observed for 'Monomax'.

The results of the baking tests showed a narrow range of bread volumes, from about 2.5 to 2.9 mL g⁻¹ flour. This might be due to the optimized recipe and procedure for einkorn bread production. The addition of pregelatinized flour increases dough viscosity and stability. Furthermore, the rather low falling numbers of sample No. 3 and especially No. 6 did not lead to poor baking results, which can be explained by the addition of dried sourdough. The acidification of the dough inhibits amylase enzymes. This effect is even more pronounced compared to common sourdough fermentation, because the lower pH is reached from the beginning of the dough preparation.

Nevertheless, the used baking process resulted in significant differences among the investigated samples as shown in Fig. 1. Samples No. 1 ('Monomax') and No. 8 ('Mv Alkor'), followed by sample No. 4 achieved the highest baking volumes. No trend regarding baking quality was observed between the tested varieties due to high variability within the samples from the same

Figure 1 Volume of einkorn breads produced from different cultivars and batches (1: Monomax; 2: Monoverde; 3-7: RLH: Raiffeisen Lager Haus reproduction; 8-9: MV Alkor; 10-11: unknown; small letters indicate significant differences based on ANOVA with p -level of 0.05)

genotype. Although all einkorn samples were cultivated under organic management, it is likely that environmental factors such as soil fertility and site specific climatic conditions have an effect on the final quality.

The results no significant correlation between quality indices and baking volume. This is in contrast to Afzal *et al.* (2022), who found SDS sedimentation, dough energy and resistance determined with the extensograph as good indicators for the baking quality. This divergence can be explained by the small number of samples of this study compared to the study by Afzal *et al.* (2022) with 148 genotypes of einkorn carried out in Germany. Additionally, extensograph parameters were not evaluated in this study due to the limited sample amount. Another study with spelt from Austria showed that only the dough energy of extensograph values correlated well with the volume of the baked breads, whereas all other quality-determining parameters did not show any significant correlation (D'Amico *et al.*, 2024).

The data presented about einkorn from organic cultivation by local farmers are highly valuable for the primary sector and processing companies such as bakeries. Furthermore, the results obtained provide an important basis for the quality classification of einkorn and reflect the great influence of the environment. Nevertheless, further tests are necessary, especially under standardized conditions over several years in VCU trials, to be able to achieve a proper quality rating as already established for other wheat species.

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References

AGES (2024) Österreichische Beschreibende Sortenliste 2024, Landwirtschaftliche Pflanzenarten. Schriftenreihe 21/2024. Österreichische Agentur für Gesundheit und Ernährungssicherheit GmbH (AGES), Wien. [https://bsl.baes.gv.at/fileadmin/BSL/pdf-Version/BSL_2024.pdf; accessed 5 Feb 2025].

Afzal M, Longin F, Pflieger F, Huintjes N, Ruhrländer M, *et al.* (2022) Agronomie und Verarbeitungseigenschaften von 148 verschiedenen Einkornsorten im Vergleich zu Weizen. Projektbericht, Universität Hohenheim [https://www.uni-hohenheim.de/uploads/media/GrossesEinkornProjekt_de.pdf; accessed 5 Feb 2025]

D'Amico S, Bischoff J, Grüniger W, Flamm C, Reiter E, *et al.* (2024) Etablierung eines Vollkornbackversuches für Dinkel aus biologischem Anbau. Getreide, Mehl und Brot 2/2024.

Janovská D, Hlásná Čepková P, D'Amico S, Brandolini A, Grausgruber H (2021) Developing hulled wheat-based cereal products with enhanced nutritional properties: emmer, einkorn and spelt. In: Beta T (ed.), Improving the nutritional and nutraceutical properties of wheat and other cereals, pp 267-291. Burleigh Dodds Science Publishing Ltd, Sawston. DOI: 10.19103/AS.2021.0087.20

Stupice – 100+ years of spring barley breeding

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Abstract

Stupice breeding station was established by the breeding company Selecta in 1921 to meet the company's demand of breeding crops that prefer fertile soils (*i.e.* sugar beet and spring barley). Since 1924, Stupice became the main breeding station of Selecta, growing from an ordinary farm with just 15 ha of fields. In 1929, the first breeding facilities were built followed by a more intensive development from 1937 to 1939 with the construction of a large selection hall, breeders workshops and company headquarters (Fig. 1). During WW2, breeding continued under the aegis of the company Lochow-Petkus. In 1948, Selecta was nationalized and incorporated into the national breeding company Oseva. At that time, there were successful breeding programmes in wheat, spring barley and pulses, ornamental plants and vegetables like tomatoes, celery or carrots in Stupice. Between 1961 and 1972, Stupice was the main breeding station specialized in mutation breeding. However, the only result of this decade long effort was variety 'Atlas'. Between 1977 and 1981, another large construction phase was finished by adding modern storage halls, garages, laboratories, workshops and greenhouses (Fig. 2). After 1993, Stupice became the core breeding station of Selgen a.s., focusing on spring and winter wheat, and spring barley. Currently, the spring barley breeding programme continues with around 200

new crosses, 2500 of 10 m² plots, 12000 ear-to-row progenies and 10 ha of multiplication every year. Table 1 displays spring barley varieties successfully released from the Stupice breeding programme since 1926.

In 2017 and 2018, seeds of 13 historical varieties from Stupice were multiplied and since 2019 these varieties were sown every year together with 3 modern varieties in a demonstration trial with 1 or 2 replicates and 10 m² plot size. Plots were scored for heading date, diseases, and lodging. After harvest, samples of the grain were analysed for quality and grain yield was determined. Micro malting of grain samples was carried out with the 2019 harvest.

The results of the experiment showed a continuous improvement in grain yield and lodging tolerance (Fig. 3), and confirmed an ≈1% annual increase in yield as revealed by earlier research studies. The highest yielding old variety was 'Stupicky starocesky' (Fig. 4), with a yield level almost comparable to the first 'Diamant' line variety 'Atlas', although being 50 years older. As expected, the old varieties showed low malting quality compared to modern varieties. In 3 old varieties, significant haze of sweet wort was detected (Table 2).

Figure 1 Construction of the company headquarter adjacent to already used selection hall and breeders workshops in 1938

Figure 2 New part of Stupice breeding station with modern greenhouses, office and laboratory building and storage halls in 1981.

Figure 3 Effect of 40 years of breeding: plant height and lodging tolerance of ‘Stupicky plnozrnný’ (left plot) and ‘Atlas’ (right plot) after flag leaf emergence and before harvest in 2023.

Table 1 List of spring barley varieties released by the Stupice breeding programme.

Year of release	Variety	Origin/Information
1926	Stupicky Hanacky	selection from Hana landraces
1926	Selecty Hanak	selection from Hana landraces
1926	Stupicky Starocesky	selection from Czech landraces
1926	Selecty Velejemny	selection from Czech landraces
1934	Hanacky Kargyn (Selecty)	Hana × Kargyn (cross by Selecta)
1937	Selecty Kneifel	selection from Kneifel (P-13; Opava line)
1937	Stupicky Plnozrnný	Starnovsky Kneifel × Stupicky Hanacky
1976	Atlas	Mutant SS55 × Diamant
1983	Mars	ST 9060/70 × Abed Lofa
1992	Akcent	Salome × EP 79
1995	Amulet	HE 2591 × Salome
1996	Atribut	KM V 3/83 × BR 2174
1996	Celestina	registered in Spain
2000	Advokat	registered in Hungary
2007	Aksamit	Century × ((Perun × TU 33) × Atribut)
2009	Advent	HE 7792 × Madonna
2010	Musa 19	Nordus × Saxo; registered in Uruguay
2013	Arthur	Madonna × ST 4397/01
2014	Francin	ST 3578 × Sebastian
2018	Spitfire	Calcule × Westminster

Figure 4 Grain yield (t ha⁻¹) of the tested spring barley varieties (2019-2024 means)

Table 2 Malting quality of the tested spring barley varieties (micro-malting results of 2019 harvest): MQI, malting quality index; Protein, grain protein content; Starch, grain starch content; Ex, extract; RE45, relative extract; K, Kolbach index; Dia P, diastatic power; F. Atten., final attenuation; Fria, friability; BGw, beta-glucan content in wort; H12°, haze of wort (12°); H90°, haze of wort (90°); Vis., viscosity; Hom. F., homogeneity by friabilimeter; PUG, partially unmodified grain; G. Kern, glassy kernels; Bulk d., bulk density.

Variety	MQI	Protein	Starch	Ex	RE45	K	Dia P	F. Atten.	Fria	BGw	H12°	H90°	Vis.	Hom.F.	PUG	G. Kern	Bulk d.
	9-1	%	%	%	%	%	uVK	%	%	mg/l	EBC	EBC	mPas	%	%	%	kg
Stupicky hanacky	1,8	16,5	59,3	75,5	41,8	35,4	215	78,5	43,2	339	1,19	1,07	1,585	78,3	21,7	2,2	56,4
Selecty Hanak	1,8	13,8	59,9	77,9	36,4	34,9	315	78,6	57,9	292	2,24	2,55	1,547	88,1	11,9	0,3	55,2
Stupicky starocesky	1,5	13,9	59,4	76,6	35,4	32,4	354	78,3	51,4	486	4,47	5,65	1,637	85,1	14,9	1,9	54,0
Selecty velejemny	1,1	13,8	58,9	77,6	34,8	31,0	232	74,4	44,2	558	2,65	3,20	1,721	77,9	22,1	1,1	56,4
Hanacky Kargyn	1,7	14,3	59,5	77,8	36,2	36,4	204	80,5	52,4	395	2,02	2,40	1,619	84,2	15,8	1,1	56,0
Stupicky plnozrnny	1,9	15,1	58,4	77,5	39,7	36,2	222	75,7	50,9	309	2,39	2,66	1,590	81,0	19,0	1,7	55,6
Atlas	2,6	12,0	62,5	81	37,1	39,2	275	80,0	69,4	172	7,73	6,25	1,556	92,7	7,3	0,2	55,6
Mars	2,8	11,8	62,7	81,3	36,1	42,3	297	80,2	80,0	223	4,82	4,05	1,533	97,7	2,3	0,1	56,4
Akcent	2,3	12,1	60,9	80,3	40,9	39,1	288	75,6	68,8	338	0,62	0,57	1,564	91,4	8,6	1,2	56,0
Amulet	1,9	11,7	62,8	80,9	34	40,4	325	75,6	77,1	157	0,71	0,61	1,503	96,5	3,5	0,2	56,4
Atribut	2,7	12,0	61,8	81	40,2	41,7	277	78,0	77,0	294	0,57	0,57	1,537	96,1	3,9	0,9	55,6
Aksamit	1,5	11,0	62,7	81,2	32,8	35,5	313	77,5	72,1	232	0,59	0,51	1,525	92,5	7,5	1,2	54,8
Advent	2,1	11,1	63,2	81,2	34,3	35,4	258	80,4	82,5	221	0,49	0,46	1,493	98,4	1,6	0,2	56,0
Arthur	4,9	10,7	63,3	82,0	37,4	43,1	301	81,1	86,2	215	1,73	1,77	1,502	95,8	4,2	0,2	68,3
Francin	6,2	10,4	64,2	82,7	40,2	43,7	353	78,2	88,5	157	2,48	2,71	1,524	99,1	1,4	0,2	69,3
Spitfire	8,7	11,2	62,7	83,3	44,6	45,6	370	81,7	99,4	39	0,75	0,69	1,424	99,6	0,6	0,1	63,3

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Further reading

Chloupek O (2011) Historie šlechtění sladového ječmene na území České republiky. Kvasny Prum 57: 180-181 (in Czech). DOI: 10.18832/kp2011015

Kosař K, Psota V, Mikyška A (2004) Barley varieties suitable for production of the Czech-type beer. Czech J Genet Plant Breed 40: 137-139. DOI: 10.17221/3712-CJGPB

Psota V, Hartmann J, Sejkorová Š, Loučková T, Vejražka K (2009) 50 Years of progress in quality of malting barley grown in the Czech Republic. J Inst Brew 115: 279-291. DOI: 10.1002/j.2050-0416.2009.tb00382.x

www.saatgut-austria.at